

Development of Reproducible Metagenomic Approaches for Skin and Wound Microbiome Analysis

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Dedication

I wish to dedicate this thesis to my loving husband, Daniel Freiheit, and parents, Gretchen Grey and Fritz Freiheit, whose hard work and sacrifices have given me a life full of opportunities. It is because of them and their unwavering support that I have been able pursue and now achieve my dreams. These words cannot possibly do justice for everything that they have given me, but I hope they can begin to understand how thankful I am to have them all in my life.

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Abstract

The skin microbiome, the collective genetic material of resident microorganisms, plays a vital role in immune defence, barrier integrity, and wound healing. Disruption of these communities is linked to infections, chronic wounds, and impaired recovery, making accurate characterisation clinically significant. Yet research remains constrained by high levels of host DNA contamination, computational and technical demands, and limited reproducibility in bioinformatic workflows. Overcoming these barriers requires methodological innovation and reproducible analysis frameworks.

Replication of landmark skin microbiome studies underscored the need for reproducibility, particularly robust workflow management, transparent data tracking, and comprehensive archiving. Building on these insights, a modular Snakemake workflow was developed to integrate multiple taxonomic classifiers through a consensus voting system, improving species-level resolution while reducing researcher burden. Adaptive sequencing was advanced as a solution to host contamination through the optimised application of ReadFish on standard research workstations. This approach achieved an approximately 50% reduction in human DNA while preserving overall community structure and increasing microbial diversity and evenness across skin microbiome samples. This work represents the first demonstration of adaptive sequencing in skin microbiome data.

Building on these advances, adaptive sequencing was extended to directly target clinically significant microbes. This novel approach enabled the enrichment of antimicrobial-resistant pathogens, achieving ~40% greater detection without distorting overall community composition. By uniting host DNA removal with pathogen and resistance gene enrichment, this study demonstrates a powerful proof-of-concept for adaptive sequencing as a diagnostic tool, advancing the field toward rapid, clinically actionable microbiome profiling. Together, these studies show how reproducible workflows and adaptive sequencing can overcome technical bottlenecks, enhance pathogen and resistance gene detection, and accelerate the translation of microbiome research into clinical and public health applications.

Open research statement

Open research is the systematic application of transparency, accessibility, and reproducibility across the scientific process. In life sciences, this means making data, methods, and computational workflows publicly available to enable independent validation (Peng, 2011). Several international frameworks define best practice, such as the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) that emphasize data stewardship to maximize discoverability and reuse (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016). The Transparency and Openness Promotion (TOP) Guidelines outline standards for sharing data, code, and materials (Nosek *et al.*, 2015).

At a policy level, United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI) open access and data policies and United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Open Science Recommendation embed openness into research culture. Together, these frameworks establish openness as a prerequisite for reliable and impactful science (Wehn *et al.*, 2024), a principle reflected in genomics and microbiome research where openness is central to reproducibility. Uploading sequence data to repositories such as International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC), GenBank, and Sequence Read Archive (SRA) is now routine practice, enabling broad availability and independent validation (Mirzayi *et al.*, 2021).

Yet openness must be balanced with ethical obligations because data protection legislation can restrict access to human-associated genomic information, complicating studies involving clinical samples. These challenges are especially relevant in human microbiome research, where openness must coexist with participant privacy, informed consent, and responsible data release (Bonomi *et al.*, 2020). Striking this balance ensures that openness strengthens, rather than compromises, the integrity, reproducibility, and clinical relevance of microbiome science.

Standards and challenges in microbiome research

Current norms in microbiome research prioritise open and reproducible practices, including data sharing, standardized metadata, and transparent computational workflows. Large-scale efforts such as the Human Microbiome Project (HMP) and the Earth Microbiome Project (EMP) established community standards for sampling, sequencing, and analysis, providing reference datasets that underpin cross-study comparability (Huttenhower *et al.*, 2023; Thompson *et al.*, 2017). Building on these frameworks, microbiome studies now typically deposit raw sequencing data in repositories like the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) or Sequence Read Archive (SRA), accompanied by metadata following the Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence (MIxS) standard (Cernava *et al.*, 2022).

Public analysis platforms such as MG-RAST and Qiita enable data exploration and comparative studies, while workflow systems including QIIME 2 and Snakemake provide reproducible pipelines with built-in provenance tracking and environment management (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Mölder *et al.*, 2021). Together, these practices reflect the field's aspiration to make microbiome research transparent, reusable, and clinically relevant (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Knight *et al.*, 2018), but significant challenges remain as microbial communities are dynamic, sequencing methods vary across laboratories, and pipelines evolve rapidly (Costea *et al.*, 2017).

Reproducibility is often hindered by incomplete metadata, poor documentation, and limited availability of raw data or code. Many published datasets lack sufficient metadata for reuse (Cernava *et al.*, 2022; Jurburg *et al.*, 2020), and missing workflow details frequently prevent replication even when raw data are accessible (Bindels *et al.*, 2025). Privacy and ethical considerations further complicate studies involving human participants (Rhodes, 2016). In practice, resource limitations, technical barriers, and publication pressures lead to many studies falling short of practical reproducibility. Replication studies are rare, and comprehensive reproducibility remains more aspirational than routine (Clausen and Willis, 2022).

The gap between community standards and everyday practice highlights a central challenge, although openness is widely recognized as essential, its consistent implementation lags behind. Addressing this shortfall is especially urgent in clinically relevant areas such as skin and wound microbiomes, where reproducible research directly influences diagnostic reliability and therapeutic development (Boxberger *et al.*, 2021). Framing reproducibility as a scientific imperative, rather than an administrative burden, is vital to ensure microbiome research delivers robust insights and improved patient outcomes.

Embedding reproducibility across the research lifecycle

Reproducibility was embedded in the design of this thesis from the outset, shaping both wet-lab and bioinformatics approaches. Transparency and openness at each stage ensured that the work is verifiable, reusable, and positioned to inform future studies.

Data and metadata deposition

All sequencing data generated here was archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007), following INSDC standards (Cochrane *et al.*, 2016). Metadata were prepared according to the MIxS specifications (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2011), with additional descriptors aligned to host-associated guidelines (Cernava *et al.*, 2022). Sensitive information was safeguarded by removing human-derived sequences before deposition.

Bioinformatics workflows and code

All scripts, standalone tools, and complete workflows were archived in publicly accessible Zenodo repositories (DOIs: 10.5281/zenodo.17753185; 10.5281/zenodo.17752049; 10.5281/zenodo.17752062), with persistent identifiers for citation. Development was version-controlled on GitHub, with repositories mirrored to Zenodo at each release. Bioinformatic workflows were developed in Snakemake (Mölder *et al.*, 2021), using community templates (Snakemake-workflows, 2024) to support modularity, reproducibility, and automated reporting.

Software environments and documentation

Analyses were conducted in controlled environments, with all software and package versions specified in Conda YAML files (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) to ensure reproducibility across operating systems. Documentation included annotated scripts, README instructions, and detailed parameter logs, capturing intermediate steps and parameter choices to allow workflows to be replayed exactly.

Wet laboratory procedures and protocols

Laboratory protocols, including sample collection, DNA extraction, and sequencing preparation, were fully standardized to minimize variability. Step-by-step methods were archived on protocols.io (DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1), providing permanent, citable records of experimental procedures. Consistency was further supported through validated kits and standardized laboratory practices.

Verification and research integrity

Reproducibility was reinforced by systematic version control, redundant backups, and electronic lab notebooks in Notion and GitHub. Workflows were periodically rerun in fresh computational environments to confirm that results could be regenerated from raw data and configuration files. Statistical analyses employed robust models and multiple-testing corrections (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995) to ensure validity. Intellectual property was safeguarded by formally citing all software dependencies and external data sources.

All results, raw data, scripts, workflows, and protocols from this thesis are openly available, with both wet-lab and computational methods fully documented. Reproducibility was built into every stage, from standardized laboratory protocols and public data deposition to version-controlled workflows and permanent archiving, ensuring that the work can be validated, reused, and extended. These practices strengthen the reliability of findings and support their translation into clinical contexts, establishing openness and reproducibility as integral to advancing human microbiome research.

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List of abbreviations

AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
API	Application Programming Interface
ARG	Antimicrobial Resistance Gene
ARP	Antimicrobial Resistance Potential
ASAW	Adaptive Sequencing Analysis Workflow
AST	Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing
ATCC	American Type Culture Collection
BAM	Binary Alignment/Map
BCID2	Blood Culture Identification 2
BED	Browser Extensible Data
BLAST	Basic Local Alignment Search Tool
BP	Base Pairs
BWA	Burrows-Wheeler Aligner
CARD	Comprehensive Antibiotic Resistance Database
CAT	Contig Annotation Tool
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRAN	Comprehensive R Archive Network
CRISPR	Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECM	Extracellular Matrix
EMBL-EBI	European Molecular Biology Laboratory's European Bioinformatics Institute
EMP	Earth Microbiome Project
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
ESBL	Extended-Spectrum β -Lactamase
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FASTA	Fast Alignment Search Tool
FASTQ	FASTA + Quality
GATK	Genome Analysis Toolkit
GC	Guanine–Cytosine
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GTDB	Genome Taxonomy Database
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
HMP	Human Microbiome Project
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTS	High-Throughput Sequencing
IBD	Inflammatory Bowel Disease

INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KEGG	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes
LCA	Lowest Common Ancestor
MEGAN	MEtaGenome ANalyzer
MGE	Mobile Genetic Element
MIxS	Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence
MLCA	Modified Lowest Common Ancestor
MMCAW	Metagenomic Microbiome Combination Analysis Workflow
MMI	Minimap2 Index
MRSA	Methicillin-Resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
Mu-DNA	Modular Universal DNA
NCBI	National Centre for Biotechnology Information
NCTC	National Collection of Type Cultures
NGS	Next-Generation Sequencing
NMDS	Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling
ONT	Oxford Nanopore Technologies
OPAL	OPTimization And evaLUation
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PCoA	Principal Coordinates Analysis
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PhiX	ΦX174 phage DNA sequencing control
QC	Quality Control
QIIME	Quantitative Insights Into Microbial Ecology
RGI	Resistance Gene Identifier
RNA	Ribonucleic Acid
SAM	Sequencing Alignment/Map
SCFAs	Short-Chain Fatty Acids
SRA	Sequence Read Archive
SURPI	Sequence-Based Ultra-Rapid Pathogen Identification
T2T	Telomere-to-Telomere
TOML	Tom’s Obvious, Minimal Language
TOP	Transparency and Openness Promotion
TSV	Tab-Separated Values
UKRI	United Kingdom Research and Innovation
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
USD	United States Dollar
VFDB	Virulence Factors Database
WMS	Whole metagenome sequencing
YAML	YAML Ain’t Markup Language

Chapter 1 Introduction

The human microbiome contains tens of trillions of microorganisms, roughly equal in number to human cells, and collectively encodes over three million genes, vastly outnumbering the ~20,000 genes of the human genome (Qin *et al.*, 2010; Sender *et al.*, 2016). Comprised of bacteria, fungi, viruses, and archaea, it is integral to physiology and health (Turnbaugh *et al.*, 2007; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Its genetic diversity underpins nutrient absorption, protection against pathogens, and metabolic homeostasis, highlighting its central role in human biology (Ma *et al.*, 2024; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Microbiome composition is driven by genetics, diet, environment, and lifestyle, with distinct communities inhabiting the gut, skin, oral cavity, respiratory tract, and urogenital system (Kennedy and Chang, 2020). These communities perform site-specific functions essential to health and adapt dynamically across the lifespan, influencing resilience and recovery from illness (Dong and Gupta, 2019; Zheng *et al.*, 2020).

The gut microbiome, the largest and most studied community, supports digestion, neurological signalling, and immune regulation. It metabolizes complex carbohydrates, synthesizes vitamins such as K and B, and provides colonization resistance against pathogens (Krajmalnik-Brown *et al.*, 2012; Valdes *et al.*, 2018). Dysbiosis is implicated in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), obesity, diabetes, and neurological disorders (Wu and Wu, 2012; de Vos *et al.*, 2022). Beyond the gut, the skin microbiome, composed mainly of bacteria with contributions from fungi and viruses, forms a protective barrier and regulates immune responses (Grice and Segre, 2011). In parallel, the respiratory microbiome, spanning the nasal passages, throat, and lungs, supports immune defence and pathogen resistance; disruption is associated with asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and increased infection risk (Lira-Lucio *et al.*, 2020; O'Dwyer *et al.*, 2016; Zhao *et al.*, 2023). The oral microbiome, another key community, colonizes teeth, gums, and tongue, aiding food breakdown and preventing pathogen overgrowth (Deo and Deshmukh, 2019). Dysbiosis contributes to dental caries, periodontal disease, and systemic conditions such as cardiovascular disease (Hu *et al.*, 2024).

Beyond local effects, the microbiome influences systemic health by regulating immunity, modulating inflammation, and affecting brain function and mood through the gut–brain axis (Marano *et al.*, 2023; Zheng *et al.*, 2020). Its composition is strongly shaped by lifestyle, not only through diet but also by exercise, stress, and sleep, all of which affect microbial balance and resilience (Conlon and Bird, 2014; Redondo-Useros *et al.*, 2020). Antibiotic overuse further disrupts communities, increasing infection risk and chronic disease (Queen *et al.*, 2020; Ramirez *et al.*, 2020). These findings have spurred interest in microbiome-based therapies, including probiotics, prebiotics, and microbiome-modulating interventions (Pires *et al.*, 2024; Zhou *et al.*,

2024). Understanding this ecosystem is essential for strategies that preserve microbial balance, improve health, and address diverse diseases. Ultimately, harnessing the microbiome may enable personalized medicine tailored to specific microbial communities to prevent disease and enhance well-being (Kashyap *et al.*, 2017; Laterza and Mignini, 2022).

1.0 The skin microbiome

Among human microbial communities, the skin microbiome is one of the most dynamic and influential. It harbours diverse bacteria, fungi, viruses, and archaea that interact closely with the host (Grice and Segre, 2011; Byrd *et al.*, 2018). This ecosystem protects against pathogens, supports skin health, and contributes to dermatological conditions. Advances in high-throughput sequencing have expanded understanding of its composition and functional roles in both local and systemic health, highlighting opportunities for novel therapeutic interventions (Yi *et al.*, 2024; Wei *et al.*, 2021).

1.0.1 Community composition and functions

The skin microbiome is a diverse ecosystem dominated by bacteria, which remain the most prevalent and extensively studied members (Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023; Byrd *et al.*, 2018). Its composition reflects the heterogeneous conditions of the skin surface, shaped by temperature, humidity, sebum production, pH, and sweat gland activity. These variables create distinct niches across body sites, supporting specialised microbial communities (Smythe and Wilkinson, 2023; Skowron *et al.*, 2021). The principal bacterial phyla include Firmicutes, Proteobacteria, Actinobacteria, and Bacteroidetes, with genera such as *Staphylococcus*, *Corynebacterium*, and *Cutibacterium* (formerly *Propionibacterium*) distributed according to site-specific conditions (Figure 1.1) (Grice and Segre, 2011; Skowron *et al.*, 2021). Sebum-rich areas such as the face and scalp favour *Cutibacterium*, whereas moist regions like the armpits and groin are dominated by *Corynebacterium* and *Staphylococcus* (Yerushalmi *et al.*, 2019; Skowron *et al.*, 2021). Environmental factors (e.g., climate and hygiene) and host factors (e.g., genetics, age, and diet) further shape these bacterial communities (Swaney *et al.*, 2023; Smythe and Wilkinson, 2023).

Figure 1.1 Skin microbiome site types, locations, and common examples of microbes.

Fungi, though less studied, are essential to the skin microbiome and vary by site. *Malassezia* predominates in sebaceous regions, while *Candida* and *Aspergillus* are more common in compromised skin or immunocompromised hosts (Figure 1.1). Although usually commensal, fungal imbalances contribute to dandruff, seborrheic dermatitis, and infections (d'Enfert *et al.*, 2021; Niedźwiedzka *et al.*, 2024). Viruses also shape the skin microbiome, such as bacteriophages that regulate bacterial populations and maintain stability (Naureen *et al.*, 2020; Alkhalil, 2023), while human-associated viruses such as herpesviruses persist latently and can cause conditions such as cold sores or genital herpes (Grinde, 2013). Archaea, though less abundant and studied, further increase complexity. Species such as *Methanobrevibacter*, commonly found in sebaceous areas (Figure 1.1), represent an emerging focus of skin microbiome research (Umbach *et al.*, 2021).

Collectively, the skin microbiome contributes to local and systemic health. It provides a barrier against pathogens, with commensals such as *Staphylococcus epidermidis* competing for space and nutrients while producing antimicrobial peptides (Sanford and Gallo, 2013; Severn and Horswill, 2023). It modulates immune activity by influencing both innate and adaptive responses; beneficial microbes promote anti-inflammatory cytokine production that preserves homeostasis and prevents excessive activation (Lunjani *et al.*, 2021; Zheng *et al.*, 2020). The microbiome also participates in sebum metabolism, with *Cutibacterium* breaking down lipids

into antimicrobial fatty acids that regulate microbial growth and reinforce barrier function (Yu and Li, 2024). Other metabolites, such as lactic acid, acidify the skin and inhibit pathogenic colonisation. Dysbiosis, broadly defined as a disruption to the composition, diversity, or function of a microbial community associated with disease, can drive inflammation and disorders including acne, eczema, and psoriasis, although the concept remains context-dependent and lacks a universally accepted definition due to variability across body sites and individuals (Petersen and Round, 2014; Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Carmona-Cruz *et al.*, 2022). Through these roles, the skin microbiome is fundamental to maintaining skin health and resilience (Costa and Horswill, 2022; Smythe and Wilkinson, 2023).

1.0.2 Influences, implications, and innovations

The skin microbiome composition is shaped by host and environmental factors that interact across the lifespan. Age is a key determinant, and infants acquire microbes through maternal contact, hormonal changes during puberty and aging drives further alterations, and in older adults reduced diversity contributes to dryness and thinning (Rapin *et al.*, 2023; Shen *et al.*, 2023; Shibagaki *et al.*, 2017). Genetics also shapes traits such as skin type, sebum production, and immune function (Heng *et al.*, 2021). These host-driven influences are modified by environmental exposures, including climate, humidity, and pollutants, which can reshape communities. Lifestyle further contributes; for example, nutrient-rich diets foster beneficial microbes, whereas high-fat or high-sugar diets favour pathogenic species (Skowron *et al.*, 2021; Dong and Gupta, 2019). Finally, hygiene practices and skincare products can disrupt microbial balance, predisposing to dysbiosis and skin disease (Pinto *et al.*, 2021).

Balanced microbial communities are critical for skin health, and dysbiosis underlies several dermatological disorders. In acne vulgaris, for instance, overgrowth of *Cutibacterium acnes* in sebaceous glands promotes inflammation and clogged pores (Yu and Li, 2024). Atopic dermatitis, by contrast, involves reduced diversity and an overrepresentation of *Staphylococcus aureus*, which exacerbates inflammation (Hwang *et al.*, 2021). Similarly, psoriasis is characterised by decreased diversity and inflammatory bacterial overgrowth (Celoria *et al.*, 2023), while seborrheic dermatitis is strongly linked to *Malassezia* proliferation in sebum-rich areas (Li *et al.*, 2022). Collectively, these examples highlight how microbial imbalance drives disease and underscore the importance of maintaining community stability for skin health and prevention (Liu *et al.*, 2023; Zhu *et al.*, 2023).

Growing knowledge of skin microbial communities is driving therapeutic innovation. Probiotics, prebiotics, and topical agents are under investigation for restoring balance in conditions such as acne, eczema, and psoriasis (Knackstedt *et al.*, 2020; Alves *et al.*, 2024).

Bacteriophage therapy, which selectively targets pathogenic bacteria while sparing commensals, is another promising approach (Natarelli *et al.*, 2023). Continued research will likely uncover deeper links between microbial communities and systemic health, with potential to revolutionise dermatological care and personalised medicine. By fostering a balanced and diverse microbial environment, personalised strategies and transformative therapeutic interventions may be developed, strengthening skin resilience, supporting repair, and ultimately promoting healthier skin and improved quality of life.

1.1 Microbes and wound healing

The skin microbiome has received growing attention for its critical role in wound healing (Canchy *et al.*, 2023). This community not only protects against infection but also contributes to effective tissue repair (Yang *et al.*, 2024). Recent studies highlight the interplay between microbial communities and host immune responses, showing how microorganisms influence healing outcomes. These insights underscore the potential of microbiome-targeted interventions, particularly for chronic wounds (Yang *et al.*, 2024; Versey *et al.*, 2021).

1.1.1 Microbial dynamics in wound repair

The skin, the body's first line of defence, is a major site for microbial colonisation. Under normal conditions, the skin microbiome maintains balance, protecting against pathogens, regulating immunity, and supporting tissue health (Schommer and Gallo, 2013; Byrd *et al.*, 2018). Injury disrupts this equilibrium, creating a vulnerable wound environment colonised by both resident and external microbes (Verbanic *et al.*, 2020). The interplay between these microbial communities and the host immune system can determine whether a wound heals or progresses to a chronic state. Balanced populations support healing by suppressing pathogens, whereas dysbiosis can drive infection, inflammation, and delayed repair (Loesche *et al.*, 2017; Zielińska *et al.*, 2023). Importantly, the wound microbiome has emerged as a key determinant of healing outcomes and represents a promising therapeutic target (Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023; Yang *et al.*, 2024).

Wound healing proceeds through four overlapping stages: haemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and maturation/remodelling (Trinh *et al.*, 2022). Microbial composition influences each phase via interactions with host immunity (Zielińska *et al.*, 2023). During haemostasis and inflammation, vasoconstriction prevents bleeding and immune cells are recruited. Certain commensals, such as *S. epidermidis*, can promote favourable immune responses by inducing anti-inflammatory cytokines (Severn and Horswill, 2022). By contrast, pathogens like *S. aureus* exacerbate inflammation, delay closure, and damage tissue (Mariani and Galvan, 2023).

Persistent imbalance during this phase predisposes to chronic wounds. In the proliferative phase, new tissue forms and angiogenesis supplies nutrients and oxygen (Verbanic *et al.*, 2020).

Microbial metabolites, such as short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), stimulate keratinocytes and fibroblasts, supporting tissue regeneration and extracellular matrix (ECM) production (Xiao *et al.*, 2022). Pathogens can disrupt this phase by releasing toxins that impair tissue formation (Verbanic *et al.*, 2020). During maturation and remodelling, collagen and the ECM reorganise to restore structural integrity (Loesche *et al.*, 2017). Maintaining microbial balance is essential for effective healing, as it prevents unchecked inflammation and pathogen dominance (Loesche *et al.*, 2017). A diverse microbiome fosters repair and may regulate scar formation. For example, *S. epidermidis* and *Corynebacterium* spp. can inhibit pathogen overgrowth and promote tissue repair, potentially reducing excessive scarring (Yang *et al.*, 2024; Byrd *et al.*, 2018).

Acute wounds, in particular, benefit from high diversity, which sustains a favourable microbial environment (Grice *et al.*, 2010). In contrast, chronic wounds such as diabetic ulcers often exhibit reduced diversity and pathogen dominance, notably by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, perpetuating inflammation and impaired healing (Loesche *et al.*, 2017). Restoring diversity in chronic wounds is a promising therapeutic strategy. Interventions under investigation include probiotics and microbiome-modulating treatments designed to enhance microbes that support repair while suppressing those that hinder it. These approaches, though still emerging, may help break the cycle of chronic inflammation and poor healing, offering new avenues for wound management (Verbanic *et al.*, 2020).

1.1.2 Pathogens and innovations in healing

While many microbes support wound repair, pathogenic microorganisms can exploit wounds, complicating healing and increasing the risk of systemic infection (Zielińska *et al.*, 2023). *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *Escherichia coli* are frequently implicated in chronic wounds, deploying virulence factors such as tissue-damaging toxins and immune evasion mechanisms (Serra *et al.*, 2015). These pathogens also often form biofilms, dense microbial communities encased in a self-produced matrix, that resist antibiotics and immune clearance (Pai *et al.*, 2023). For example, *S. aureus* contributes to biofilm development in diabetic foot ulcers, while *P. aeruginosa* causes aggressive tissue destruction in poorly vascularised wounds (Malone *et al.*, 2017).

Controlling pathogens is critical to prevent infection and support repair, making the interplay between the skin microbiome and wound healing a key focus for innovation, particularly in chronic wounds where dysbiosis is common (Grice and Segre, 2011). Current strategies seek not only to suppress harmful organisms but also to restore balance. For instance,

antibiotic stewardship aims to target pathogens precisely, limiting resistance while preserving commensals (Ventola, 2015). Complementary biological approaches are also emerging, including probiotics that introduce beneficial microbes directly into wounds and prebiotics that supply nutrients to support their growth, together enhancing diversity and fostering a repair-conducive environment (Bădăluță *et al.*, 2024). Bacteriophage therapy also offers a promising approach, using viruses to selectively eliminate harmful bacteria while sparing commensals, reducing infection risks and helping counter antibiotic resistance (Sawa *et al.*, 2024).

In parallel, advanced wound dressings are being developed that incorporate microbiome-modulating technologies, from releasing antimicrobial agents to promoting beneficial colonisation (Malone *et al.*, 2017). As understanding of microbial roles in repair deepens, such innovations highlight a shift toward personalised wound care. Probiotics, bacteriophages, and other microbiome-focused treatments together have the potential to accelerate healing, reduce the burden of chronic wounds, and improve outcomes (Singer and Dagum, 2008). Realising these benefits, however, requires equally robust diagnostics to monitor wound status and microbial dynamics, as even the most advanced therapies are limited without accurate, real-time characterisation of infections. Integrating diagnostic precision with therapeutic strategies across the stages of repair may ultimately transform wound management and enhance quality of life worldwide (Loesche *et al.*, 2017).

1.2 Traditional approaches

Modern diagnostic methods for wound infections and microbiome analysis build on traditional approaches (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Grice *et al.*, 2010). Conventional techniques remain central in dermatology, wound care, and infectious disease management, primarily supporting pathogen identification, microbial monitoring, and treatment decisions (Boxberger *et al.*, 2021; Ersanli *et al.*, 2023); however, these methods are limited in accuracy, scope, and resolution (Loesche *et al.*, 2017; Schommer and Gallo, 2013). As the field advances, emerging innovations promise more comprehensive insights, underscoring the need for refined approaches to fully realise the potential of microbiome research (Ma *et al.*, 2024; Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023).

1.2.1 Diagnostic methods for wound infection

Clinical assessment remains one of the most basic and widely used methods for diagnosing wound infections. Clinicians rely on visual and physical examination to detect redness, swelling, heat, pain, and exudate, along with systemic indicators such as fever and elevated white blood cell counts (Li *et al.*, 2021). This approach is non-invasive, cost-effective, and widely accessible, making it valuable for initial screenings and in resource-limited settings;

however, it is inherently subjective, depending heavily on clinical expertise (Table 1.1). Such subjectivity complicates differentiation between colonisation and active infection, increasing risks of misdiagnosis, overtreatment, or undertreatment (Ding *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2020).

Table 1.1 Traditional diagnostic methods for wound infection diagnosis.

Method	Description	Advantages	Limitations
Clinical Assessment	Visual/physical exams detect infection signs (e.g., redness, swelling); systemic indicators (e.g., fever) considered.	Non-invasive, cost-effective, accessible.	Subjective; may misinterpret colonization as infection; risk of misdiagnosis.
Swab Cultures	Collects wound bed samples for microbial growth on media.	Widely available, cost-effective.	Contamination risk; slow (24–72 hours); misses less dominant species.
Tissue Biopsies	Removes wound tissue for analysis.	Accurate; diagnoses chronic infections.	Invasive, painful; requires skilled personnel; may yield insufficient material.
Fluid Aspiration	Extracts wound fluid with a syringe.	Useful for deep infections.	Invasive, limited material may hinder diagnosis.
Gram Staining	Categorizes bacteria (Gram-positive/negative) via staining and microscopy.	Rapid preliminary insights.	Lacks specificity; limited for polymicrobial infections.
AST	Tests microbial susceptibility to antibiotics.	Tailors treatments; reduces resistance.	Time-intensive; requires isolated pathogens; risk of inappropriate antibiotic treatment.

After clinical assessment, swab cultures are among the most common diagnostic techniques. A sterile swab is used to collect a sample from the wound bed, which is streaked onto growth media, incubated, and analysed to identify pathogens (Edwards *et al.*, 2024). Swab cultures are inexpensive and widely available, but they have significant limitations. They often fail to capture the full microbial landscape, missing less-dominant species, and are prone to contamination, which reduces accuracy. Results also require 24–72 hours, delaying treatment decisions (Table 1.1) (Edwards *et al.*, 2024; Li *et al.*, 2021). Tissue biopsies and fluid aspiration, however, provide more precise diagnostic data. Biopsies involve removing a small piece of wound tissue, while fluid aspiration extracts wound fluid with a syringe (Rondas *et al.*, 2013).

Biopsies are particularly useful for deep-seated or chronic infections, but they are invasive, painful, and require skilled personnel. In addition, fluid aspiration may yield insufficient material, complicating analysis (Table 1.1) (Li *et al.*, 2021). Gram staining is another traditional diagnostic tool, categorising bacteria as Gram-positive or Gram-negative based on cell wall properties. Staining and microscopic examination provide rapid preliminary insights

into wound microbiota (Tripathi *et al.*, 2025); however, Gram staining lacks specificity and sensitivity, it cannot identify species or detect minor populations in polymicrobial infections, limiting its use in complex cases (Table 1.1) (Powers-Fletcher and Smulian, 2023; Altmann *et al.*, 2025).

Once pathogens are identified, antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) is used to evaluate their resistance or susceptibility to antibiotics. In AST, isolates are exposed to different antibiotics to determine growth inhibition (Gajic *et al.*, 2022). Although AST remains the gold standard for tailoring therapies, it is time-intensive and depends on prior successful pathogen isolation, which is not always achievable (Table 1.1) (Salam *et al.*, 2023). Delays or inaccuracies in diagnosis may also postpone appropriate intervention, increasing the risk of infection progression, systemic complications, and potentially fatal outcomes (Ma *et al.*, 2024; Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023). Traditional diagnostic methods have been foundational to wound care and microbiology, but their limitations, including time, subjectivity, invasiveness, and restricted scope, underscore the need to integrate advanced approaches that can better address the complexities of wound infections (Vo and Trinh, 2025).

1.2.2 Skin microbiome analysis methods

In research as in clinical diagnostics, early studies of the skin microbiome relied heavily on culture-based techniques, in which samples are cultivated on growth media under specific conditions to identify viable microorganisms. While straightforward and effective for detecting culturable microbes, these methods fail to capture the many skin microorganisms that cannot be grown under standard laboratory conditions (Skowron *et al.*, 2021). Consequently, culture-based approaches provide only a partial view of the microbiome, limiting insight into its true diversity. Microscopy has also played a foundational role, often paired with staining techniques to visualise microbial communities (Gotschlich *et al.*, 2019). By preparing and staining samples on slides, researchers can examine microbial morphology and spatial arrangement; however, like Gram staining, microscopy lacks precision for species-level identification and cannot resolve complex microbial interactions or community dynamics (Kim *et al.*, 2024).

To address these gaps, biochemical and serological tests, such as catalase and coagulase assays, have traditionally been used to detect skin-associated pathogens. These tests are rapid and effective for identifying specific microbes, making them useful for targeted diagnostics (Gajic *et al.*, 2022). Their scope, however, is limited, offering little information about overall microbial diversity or ecological interactions (Salam *et al.*, 2023). Phenotypic profiling, which evaluates functional traits such as metabolic activity and enzymatic capacity, has provided deeper insights into microbial roles. Despite this utility, phenotypic approaches are labour-

intensive and do not capture the broader community interactions critical to understanding the skin microbiome as an ecosystem (Liu *et al.*, 2022). These limitations highlight the need for alternative methods that can provide a more comprehensive and clinically relevant picture.

1.2.3 Challenges and emerging solutions

Traditional diagnostic methods for wound infection and skin microbiome analysis, though historically valuable, are insufficient for modern clinical and research needs. They detect only culturable organisms, representing a fraction of the skin microbiome (Skowron *et al.*, 2021; Byrd *et al.*, 2018). Culture-based methods and AST are time-intensive, delaying treatment decisions. Subjective approaches such as clinical assessment and microscopy introduce variability through reliance on individual interpretation (Gotschlich *et al.*, 2019; Grice and Segre, 2011). These methods also fail to capture polymicrobial community dynamics, including rapid shifts in dominant and opportunistic species, and are vulnerable to contamination during sample collection and processing, which compromises accuracy (Zielińska *et al.*, 2023). Although still relevant in resource-limited settings and acute care scenarios, traditional diagnostics cannot adequately address the complexity of microbial ecosystems or rapidly evolving clinical demands (Ranjan *et al.*, 2016; Thompson *et al.*, 2017).

Next-generation sequencing (NGS) and other molecular methods provide a transformative solution. These approaches detect non-culturable organisms, enable comprehensive profiling of microbial communities, and generate faster, more reliable diagnostic insights (Janda and Abbott, 2007). Integrating NGS into clinical workflows represents a critical evolution in medical microbiology, offering unprecedented resolution of microbial diversity and dynamics (Xu and Hsia, 2018). By accurately identifying pathogens, polymicrobial interactions, and rapidly shifting microbial community dynamics, NGS can inform targeted, personalised therapies and reduce unnecessary broad-spectrum antibiotic use, thereby helping to limit antimicrobial resistance (Nafea *et al.*, 2024). While conventional approaches provided the foundation for current practice, continued progress depends on advanced, integrative strategies. High-throughput sequencing (HTS) technologies, in particular, have become central to this shift, paving the way for deeper insights into microbial ecology, improved infection management, and the next generation of microbiome research (Chiu and Miller, 2019).

1.3 High-throughput sequencing

Traditional methods for diagnosing wound infections and analysing the skin microbiome have provided essential insights but remain limited in capturing the full complexity of microbial ecosystems and their interactions. HTS has transformed the field by enabling culture-

independent analysis that reveals microbial diversity, composition, and function (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Almeida *et al.*, 2019). By overcoming many of the constraints of conventional microbiology, HTS offers deeper understanding of the human microbiome and its role in health and disease (Pollock *et al.*, 2018; Thompson *et al.*, 2017). This transformative approach is reshaping microbiome research and clinical practice, supporting more accurate diagnostics, improved treatments, and personalised care (Liu *et al.*, 2022; Janda and Abbott, 2007).

1.3.1 Techniques in microbiome research

One of the most widely used molecular techniques in microbiome research is 16S rRNA gene sequencing, which targets conserved regions of the bacterial ribosomal RNA gene to identify and classify bacterial species (Figure 1.2). This method is valued for its ability to rapidly profile bacterial communities in a cost-effective manner with relatively low computational demands (Johnson *et al.*, 2019; Quince *et al.*, 2017); however, it is restricted to bacteria, excluding viruses, fungi, and archaea, and offers only limited taxonomic resolution, making it less effective for distinguishing closely related species (Schloss, 2018).

Figure 1.2 Example process of next generation sequencing from a mixed microbial sample with a comparison of metagenomic and amplicon sequencing, such as 16S method.

Whole metagenome sequencing (WMS) provides a broader view by sequencing all genetic content, capturing bacteria, archaea, fungi, and viruses while enabling functional analyses such as pathway reconstruction and resistance profiling (Almeida *et al.*, 2019; Nayfach

et al., 2021). Its drawbacks include higher costs, DNA quality requirements, and advanced bioinformatics needs (Pollock *et al.*, 2018). Shotgun metagenomics, a form of WMS based on random DNA fragmentation, provides higher resolution for detecting novel genes, pathways, and host–microbe interactions but generates complex datasets that are difficult to interpret and prone to contamination (Navgire *et al.*, 2022; Qin *et al.*, 2010).

Metatranscriptomics provides complementary insight by sequencing RNA to capture gene expression and active pathways, offering understanding of dynamic microbial responses (Franzosa *et al.*, 2018). Challenges include RNA instability, technical complexity, and high cost (Jiang *et al.*, 2016). Emerging methods such as single-cell sequencing and long-read technologies, such as PacBio and Oxford Nanopore, are overcoming these limitations, enabling more accurate genome assembly and characterisation of complex communities and their distribution across human body sites (Wu and Schmitz, 2023; Wrighton, 2021).

HTS applications have revealed distinct microbial communities across body sites, such as *Firmicutes* and *Bacteroidetes* in the gut, *Staphylococcus* and *Cutibacterium* on the skin, and *Streptococcus* and *Porphyromonas* in the oral cavity (Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2017; Hou *et al.*, 2022). Dysbiosis in these niches is linked to disease, including inflammatory bowel disease, obesity, and cancer in the gut (Lynch and Pedersen, 2016; Hrcir, 2022), eczema, psoriasis, and acne in the skin, and periodontal and systemic conditions such as cardiovascular disease in the oral cavity (Kilian *et al.*, 2016; Jia *et al.*, 2018). Recent advances in WMS and metatranscriptomics further reveal microbial functions in nutrient metabolism, immune modulation, vitamin and neurotransmitter synthesis, and interspecies interactions (Fan and Pedersen, 2021; Hou *et al.*, 2022).

1.3.2 Applications and current challenges

HTS has transformed microbiome research by supporting applications that span from clinical diagnostics to environmental monitoring, while also introducing new challenges in data analysis and interpretation (Human Microbiome Project Consortium, 2012; Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2017). Its applications extend to biomarker discovery, antimicrobial resistance monitoring, and linking microbiome composition to diet, lifestyle, and health outcomes (Quince *et al.*, 2017). These capabilities underscore its potential in diagnostics, therapeutics, and public health (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Despite this promise, significant challenges remain. Technical issues include variability in sample collection, sequencing biases, and the computational burden of large datasets, which require robust bioinformatics pipelines (Pollock *et al.*, 2018; Franzosa *et al.*, 2018).

Accurate taxonomic classification and functional annotation are further constrained by poorly characterised microbes (Almeida *et al.*, 2019). In addition, distinguishing causation from correlation in microbiome–disease associations remain a major limitation (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Human microbiome composition is also highly variable across populations and can be influenced by ethnicity, geography, climate, diet, hygiene practices, cultural behaviours, age, and environmental exposures, complicating cross-study comparisons and reducing reproducibility (Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023; Byrd *et al.*, 2018). Temporal fluctuations in microbial communities further increase analytical complexity, particularly when attempting to distinguish stable disease-associated signatures from normal variation (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Large HTS datasets also increase the risk of false-positive associations due to multiple statistical comparisons, making false discovery rate (FDR) correction essential for reducing spurious findings and improving confidence in microbiome analyses (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995).

Ethical and regulatory considerations, including data privacy and standardisation of diagnostics, also present barriers to translation (Rhodes, 2016). Emerging solutions include integrative multi-omics approaches, such as combining HTS with proteomics and metabolomics, to provide a more comprehensive view of host–microbe interactions (Jansson and Baker, 2016; Knight *et al.*, 2018). Long-read sequencing technologies, including PacBio and Oxford Nanopore, further enhance resolution, enabling accurate genome assembly and better characterisation of complex communities (Wu and Schmitz, 2023; Wrighton, 2021). Advances in computational tools, particularly artificial intelligence and machine learning, are improving data interpretation and predictive modelling (Topol, 2019). Together, these developments illustrate both the opportunities and barriers in applying HTS to clinical and translational microbiome research, highlighting the need for specialised approaches such as metagenomics to capture the full scope of microbial communities.

1.4 Metagenomic analysis

Metagenomics applies high-throughput sequencing (HTS) directly to environmental or host-associated samples to characterise the collective genetic material of microbial communities (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Almeida *et al.*, 2019). By shifting focus from individual isolates to entire ecosystems, metagenomic analysis enables simultaneous profiling of taxonomic composition and functional potential. This approach has been particularly influential in human microbiome research, where it provides insight into microbial diversity, ecological interactions, and the genetic basis of traits such as antimicrobial resistance and pathogenicity (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018; Knight *et al.*, 2018).

1.4.1 Methods and challenges in metagenomics

Metagenomics begins with sample collection and DNA extraction, which underpin all downstream analyses. DNA extraction protocols must recover high-quality nucleic acids while minimising contamination from host or environmental DNA (Sergaki *et al.*, 2018; Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2017). Inefficient extraction can bias results by underrepresenting microbes with more resilient cell walls, while external contamination may obscure microbial signals (Costea *et al.*, 2017; Karstens *et al.*, 2019). The two sequencing approaches that dominate metagenomics are shotgun metagenomics and amplicon sequencing. Shotgun metagenomics randomly sequences all DNA in a sample, providing comprehensive insights into taxonomic composition, functional potential, and metabolic pathways (Table 1.2) (Quince *et al.*, 2017).

Table 1.2 Summary of metagenomic sequencing methods.

Method	Description	Advantages	Challenges
Shotgun Metagenomics	Random sequencing of all DNA within a sample to assess taxonomic composition and functional potential.	Comprehensive insights into microbial diversity and function; captures all domains of life.	High cost; requires advanced bioinformatics pipelines; sensitive to contamination.
Amplicon Sequencing	Targets specific marker genes, such as 16S rRNA (bacteria/archaea) or ITS (fungi).	Cost-effective; ideal for studying microbial diversity; low computational requirements.	Limited to specific taxa; provides minimal functional insights.
Meta-transcriptomics	Sequencing of RNA to study active microbial genes and pathways.	Identifies active functions and dynamic responses to environments.	RNA instability; high technical complexity; expensive.
Single-Cell Sequencing	Sequencing individual microbial cells for high-resolution insights into rare or unculturable taxa.	Resolves functional heterogeneity; useful for studying individual microbes.	Labor-intensive; expensive; limited throughput.
Multi-Omics Integration	Combines metagenomics with transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics.	Offers holistic insights into microbial functions and host-microbe interactions.	Complex data integration; requires advanced computational tools.

Shotgun metagenomics is well suited for studying microbial interactions but, when performed with short-read technologies such as Illumina, often struggles to assemble complete genomes in repetitive or complex regions (Almeida *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, amplicon sequencing targets marker genes such as 16S rRNA for bacteria and archaea or ITS regions for fungi, providing efficient community-level profiling but limited functional insight (Table 1.2) (Knight *et al.*, 2018). Once sequencing is complete, data analysis proceeds through several

linked steps. Preprocessing removes low-quality reads and contaminants (Ewels *et al.*, 2020), while taxonomic classification assigns sequences to microbial taxa using databases such as SILVA, Greengenes, or GTDB, though gaps in reference collections can still cause errors or ambiguities (Parks *et al.*, 2018).

Functional annotation links genes to pathways and metabolic networks using resources such as KEGG, MetaCyc, or eggNOG, though predictions can be unreliable for poorly characterised genes (Liu *et al.*, 2022). Building on this, statistical analyses assess diversity, community composition, and ecological patterns (Jansson and Hofmockel, 2018); however, several challenges complicate these steps, such as sequencing errors that can distort results (Zhao *et al.*, 2020), short-read assemblies that often fail to resolve complex genomic regions (Almeida *et al.*, 2019), and annotation inaccuracies that further limit interpretation (Liu *et al.*, 2022). In addition, the sheer scale of metagenomic datasets demands considerable computational resources and expertise (Knight *et al.*, 2018).

Advances are helping to address these obstacles through improvements across sequencing, quality control, and reference resources. Long-read platforms such as PacBio and Oxford Nanopore now enable near-complete genome assemblies and greater resolution of complex genomic structures (Kim *et al.*, 2024; Amarasinghe *et al.*, 2020). At the same time, enhanced quality control protocols reduce contamination and safeguard data integrity (Ewels *et al.*, 2020; Karstens *et al.*, 2019). In parallel, the expansion of genome databases is improving the reliability of both taxonomic and functional annotations (Parks *et al.*, 2018; Nayfach *et al.*, 2021). Together, these advances refine metagenomic workflows and overcome key limitations, creating the foundation for wider application.

1.4.2 Applications and advancements

Metagenomics now underpins diverse fields by revealing the diversity and functions of complex microbial communities, with impacts ranging from discovery to clinical translation. In environmental microbiology, it has clarified the roles of soil and marine microbes in nutrient cycling, carbon metabolism, and plant health, as well as in bioremediation of pollutants such as hydrocarbons and heavy metals (Fierer, 2017; Azam and Malfatti, 2007; Murillo *et al.*, 2019; Hlihor and Cozma, 2023). In human health, metagenomics links microbial communities to digestion, immune modulation, and disease, and it underpins clinical diagnostics by enabling rapid detection of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes (Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2019; Chiu and Miller, 2019; de Abreu *et al.*, 2021).

Beyond diagnostics, metagenomics accelerates drug discovery, supports food safety and fermentation, advances biofuel production, and informs sustainable agriculture through

improved soil and crop microbiome management (Suman *et al.*, 2022; Ercolini, 2013). Ongoing technological innovations are further expanding these capabilities. Long-read sequencing now enables complete genome assembly and resolution of complex genomic regions (Amarasinghe *et al.*, 2020; Kim *et al.*, 2024), while single-cell metagenomics captures rare or uncultivable taxa (Hosokawa and Nishikawa, 2023). Integrative multi-omics approaches add functional context by linking metagenomic data with transcriptomic, proteomic, and metabolomic layers (Table 1.2) (O'Connor *et al.*, 2023; Zhang *et al.*, 2024). Complementing these advances, machine learning enhances analysis by improving prediction and uncovering hidden patterns (de Abreu *et al.*, 2021).

Large-scale initiatives such as the Earth Microbiome Project demonstrate the global impact of metagenomics in cataloguing microbial diversity (Thompson *et al.*, 2017; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). At the same time, clinical translation is advancing, with metagenomic approaches informing diagnostics, therapeutics, and personalised medicine (Chiu and Miller, 2019; Quince *et al.*, 2017). Beyond healthcare, synthetic biology and microbial engineering are extending applications into agriculture, health, and industry (Nazir *et al.*, 2024; Goold *et al.*, 2018). Despite remaining challenges in accuracy and interpretation, metagenomics continues to reshape microbiology by offering comprehensive insights into microbial diversity, ecology, and function, while also driving demand for sequencing platforms capable of greater speed and flexibility (Nayfach *et al.*, 2021; Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2017).

1.5 Oxford Nanopore Technologies

Oxford Nanopore sequencing represents a major advance in genomics, offering real-time analysis, ultra-long reads, and portability. These features are reshaping applications from environmental monitoring to clinical diagnostics and metagenomics (Kasianowicz *et al.*, 1996; Rang *et al.*, 2018). Developed by Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT), the platform detects changes in ionic current as DNA or RNA molecules pass through a nanopore, providing advantages over short-read systems such as Illumina in read length, speed, and accessibility (Jain *et al.*, 2016; Simpson *et al.*, 2017).

1.5.1 Core principles and sequencing process

Oxford Nanopore sequencing relies on a biological nanopore, a protein, embedded in a synthetic membrane. When a voltage is applied, DNA or RNA molecules pass through the pore, generating ionic current whose disruptions correspond to specific nucleotides (Figure 1.3) (Kasianowicz *et al.*, 1996; Branton *et al.*, 2008). These electrical signals are decoded in real time, enabling continuous sequencing of entire molecules rather than short fragments (Jain *et al.*,

2016; Rang *et al.*, 2018). By producing ultra-long reads, the technology resolves repetitive regions, structural variants, and other complex genomic features that short-read platforms often fail to capture (Wick *et al.*, 2019).

To generate ultra-long reads, sequencing requires careful sample preparation. DNA can be sequenced directly, while RNA is typically reverse transcribed into complementary DNA (cDNA), though direct RNA sequencing is also possible (Garalde *et al.*, 2018). Unlike most sequencing platforms, Nanopore sequencing does not require PCR amplification, reducing preparation time and minimising bias (Wang *et al.*, 2021). Molecules are directed into the pore by a motor protein that controls translocation one nucleotide at a time (Branton *et al.*, 2008). As bases move through, signal fluctuations are converted into nucleotide sequences by advanced basecalling algorithms (Figure 1.3) (Simpson *et al.*, 2017). A defining strength of the platform is real-time data generation, which enables immediate analysis and supports rapid decision-making in clinical and diagnostic contexts (Jain *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 1.3 Oxford Nanopore Technology sequencing procedure shown with a DNA strand passing through a nanopore and the raw electrical signal being translated into base pairs via basecalling.

1.5.2 Nanopore key features and advantages

Nanopore sequencing offers several distinguishing features compared to other platforms. Its ability to generate ultra-long reads, often exceeding 100 kilobases, facilitates the resolution of complex genomic regions, repetitive sequences, and structural variations (Jain *et al.*, 2016; Rang *et al.*, 2018). In metagenomics, long reads enable complete microbial genome assembly, strengthening both taxonomic and functional analyses (Wick *et al.*, 2019). Portability is another major advantage. Compact, USB-powered devices such as the MinION allow sequencing in diverse settings, including fieldwork and outbreak investigations, while higher-throughput platforms like the GridION and PromethION support large-scale projects (Quick *et al.*, 2016; Jain

et al., 2016). The Flongle adapter extends flexibility by providing a low-cost option for smaller-scale experiments (Magi *et al.*, 2018).

Real-time data generation further sets nanopore sequencing apart, results are available as sequencing occurs, enabling rapid decision-making in time-sensitive contexts such as clinical diagnostics and pathogen surveillance (Quick *et al.*, 2016; Charalampous *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, the ability to sequence raw DNA and RNA without amplification minimises PCR bias and preserves accurate representation of samples. Direct RNA sequencing, in particular, allows transcriptome analysis without cDNA synthesis, providing a more precise view of gene expression (Garalde *et al.*, 2018; Workman *et al.*, 2019). Together, these features, long reads, portability, real-time data generation, and amplification-free sequencing, make nanopore technology uniquely suited for applications ranging from basic research to clinical diagnostics.

1.5.3 Impact, applications, and limitations

Nanopore sequencing has now become a versatile tool across disciplines. In metagenomics, its long reads enable near-complete microbial genome assemblies and improved detection of low-abundance species, offering insights into community structure and interactions (Jain *et al.*, 2016; Wick *et al.*, 2019). Clinically, its real-time capabilities support rapid pathogen detection and genetic characterisation, demonstrated during the COVID-19 pandemic when the MinION device was widely used for SARS-CoV-2 sequencing to track viral evolution and transmission (Quick *et al.*, 2016; Tyson *et al.*, 2020). Beyond the clinic, it is applied in environmental monitoring, including microbial diversity surveys, ecosystem assessments, and responses to environmental change (Magi *et al.*, 2018; Alneberg *et al.*, 2014).

Nanopore sequencing also contributes to genomics and transcriptomics, supporting *de novo* assembly, structural variant detection, and direct RNA sequencing for accurate transcriptome profiling (Garalde *et al.*, 2018; Workman *et al.*, 2019; Miga *et al.*, 2020). Despite these strengths, limitations remain. Raw read accuracy is lower than that of short-read platforms, particularly in homopolymer regions, although continual improvements in basecalling algorithms and error-correction tools are reducing error rates (Rang *et al.*, 2018; Wick *et al.*, 2019; Loman *et al.*, 2015). Data volumes require substantial computational resources and bioinformatics expertise, which can pose barriers for some users (Magi *et al.*, 2018). Overall, while challenges persist, nanopore sequencing's combination of portability, long reads, and real-time data generation has established it as a powerful and increasingly accessible technology. Ongoing improvements in accuracy, scalability, and ease of use continue to expand its role in microbiome research and clinical diagnostics.

1.6 Microbiome host contamination

Despite advances in sequencing technologies, including ONT, host contamination remains a major challenge in microbiome research. It refers to the unintended inclusion of human-derived material in microbiome samples, which can compromise data quality, interpretation, and reproducibility (Marotz *et al.*, 2018; McLaren *et al.*, 2019). Addressing this issue requires understanding its sources, assessing its impact, and applying strategies to minimise contamination to ensure reliable microbiome analyses (de Goffau *et al.*, 2018; Eisenhofer *et al.*, 2019).

1.6.1 Challenges of host interference

Human DNA contamination can occur at multiple stages of microbiome research, undermining data accuracy and reproducibility. During sample collection, host material is inevitably co-sampled, including faecal samples containing sloughed intestinal epithelial cells, while oral and skin swabs frequently capture buccal or keratinised epithelial cells (Marotz *et al.*, 2018; Eisenhofer *et al.*, 2019). Sampling tools such as swabs, brushes, and biopsy instruments can also collect host cells alongside microbial material, further increasing the proportion of human DNA (Karstens *et al.*, 2019). Storage and transport practices exacerbate this problem, as microbial DNA often degrades more rapidly than human DNA, which is typically more abundant and stable (Poulsen *et al.*, 2021).

Additionally, repeated freeze–thaw cycles or prolonged storage selectively reduce microbial integrity, resulting in datasets dominated by host reads (Costea *et al.*, 2017). Laboratory steps add further bias, such as lysis protocols that frequently break down host cells more efficiently than microbial cells, especially Gram-positive bacteria with resilient walls, and PCR-based library preparation may preferentially amplify host DNA (de Goffau *et al.*, 2018). These biases significantly impact downstream analysis. Moreover, excess human DNA reduces sensitivity for detecting microbial signatures, particularly in low-biomass samples such as blood, cerebrospinal fluid, or skin, where microbial reads can be completely obscured (Eisenhofer *et al.*, 2019).

Dominance of host material not only masks rare taxa, leading to incomplete or misleading community profiles (Karstens *et al.*, 2019), but also increases the risk of misclassification, where host sequences are mistakenly annotated as microbial. Such errors can inflate diversity estimates or distort functional annotations, while variability in contamination levels across studies further undermines reproducibility and complicates cross-study comparisons (Nearing *et al.*, 2021). In clinical contexts, misinterpreting host-derived reads as microbial signals may result in diagnostic errors or inappropriate treatment decisions

(Eisenhofer *et al.*, 2019). Beyond technical concerns, contamination raises ethical and clinical issues. Human DNA in microbiome datasets can reveal sensitive genetic information about subjects, posing privacy risks (Costea *et al.*, 2017).

1.6.2 Mitigating human DNA contamination

Strategies to reduce human DNA contamination include careful sample handling, selective lysis, commercial host DNA depletion kits, and computational filtering of host-derived reads (Marotz *et al.*, 2018; McLaren *et al.*, 2019). While these approaches can improve data quality, each carries trade-offs, such as loss of microbial taxa, added complexity, or incomplete removal of host sequences. Increasing sequencing depth partly mitigates the problem but raises costs and does not resolve underlying biases (Marotz *et al.*, 2018; Pereira-Marques *et al.*, 2019).

An emerging solution is adaptive sequencing, in which Oxford Nanopore devices can selectively reject host reads or enrich for microbial sequences in real time. This approach offers a direct, sequencing-based strategy to reduce contamination and improve sensitivity, particularly in low-biomass samples where host DNA dominates (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Payne *et al.*, 2021). Adaptive sequencing therefore holds significant promise for advancing microbiome research and clinical applications.

1.7 Adaptive sequencing

Adaptive sequencing, developed by Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT), enables real-time selection of DNA or RNA molecules for sequencing based on their sequence content, dynamically accepting or rejecting reads during the process (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Unlike conventional sequencing, which processes all molecules indiscriminately, this targeted approach optimizes data collection, improves efficiency, and reduces unwanted sequences. By combining long-read sequencing with real-time decision-making, adaptive sequencing offers powerful opportunities for applications in microbiome research, targeted sequencing, and personalized medicine (Kovaka *et al.*, 2021; Weilguny *et al.*, 2023).

1.7.1 Key concepts, workflow, and strengths

As previously described, nanopore sequencing functions by passing DNA or RNA molecules through protein nanopores embedded in a synthetic membrane, recording ionic current changes that are then translated into nucleotide sequences in real time (Deamer *et al.*, 2016; Jain *et al.*, 2016). Adaptive sequencing builds on this principle by using real-time signal processing to evaluate molecules as they enter the pore, enabling dynamic selection based on sequence content (Payne *et al.*, 2021).

The adaptive sequencing workflow involves three steps. First, as a nucleic acid molecule begins to pass through the pore, a partial sequence is generated during the read-in phase (Figure 1.4A). Second, basecalling translates current fluctuations into nucleotide sequences (Figure 1.4B) (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Third, computational algorithms compare the sequence against user-defined criteria, such as alignment to a reference genome or target regions (Figure 1.4C). Molecules meeting these criteria are sequenced in full, while those that do not are ejected, allowing new molecules to enter (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Weilguny *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 1.4 Basic method of adaptive sequencing. (A) DNA strand passing through a pore and producing a raw electrical signal. (B) Basecalling of raw electrical signals into reads. (C) Adaptive sequencing software comparing the incoming read to a reference genome and sending the decision back to the Nanopore device.

This real-time decision-making, implemented through ONT's MinKNOW software, streamlines sequencing by replacing labour-intensive enrichment techniques such as PCR or hybrid capture (Rang *et al.*, 2018; Payne *et al.*, 2021). Rejecting unwanted molecules frees capacity for regions or organisms of interest, making adaptive sequencing particularly effective for targeted applications (Workman *et al.*, 2019). Its versatility extends to both DNA and RNA, supporting diverse research areas from human genomics to environmental microbiology (Weilguny *et al.*, 2023; Kovaka *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, acceptance and rejection criteria can be adjusted during sequencing runs, enabling flexible and iterative experimental designs that respond to real-time data (Payne *et al.*, 2021).

1.7.2 Applications of adaptive sequencing

Nanopore adaptive sequencing has broad applications across human genomics, cancer research, microbiome studies, metagenomics, and personalized medicine (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Weilguny *et al.*, 2023). In human genomics, adaptive sequencing enables precise detection of

genetic variants, including single nucleotide variants, insertions/deletions, and structural variations. By selectively sequencing alleles of interest, it supports haplotype resolution and advances the study of complex traits and diseases (Jain *et al.*, 2016). Adaptive sequencing also facilitates targeted epigenetic analysis, revealing methylation patterns and regulatory mechanisms implicated in epigenetic disorders (Simpson *et al.*, 2017; Yuen *et al.*, 2024). In oncology, it enhances mutation detection and biomarker discovery by focusing on tumour-associated genetic regions, providing high-resolution insights into tumour heterogeneity (Workman *et al.*, 2019; Kovaka *et al.*, 2021; Nakamura *et al.*, 2023).

In microbiome research, adaptive sequencing improves pathogen detection and antimicrobial resistance profiling by selectively sequencing microbial genomes within complex samples (Leggett and Clark, 2017; Liu *et al.*, 2024). Its ability to enrich microbial DNA while excluding host DNA is particularly valuable in low-biomass environments, such as skin or lung samples, where host contamination often obscures microbial signals (Parker *et al.*, 2017). This enables strain-level resolution and targeted investigation of taxa or functional genes linked to health and disease, including conditions such as inflammatory bowel disease and obesity (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Martin *et al.*, 2022). Adaptive sequencing also facilitates studies of host-microbe interactions, integrating microbial and host genomic signals for a deeper understanding of immune and metabolic pathways (Gan *et al.*, 2021).

In personalized medicine, adaptive sequencing helps identify microbiome-based biomarkers for diagnosis and monitoring (Yuen *et al.*, 2024). By targeting microbial pathways involved in drug metabolism, it supports microbiome-guided therapeutic strategies (Zhao *et al.*, 2023). Its capacity for real-time pathogen detection and resistance profiling is particularly valuable in infectious disease management, enabling rapid, informed clinical decisions (Payne *et al.*, 2021). In environmental genomics, adaptive sequencing enriches low-abundance taxa and functional genes, uncovering rare microbial contributors to ecosystem processes and diversity (Martin *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2024). By combining targeted enrichment with real-time analysis, adaptive sequencing bridges advanced sequencing technology with high-resolution applications across medicine, microbiology, and ecology. Its flexibility ensures continued impact as a transformative tool in both research and clinical practice.

1.7.3 Obstacles, innovations, and possibilities

Despite its transformative potential, adaptive sequencing faces several challenges. Real-time signal processing and decision-making demand substantial computational resources and efficient algorithms (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Molecule rejection is not flawless, as some unwanted sequences are fully sequenced, reducing efficiency (Weilguny *et al.*, 2023). Reference bias is

another limitation, because reliance on alignment to reference genomes restricts utility for poorly characterized or novel organisms (Leggett and Clark, 2017). Scaling adaptive sequencing to high-throughput settings increases computational overhead and data management complexity, while the intrinsic error rates of nanopore sequencing can compromise precision in real-time decisions and downstream analyses (Jain *et al.*, 2016).

Ongoing innovations are addressing these barriers, such as machine learning models that improve real-time rejection accuracy and sequencing efficiency (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022), while hybrid approaches, including CRISPR-based enrichment, enhance specificity and scalability (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Additionally, advances in nanopore chemistry and basecalling continue to reduce error rates (Chiou *et al.*, 2023). Integration with transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics expands adaptive sequencing's scope for multidimensional analyses (Huang *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*, 2023). Portable platforms such as the MinION and Flongle extend adaptive sequencing applications to pathogen surveillance and environmental monitoring in resource-limited settings (Parker *et al.*, 2017).

Looking forward, improved accuracy, scalability, and automation will facilitate clinical adoption, particularly in cancer genomics and infectious disease diagnostics (Kovaka *et al.*, 2021). Expanding reference databases, improving computational frameworks, and advances in on-device computing will further broaden applicability, enabling sophisticated analyses such as variant calling and functional annotation during sequencing runs (Simpson *et al.*, 2017; Payne *et al.*, 2021). With its adaptability and efficiency, adaptive sequencing is poised to transform genomics, microbiome research, and precision medicine, defining a new era of real-time, targeted sequencing (Weilguny *et al.*, 2023).

1.8 Microbial bioinformatics

Interpreting microbiome data requires robust computational approaches to manage the large and complex datasets generated by sequencing. Bioinformatics provides the frameworks and tools for processing raw reads, identifying and classifying microbial species, and annotating their functional potential (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Almeida *et al.*, 2019). These methods are central to addressing challenges and translating sequencing advances, such as adaptive sequencing, into reliable research and clinical applications. By enabling accurate taxonomic profiling, functional annotation, and integrative analyses, bioinformatics underpins modern microbiome research and continues to evolve in response to its challenges (Hugerth and Andersson, 2017; Knight *et al.*, 2018).

1.8.1 Role and methods in microbiome research

By leveraging computational methods, bioinformatics plays a vital role in processing, analysing, and interpreting complex microbiome data, offering critical insights into microbial communities and their interactions with the host (Hiraoka *et al.*, 2016). Key applications include taxonomic profiling, which identifies and classifies microbial species, functional analysis, which uncovers metabolic potential and ecological roles, and diversity analysis measuring within-sample (alpha) and between-sample (beta) variation (Table 1.3) (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Douglas *et al.*, 2020; Knight *et al.*, 2018).

Table 1.3 Typical bioinformatic stages and processes for microbiome research.

Stage	Description	Applications	Common Tools
Data Acquisition	Collection of sequencing data using technologies like amplicon sequencing, shotgun metagenomics, and metatranscriptomics.	Targeted studies, broad community profiling, and active gene expression analysis.	16S rRNA sequencing, ITS sequencing.
Public Databases	Use of repositories for reference and comparative data.	Microbial classification, comparative studies, and dataset sharing.	HMP, ENA.
Preprocessing	Quality control, filtering, trimming, and contaminant removal.	Ensures data reliability and accuracy before downstream analyses.	Trimmomatic, Cutadapt, Bowtie2.
Taxonomic Profiling	Assigns sequences to microbial taxa using marker-gene or genome-based databases.	Microbial identification and community composition analysis.	SILVA, Kraken2, MetaPhlan.
Functional Annotation	Links sequences to metabolic pathways and functional roles.	Understanding microbial functionality and ecosystem contributions.	KEGG, MetaCyc, eggNOG.
Genome Assembly	Reconstructs individual microbial genomes from sequencing data.	Resolves genome structures and detects novel species.	MEGAHIT, SPAdes.
Diversity Analysis	Measures microbial diversity within (alpha) and between (beta) samples.	Community structure analysis and ecological studies.	Shannon index, Bray-Curtis dissimilarity.
Visualization	Generates plots and heatmaps to represent microbial data intuitively.	Enhances data interpretation and presentation.	QIIME2, phyloseq, MicrobiomeAnalyst.
Multi-Omics Integration	Combines microbiome data with other omics layers like genomics, proteomics, and metabolomics.	Comprehensive insights into host-microbe interactions and metabolic pathways.	MetaboAnalyst, MIMOSA.
Analysis Pipelines	Comprehensive workflows for microbiome data processing and analysis.	Streamlined data processing, functional profiling, and pathway predictions.	QIIME2, MG-RAST, Mothur, HUMAnN, PICRUSt2.

Mock datasets and mock microbial communities are commonly used to benchmark microbiome workflows, evaluate sequencing performance, and assess the accuracy of bioinformatic analyses under controlled conditions. These standards typically contain defined microbial compositions that enable comparison between expected and observed results, helping identify biases introduced during sequencing, taxonomic classification, or downstream analysis (Bokulich *et al.*, 2016; McLaren *et al.*, 2019). Different mock community designs serve distinct purposes. DNA standards containing purified genomic material are particularly useful for evaluating sequencing technologies, taxonomic assigners, and bioinformatic pipelines independent of variability introduced during culturing or extraction (McLaren *et al.*, 2019; Lloréns-Rico *et al.*, 2021), whereas culture-based mock communities additionally assess laboratory workflows such as sample preparation, extraction efficiency, and contamination control. Because microbiome datasets are inherently complex and variable, mock communities provide an important reference framework for validating reproducibility, sensitivity, and methodological performance across studies (Bokulich *et al.*, 2016; McLaren *et al.*, 2019).

Another strength is the integration of microbiome data with other omics layers, including genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, providing a holistic view of host–microbe interactions (Huang *et al.*, 2017). This integration is supported by a comprehensive workflow that begins with data acquisition through sequencing technologies (Table 1.3) (Almeida *et al.*, 2019). Amplicon sequencing targets specific marker genes such as 16S rRNA or ITS, shotgun metagenomics captures all DNA in a sample, and metatranscriptomics profiles active microbial genes via RNA sequencing (Table 1.2) (Quince *et al.*, 2017). Public databases, including the Human Microbiome Project (HMP) and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), provide essential reference datasets (Table 1.3) (Turnbaugh *et al.*, 2007; Cochrane *et al.*, 2013).

After acquisition, preprocessing ensures data quality through filtering and adapter removal (e.g., Trimmomatic, Cutadapt), host DNA removal (Bowtie2), and error correction (DADA2, Deblur) (Bolger *et al.*, 2014; Martin, 2011; Callahan *et al.*, 2016; Amir *et al.*, 2017). Genome assemblers such as MEGAHIT and SPAdes reconstruct microbial genomes (Li *et al.*, 2015; Bankevich *et al.*, 2012). Taxonomic profiling assigns sequences to microbial taxa using databases such as SILVA, Greengenes, or RDP, or genome-based tools like Kraken2 and MetaPhlAn (Wood *et al.*, 2019; Segata *et al.*, 2012). Functional annotation links sequences to pathways with KEGG, MetaCyc, or eggNOG (Kanehisa *et al.*, 2016; Caspi *et al.*, 2016; Huerta-Cepas *et al.*, 2019).

Statistical and diversity analyses follow, using metrics like Shannon and Chao1 for alpha diversity and Bray–Curtis or UniFrac for beta diversity (Table 1.4) (Hill, 1973; Lozupone and

Knight, 2005). Visualization tools such as QIIME2 and phyloseq generate intuitive plots and heatmaps (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; McMurdie and Holmes, 2013). Integration with host omics further strengthens insights, for example combining host transcriptomics with metagenomics to study immune responses or linking microbial genes to metabolites with MetaboAnalyst or MIMOSA (Chong *et al.*, 2018; Noecker *et al.*, 2016).

Table 1.4 Common statistical and analytical approaches used in microbiome analysis.

Approach	Purpose in research	Example application
Alpha diversity analysis	Measures diversity within samples.	Comparing diversity across skin, wound, and mock microbiomes.
Beta diversity analysis	Measures differences between microbial communities.	Comparing microbiome composition across sample groups.
Bray–Curtis dissimilarity	Quantifies compositional differences between samples.	Comparing control and adaptive sequencing runs.
Chao1 richness	Estimates total species richness.	Assessing richness in complex microbiome samples.
Normalisation analysis	Reduces technical bias between samples or datasets.	Standardising abundance data before diversity analysis.
PCA / PCoA / NMDS	Visualises clustering and relationships between samples.	Examining microbiome clustering patterns.
PERMANOVA	Tests for significant differences between microbial communities.	Evaluating separation between microbiome groups.
Relative abundance analysis	Measures proportional representation of taxa or genes.	Assessing dominant taxa or ARGs across samples.
Sequence statistics analysis	Summarises sequencing quality and output characteristics.	Comparing read quality, length, and yield between runs.
Shannon diversity	Measures diversity accounting for richness and evenness.	Comparing diversity across microbiome samples.
UniFrac distance	Measures phylogenetic differences between communities.	Comparing relatedness of microbiome communities.

Finally, a wide array of tools and platforms support microbiome research (Table 1.5). Pipelines like QIIME2, MG-RAST, and Mothur enable data processing (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Keegan *et al.*, 2016; Schloss, 2020). Taxonomic classification tools such as Kraken2 and MetaPhlAn provide accurate species identification, while HUMAnN and PICRUSt2 predict and quantify microbial metabolic pathways (Franzosa *et al.*, 2018; Douglas *et al.*, 2020). For visualization, phyloseq and MicrobiomeAnalyst remain common resources (Chong *et al.*, 2018; McMurdie and Holmes, 2013). Collectively, these approaches make bioinformatics indispensable to advancing microbiome research.

Table 1.5 Common bioinformatic tools and platforms used in microbiome research.

Tool/platform	Category	Primary function
ReadBouncer	Adaptive sequencing	Real-time nanopore read rejection and host depletion.
ReadFish	Adaptive sequencing	Real-time targeted nanopore enrichment and depletion.
ReadUntil	Adaptive sequencing	Framework for selective nanopore sequencing control.
MG-RAST	Analysis platform	Automated metagenomic analysis and annotation platform.
Mothur	Analysis platform	Microbiome sequence processing and community analysis.
QIIME2	Analysis platform	Integrated microbiome analysis and visualization platform.
Guppy	Basecalling	Nanopore signal processing and basecalling.
Conda/Miniconda	Environment management	Reproducible software and dependency management.
Docker	Environment management	Portable and reproducible software containerization.
HUMAnN	Functional annotation	Functional and metabolic pathway profiling.
PICRUSt2	Functional annotation	Prediction of microbial functional potential.
Cutadapt	Preprocessing	Adapter trimming and preprocessing of sequencing reads.
fastp	Preprocessing	Quality control and filtering of sequencing reads.
FASTX Toolkit	Preprocessing	Basic preprocessing and manipulation of sequencing reads.
Trimmomatic	Preprocessing	Quality trimming and filtering of sequencing reads.
Flye	Read assembly	Long-read microbial genome and metagenome assembly.
MEGAHIT	Read assembly	Assembly of metagenomic sequencing datasets.
RGI	Resistance profiling	Identification of antimicrobial resistance genes.
Bowtie2	Sequence alignment	Alignment of sequencing reads to reference genomes.
DIAMOND	Sequence alignment	Fast protein alignment for metagenomic analysis.
Minimap2	Sequence alignment	Long-read sequence alignment and mapping.
DADA2	Sequence processing	Error correction and amplicon sequence inference.
SAMtools	Sequence processing	Manipulation and processing of alignment files.
Seqtk/Seqkit	Sequence processing	FASTA/FASTQ processing and sequence statistics.
MinKNOW	Sequencing platform	Control and management of nanopore sequencing runs.
R	Statistical analysis	Statistical computing and graphical data analysis.
BLAST	Taxonomic classification	Sequence alignment and similarity-based taxonomic identification.
CAT	Taxonomic classification	Contig-based taxonomic classification using protein annotations.
Kraken2	Taxonomic classification	Rapid k-mer based microbial classification.
MEGAN	Taxonomic classification	Taxonomic and functional exploration of metagenomic data.
MetaPhlAn	Taxonomic classification	Marker gene-based microbial profiling.
GitHub	Version control	Code sharing, workflow archiving, and collaboration.
MicrobiomeAnalyst	Visualization	Interactive microbiome data analysis and visualization.
phyloseq	Visualization	Microbiome analysis and visualization in R.
ASAW	Workflow management	Adaptive sequencing analysis workflow for comparative microbiome analysis.
DBCW	Workflow management	Reproducible workflow for database creation.
MMCAW	Workflow management	Modular microbiome metagenomic analysis workflow.
Snakemake	Workflow management	Reproducible and scalable workflow automation.

1.8.2 Overcoming challenges and innovations

Despite its transformative capabilities, bioinformatics in microbiome research faces several obstacles. The vast and heterogeneous nature of datasets demands substantial computational resources for storage, processing, and analysis (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Hu *et al.*, 2022). Host DNA contamination, sequencing artifacts, and incomplete microbial genome databases complicate accurate taxonomic and functional annotation, underscoring the need for rigorous preprocessing and continual curation (Hugerth and Andersson, 2017; Almeida *et al.*, 2019). Variability in sample collection, sequencing protocols, and analysis pipelines further reduces reproducibility, while linking microbial diversity to host phenotypes is confounded by complex environmental and clinical factors, requiring robust statistical models (Knight *et al.*, 2018; Sinha *et al.*, 2017; Gilbert *et al.*, 2016; McLaren *et al.*, 2019).

Emerging innovations are addressing these challenges and broadening microbial bioinformatics. Long-read platforms such as PacBio and Oxford Nanopore improve genome assembly and resolve complex communities (van Dijk *et al.*, 2018). Complementing this, machine learning and artificial intelligence uncover hidden patterns in large datasets, strengthening predictive power (D'Urso and Broccolo, 2024; Hernández Medina *et al.*, 2022). Additionally, single cell microbiomics captures rare taxa and functional heterogeneity at high resolution (Browne *et al.*, 2016). Integrated multi-omics approaches allow comprehensive views of host–microbe interactions, while cloud-based platforms like Terra and Galaxy offer scalable infrastructure for collaborative research (Huang *et al.*, 2017; Langmead and Nellore, 2018; Afgan *et al.*, 2018). Together, these advances are steadily overcoming barriers and expanding the scope and applications of microbial bioinformatics.

1.8.3 Applications and potential prospects

Bioinformatics is driving transformative progress in microbiome research across health, environment, and biotechnology. In clinical contexts, computational tools are used to identify microbial signatures linked to conditions such as obesity, diabetes, and inflammatory bowel disease, as well as to study the roles of the skin and oral microbiomes in systemic health and wound healing (Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2017; Byrd *et al.*, 2018). These insights increasingly inform precision medicine, supporting interventions such as probiotics, faecal microbiota transplants, and diagnostic pipelines for pathogen detection and antimicrobial resistance monitoring (Quaranta *et al.*, 2022; Almeida *et al.*, 2019).

Beyond medicine, bioinformatics advances environmental and nutritional research by clarifying how diet shapes microbial composition and by enabling the design of synthetic

microbial communities for therapeutic, agricultural, and industrial applications (De Filippo *et al.*, 2010; Turnbaugh *et al.*, 2009). Looking forward, real-time analysis powered by nanopore sequencing and edge computing promises to accelerate microbiome studies, making them more accessible and actionable (Simpson *et al.*, 2017; Jain *et al.*, 2016). Integration of environmental and clinical data will further refine functional annotation and improve predictions of microbiome–host interactions (Quince *et al.*, 2017).

At the same time, ethical frameworks must evolve to safeguard privacy and ensure responsible management of sensitive genomic and microbiome data (Lange *et al.*, 2022). Alongside these safeguards, collaborative initiatives, such as the Earth Microbiome Project, are building global reference datasets, strengthening the foundation for cross-study comparisons and novel discoveries (Thompson *et al.*, 2017). As sequencing technologies and computational methods continue to advance, bioinformatics will remain central to microbiome research. By addressing current limitations, embracing multi-omics integration, and embedding reproducible practices, the field is poised to deliver new insights into health, disease, and ecology, with far-reaching scientific and societal impact (Douglas *et al.*, 2020; Kumar *et al.*, 2024).

1.9 Research reproducibility

Reproducibility, the ability to obtain consistent results across independent studies, is fundamental to scientific reliability. The demand is particularly acute in bioinformatics-driven microbiome research, where methodological variability, dynamic microbial communities, and complex sequencing data often lead to inconsistent or non-comparable findings (Schloss, 2018; Bharti and Grimm, 2021). These challenges have been magnified by wider concerns over a biomedical “reproducibility crisis,” raising questions about the robustness of reported results. Establishing standardized protocols, transparent reporting, and rigorous validation is therefore essential to ensure that analyses of the microbiome can be reliably extended and meaningfully interpreted across studies (Duvallet *et al.*, 2017; Costea *et al.*, 2017).

1.9.1 Limitations to achieving reproducibility

Achieving reproducibility is essential for ensuring reliable and clinically translatable microbiome research (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018; Duvallet *et al.*, 2017). Yet, multiple sources of variability hinder consistency across studies. Sample collection and handling are major contributors, such as differences in swab versus faecal sampling, storage conditions, or preservation methods, which can alter microbial composition and DNA integrity (Knight *et al.*, 2018; Sinha *et al.*, 2017). Sequencing platforms also introduce discrepancies, as Illumina and ONT vary in read length, error profiles, and inherent biases (Amos *et al.*, 2020; Stevens *et al.*,

2023). Downstream, inconsistent bioinformatics pipelines for preprocessing, assembly, and annotation further complicate comparability (McLaren *et al.*, 2019).

Incomplete metadata and insufficient reporting of study design, participant demographics, or experimental conditions limit replication and cross-study integration (Thompson *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, the absence of appropriate positive and negative controls makes it difficult to distinguish true microbial signals from artifacts (Heintz-Buschart and Wilmes, 2018). Finally, the dynamic and contextual nature of the microbiome adds biological complexity, including temporal fluctuations driven by diet, health, or environment, along with high inter-individual variability, make it challenging to generalize findings across populations (Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2017). These factors collectively underscore the difficulty of achieving reproducibility in microbiome studies and highlight the urgent need for standardization and best-practice guidelines.

1.9.2 Overcoming barriers and future strategies

Improving reproducibility in microbiome research requires coordinated strategies across experimental design, bioinformatics, and data sharing. Standardization of protocols is central, with initiatives such as the Human Microbiome Project (HMP) and Earth Microbiome Project (EMP) providing benchmarks for sample collection, storage, and sequencing (Costea *et al.*, 2017; Thompson *et al.*, 2017). Validated preservation methods (e.g., RNAlater, dry ice) and quality controls, including spike-in standards and mock microbial communities, further reduce variability (Sinha *et al.*, 2017; Amos *et al.*, 2020). Replication of studies, transparent reporting, and following frameworks like MIxS, strengthen reliability across laboratories (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2011; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018).

Data management practices are equally important. FAIR principles ensure datasets are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, with repositories such as MG-RAST and NCBI SRA facilitating open sharing (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016; Leinonen *et al.*, 2011). Standardized pipelines (e.g., QIIME2, DADA2) and curated reference databases (e.g., SILVA, GTDB) improve consistency in taxonomic and functional annotation (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Parks *et al.*, 2018). Clear communication of workflows, computational tools (Table 1.5), statistical approaches (Table 1.4), and benchmarking strategies is equally important for reproducibility, ensuring that microbiome analyses can be interpreted, replicated, and extended across studies. Version control systems such as GitHub increase transparency, while statistical rigor, through robust models and multiple-testing corrections, reduces spurious associations (Weiss *et al.*, 2017; Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995).

Future strategies build on these foundations, such as long-read sequencing and single-cell microbiomics because they promise improved genome assembly and high-resolution profiling (Wick *et al.*, 2019). Expanding reference databases and applying machine learning will enhance annotation and pattern discovery (Hug *et al.*, 2016; D'Urso and Broccolo, 2024). Additionally, real-time sequencing and edge computing may enable on-the-fly validation (Stevens *et al.*, 2023). Crucially, the adoption of internationally accepted guidelines and open science practices will harmonize methods across the field, ensuring reproducible, comparable, and clinically translatable findings (Knight *et al.*, 2018).

1.10 Goals of the thesis

The overarching aim of this thesis is to improve reproducibility and ultimately the diagnostic capacity of human microbiome research through the development and application of adaptive sequencing methods. Although high-throughput sequencing has transformed the field, challenges such as host DNA contamination, workflow variability, and limited methodological standardization continue to hinder reproducibility and clinical translation. Overcoming these barriers requires approaches that integrate methodological rigor with diagnostic relevance, ensuring that technical innovation serves as a foundation for scalability and translational impact rather than an endpoint in itself.

To this end, three interconnected data chapters are presented. The first establishes methodological stability by developing and validating a reproducible, modular workflow for microbiome metagenomics, embedding environment control, provenance tracking, and consensus-based taxonomic assignment within a reusable analytical framework. The second optimises adaptive sequencing for selective human DNA depletion in skin microbiome samples, demonstrating, for the first time in this context, how sequencing outputs can be shaped directly to reduce host dominance on accessible hardware. The third extends this approach to simultaneous host depletion and targeted enrichment, evaluating whether these improvements enhance recovery of clinically relevant signals, particularly pathogens and antimicrobial resistance determinants within low-yield, host-dominated samples.

Together, these studies provide reproducible, scalable, and clinically relevant strategies for addressing key barriers in microbiome research. By combining methodological rigor with translational intent, this thesis offers practical tools and conceptual advances to support more reliable microbiome science and its application in diagnostic and therapeutic settings.

Chapter 2 Reproducibility and development of workflows for metagenomic analysis of the skin microbiome

2.1 Introduction

A 2024 survey of biomedical researchers found that 72% perceived a reproducibility crisis, with only half attempting replication and just 16% reporting institutional procedures to support it (Cobey *et al.*, 2024). While only one example, these findings are consistent with broader concerns in the biomedical sciences, where the lack of standardized practices has fuelled the open and reproducible research movement to strengthen reliability (Schloss, 2018). Reproducibility is especially difficult in microbiome science, where biological variability, technical inconsistencies in sampling, and reliance on high-dimensional sequencing data complicate validation (Schloss, 2018; Martin, 2019; Kashyap *et al.*, 2017). These challenges are especially acute in the skin microbiome, where diverse and dynamic microbial communities hinder consistent analysis (Turnbaugh *et al.*, 2007; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Reliable workflows are therefore critical for advancing microbiome research and enabling applications in personalized medicine, diagnostics, and therapeutics (Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2019; Quince *et al.*, 2017). Developing reproducible bioinformatics pipelines addresses these needs by standardizing analyses, improving cross-study comparability, and supporting robust taxonomic assignment through integrating multiple complementary tools.

2.1.1 Reproducibility challenges

Reproducibility in research is the ability to obtain consistent results under similar conditions. It is critical for validating findings, enabling meta-analyses, and supporting clinical translation, yet is often undermined by variability introduced during study design and execution (Schloss, 2018). In human microbiome research, this challenge is compounded by biological heterogeneity, as differences across individuals, populations, and time points complicate replication under ostensibly similar conditions (Yatsunenko *et al.*, 2012). For example, short-term dietary changes can rapidly restructure gut microbial communities (Forry *et al.*, 2024), while urban and rural populations display distinct microbiomes due to lifestyle and environmental exposures (Zhernakova *et al.*, 2016).

Technical and analytical factors further contribute to variability. Sample handling, sequencing methods, and bioinformatics pipelines can all influence microbial profiles and diversity estimates, producing contrasting interpretations of the same dataset (Costea *et al.*, 2017; Bharti and Grimm, 2021; McIntyre *et al.*, 2017). Improving reproducibility therefore requires rigorous methodological standards but, above all, transparent reporting of protocols

and parameters (Nearing *et al.*, 2021). Detailed documentation enables independent replication and distinction between biological and methodological effects (Amos *et al.*, 2020; Knight *et al.*, 2018). Such measures are essential for ensuring reliable microbiome science and for realizing its clinical potential, from personalized medicine to novel diagnostics (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018).

2.1.2 Microbiome metagenomics

Building on the need for transparent and reliable methods, metagenomics has revolutionized microbiome research by enabling direct sequencing of microbial communities from environmental or host-associated samples (Quince *et al.*, 2017). Unlike culture-based methods, which capture only culturable organisms, metagenomic sequencing identifies both culturable and unculturable species, providing insights into taxonomic composition and functional potential (Human Microbiome Project Consortium, 2012; Marchesi *et al.*, 2016). By interrogating genetic content, it reveals metabolic pathways, resistance genes, and ecological functions, while its unbiased approach facilitates the discovery of rare taxa, novel species, and unique microbial traits (Costea *et al.*, 2017; Knight *et al.*, 2018).

While metagenomics expands the scope of microbiome analysis, it also introduces new challenges for reproducibility, especially for technical and procedural variability. Sequencing platforms such as Illumina and Oxford Nanopore differ in error profiles, read lengths, and coverage, while inconsistencies in DNA extraction and library preparation can distort community profiles (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2019; Nayfach *et al.*, 2021). Reliability therefore depends on workflow standardization from sampling through analysis, rigorous quality control with benchmarking datasets (e.g., mock communities as discussed in [Subsection 1.9.1](#)), and transparent reporting of methods (Bowers *et al.*, 2017; Knight *et al.*, 2018; Lloréns-Rico *et al.*, 2021).

Reproducibility is further complicated by the uneven distribution of research across body sites. Most metagenomic resources and studies have focused on the gut microbiome, leaving the skin comparatively underrepresented (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018; Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2019). This imbalance complicates reproducibility in skin microbiome research and underscores the need for datasets and pipelines tailored to skin ecosystems (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Ruuskanen *et al.*, 2022). Addressing these gaps will enable metagenomics to more effectively capture microbial diversity, uncover functional insights, and accelerate the discovery of novel species (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Knight *et al.*, 2018; Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2019).

2.1.3 Bioinformatic workflows

Bioinformatics provides the foundation for metagenomic research, transforming raw sequencing data into insights on microbial diversity and function, but variability across

workflows can undermine reproducibility (Knight *et al.*, 2018; Lagier *et al.*, 2015). Analysis begins with quality control and preprocessing to remove artifacts and contaminants. Tools assess read quality, trim adapters, and filter low-quality reads (Andrews, 2010; Bolger *et al.*, 2014), though inconsistent thresholds affect downstream accuracy (Bokulich *et al.*, 2013). Taxonomic profiling tools assign microbial identities (Wood *et al.*, 2019; Beghini *et al.*, 2021), while functional profiling infers pathways and ecological roles (Table 1.5) (Franzosa *et al.*, 2018; Seemann, 2014).

Both depend on reference databases such as RefSeq, Greengenes, and GTDB, whose variable coverage and quality highlight the need for reliable resources (O'Leary *et al.*, 2016; Quast *et al.*, 2013; Parks *et al.*, 2021). Metagenome assembly and binning reconstruct microbial genomes for detailed taxonomic and genetic analyses (Li *et al.*, 2015; Nurk *et al.*, 2017), but differences in algorithm sensitivity and specificity affect genome recovery and contig accuracy (Table 1.5) (Kang *et al.*, 2015; Chen *et al.*, 2024). Downstream, statistical approaches, including diversity measures, differential abundance testing, and network analysis, are essential for community-level inference (Table 1.4) (Gloor *et al.*, 2017).

Yet the compositional, high-dimensional nature of microbiome data requires specialized methods to reduce false discoveries (Lozupone *et al.*, 2011). Visualization tools enhance interpretability, while multi-omics approaches such as metatranscriptomics and metabolomics expand ecosystem-level insights (Wickham, 2009; McMurdie and Holmes, 2013; Jansson and Baker, 2016); however, integration of these methods increases complexity and underscores the need for standardized workflows to ensure consistency and reproducibility (Knight *et al.*, 2018). Addressing these challenges is critical for advancing microbial bioinformatics and enabling deeper exploration of ecosystem structure and function (Qin *et al.*, 2010; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018).

2.1.4 Practical solutions

Improving reproducibility in microbiome bioinformatics requires standardized methodologies, transparency, and collaboration. Key strategies include modular pipelines built with workflow managers to streamline analyses and enhance consistency (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Afgan *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, systematic benchmarking identifies optimal methods and improves reliability (Costea *et al.*, 2017), while sharing workflows through GitHub, Bioconda, and Docker promotes accessibility and minimizes variability (Table 1.5) (Grüning *et al.*, 2018). Adherence to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles is equally vital (Table 2.1) (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016). For example, public repositories with unique identifiers and open formats ensure accessibility, while standardized ontologies and metadata schemas facilitate dataset integration and comparison (Sansone *et al.*, 2019).

Table 2.1 Description of FAIR principles and practical examples for microbiome metagenomic research.

Principle	Description	Metagenomic example
Findability	Data and metadata should be readily locatable for humans and machines using persistent identifiers and searchable metadata.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unique dataset identifiers (e.g., DOIs for raw sequencing data) ▪ Deposition of raw reads and metadata in repositories (e.g., NCBI SRA, MG-RAST, EBI-ENA)
Accessibility	Data must be retrievable via standardized protocols, with authentication or authorization where required.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Storage in open- or controlled-access repositories ▪ Long-term availability through established archives (e.g., NCBI GenBank, EMBL-EBI)
Interoperability	Data and metadata should use standardized formats and vocabularies to enable integration across datasets and tools.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Adoption of community metadata standards (e.g., MIxS) ▪ Use of interoperable formats (e.g., FASTA, FASTQ, JSON)
Reusability	Data and metadata must be well-documented, clearly licensed, and structured to support replication and further analysis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Comprehensive documentation of methods and pipelines ▪ Open licensing (e.g., Creative Commons) ▪ Mock microbial datasets for benchmarking

Standards such as MIxS and repositories including MG-RAST, NCBI SRA, and ENA improve consistency, but challenges such as data complexity and inconsistent reporting highlight the need for stronger community-driven frameworks (Table 2.1) (Yilmaz *et al.*, 2011; Ruuskanen *et al.*, 2022). Building on these efforts, training programs and community-driven guidelines, such as IHMS, are essential for equipping researchers and minimizing variability (Schloss, 2018; Proctor *et al.*, 2019). Transparency is further reinforced by open science practices, including open-source tools and open data, which promote accessibility and collaboration (Poldrack *et al.*, 2018). Large-scale initiatives such as the Human Microbiome Project (HMP) and Earth Microbiome Project (EMP) exemplify how collective efforts can embed such practices into community standards (Turnbaugh *et al.*, 2007; Thompson *et al.*, 2017).

Achieving reproducibility, however, also depends on systematic replication of published studies to expose methodological limitations and guide improvements (Stodden *et al.*, 2018; Ioannidis, 2016a). Yet despite rapid growth in microbiome research, few skin microbiome studies have been reproduced, representing a major gap (Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2016; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Addressing this will require rigorous quality control with mock communities and spike-ins (Tourlousse *et al.*, 2018) as well as inter-laboratory replication to reveal variability (Sinha *et al.*, 2017). At present, reproducing skin metagenomic studies remains hindered by inconsistent

workflows, limited data tracking, and inadequate documentation. Additionally, few workflows are tailored to nanopore sequencing or capable of integrating multiple analytical approaches (Ruuskanen *et al.*, 2022).

This study addresses a central challenge in microbiome research: the lack of reproducible and standardised bioinformatic workflows. In line with the overarching aim of this thesis to improve reproducibility and diagnostic capacity, it focuses on developing a modular, transparent framework for skin metagenomics. Through reconstruction and critical evaluation of existing workflows, this work aims to identify key barriers to reproducibility and establish a structured approach for consistent, interpretable, and scalable analysis. By defining and operationalising reproducibility within microbiome bioinformatics, this chapter lays the groundwork for more reliable and transferable metagenomic research.

2.2 Methods and materials

Ethical approval was provided by the Hull Royal Tissue ethics committee (REC: 19/NE/0150) and the Faculty Ethics Committee for the Faculty of Science and Engineering at the University of Hull.

2.2.1 Reproducing Afshinnekoo *et al.* (2015)

Afshinnekoo *et al.* (2015) and Kang *et al.* (2018) were selected for replication because they represent two of the most widely cited and influential skin metagenomic microbiome studies currently available. Skin metagenomic studies remain relatively limited compared to other microbiome fields, making these studies particularly important benchmarks for evaluating reproducibility and bioinformatic transparency. Both studies were published in high-impact journals, incorporated comparatively comprehensive bioinformatic workflows, and provided sufficient methodological detail and data accessibility to align with FAIR reproducibility principles. In addition, the studies received substantial scientific and public attention, highlighting their broader impact and suitability for reproducibility assessment.

Replication of “Geospatial Resolution of Human and Bacterial Diversity with City-Scale Metagenomics” (Afshinnekoo *et al.*, 2015) focused on reconstructing the computational pipeline, processing raw data, and assessing reproducibility challenges (Table 2.2). Only the initial steps, setting up Conda environments, retrieving sequencing data, and performing quality control, were completed successfully. Modular Conda environments were built for Trimmomatic (version unspecified) (Bolger *et al.*, 2014), MetaPhlan v2.0 (Segata *et al.*, 2012), and QIIME (version unspecified) (Caporaso *et al.*, 2010) (Table 1.5) on a high-performance computing (HPC) cluster, as incompatibilities prevented reconstruction of the full environment. Raw data (PRJNA271013) were retrieved from the NCBI BioProject database (O’Leary *et al.*, 2016) and processed using the study’s quality control criteria: >Q20 reads, <1% PhiX alignment, and insert sizes of 550 ± 70 bp. Reads were trimmed, filtered, and prepared for MegaBLAST (version unspecified) (Wolfsberg and Madden, 2001) using the FASTX Toolkit (version unspecified) (Table 2.2).

Although subsequent steps were outlined, including arranging scripts and configuring additional software, resource constraints limited replication to the early stages. Completing downstream analyses, including taxonomic assignment with MEGAN (version unspecified) (Huson *et al.*, 2007), pathogen screening with SURPI (version unspecified) (Naccache *et al.*, 2014) and BWA v7.10 (Li and Durbin, 2010), and geospatial/statistical analyses, would have required disproportionate investment, underscoring the impracticality of fully replicating the study within this project.

Table 2.2 Summary of methods and computational analysis steps for Afshinnekoo *et al.* (2015) and Kang *et al.* (2018) study replication.

Aspect	2015 Study	2018 Study
Objective	Analysed human and bacterial diversity in city environments using metagenomics.	Investigated metro traffic and environmental effects on the skin microbiome and resistome.
Bioinformatics Tools	Kraken, MetaPhlan, and Bowtie2 for taxonomic profiling and alignment.	PanPhlan and HUMAnN2 for taxonomy, pathway, and resistome analysis.
Data Processing	Low-quality reads filtered with Trimmomatic.	Pre-processed with Cutadapt; host sequences removed using BWA.
Taxonomic Assignment	Microbial diversity profiled with Kraken and MetaPhlan.	Species and resistome profiling with MetaPhlan2, targeting ARGs.
Functional Analysis	Pathways annotated with KEGG; no resistome analysis.	HUMAnN2 combined with ARG detection and functional profiling.
Metadata	Sample details included but lacked standardization or environmental context.	Comprehensive metadata aligned with MIxS, including traffic and environmental variables.
Quality Control	Basic filtering and trimming.	Added deduplication and advanced contamination detection.
Host Depletion	Bowtie2 used for host sequence removal.	Iterative Bowtie2 protocol improved precision.
Functional Annotation	KEGG pathway annotation without resistome analysis.	HUMAnN2 linked ARGs with microbial taxonomy and environmental variables.
Data Availability	Sequencing data deposited in SRA; workflows not shared.	Data and workflows shared publicly via SRA and GitHub.
Reproducibility Considerations	Reproducibility acknowledged but not implemented; limited standardization, custom scripts not shared.	More detailed workflows and metadata provided; standardized pipelines shared publicly, though some software and scripts remained unavailable.

2.2.2 Reproducing Kang *et al.* (2018)

Replication of “The Environmental Exposures and Inner- and Intercity Traffic Flows of the Metro System May Contribute to the Skin Microbiome and Resistome” (Kang *et al.*, 2018) focused on bioinformatics analysis. The first five analytical steps were completed, but further progress was limited by resource demands. Conda environments were created for Cutadapt (version unspecified) (Martin, 2011), BWA (version unspecified) (Li and Durbin, 2010), R v3.2, ResFinder (version unspecified) (Kleinheinz *et al.*, 2014), and DIAMOND (version unspecified) (Buchfink *et al.*, 2015) (Table 1.5) (Table 2.2). Raw sequencing data and metadata (BioProject PRJNA413474, SRP119528) describing passenger exposure, traffic flows, and environmental factors were retrieved from NCBI. Reads were pre-processed with Cutadapt using unspecified quality trimming and filtering parameters on an HPC cluster. Alignment and assembly with

Bowtie2 or BWA were initiated but could not be completed due to insufficient methodological detail.

Downstream steps, therefore, could not be implemented. These included taxonomic profiling with DIAMOND and LCA assignment in MEGAN5 (Huson *et al.*, 2011) targeting the 744 most abundant species (95% of reads). Although software and workflows were partially arranged, the time required for these early stages exhausted feasible resources. Additional analyses, including pan-genome reconstruction with PanPhlAn (Scholz *et al.*, 2016), antimicrobial resistance gene (ARG) detection with DIAMOND against CARD (Alcock *et al.*, 2023) and ResFams (Gibson *et al.*, 2015), horizontal gene transfer inference with RANGER-DTL v2.0 (Bansal *et al.*, 2012), and ARG abundance, virulence factor identification (VFDB), and diversity metrics (Table 1.4) (Simpson index, weighted UniFrac), were also prohibitive (Table 2.2).

2.2.3 Sample collection and sequencing

Skin microbiome samples were collected with FLOQSwabs® from the forearm of a healthy volunteer. A previously collected *Escherichia coli* isolate from wound swabs served as a positive control and was cultured on nutrient agar following protocols in “Sample collection, preparation, and sequencing protocols for developing metagenomic approaches in skin and wound microbiome analysis” (DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1; Appendix 1: Sections 1-2). A human alveolar epithelial cell subculture (ATCC CCL-185) was also maintained according to Thermo Fisher Scientific’s protocol. DNA was extracted from all samples using a modified Mu-DNA protocol (Sellers *et al.*, 2021) (Appendix 1: Section 3).

DNA concentration, purity, and fragment length were assessed using Qubit dsDNA HS assay (Invitrogen, 2024), NanoDrop spectrophotometry (Thermo Scientific, 2006-24), and GelRed® agarose gel electrophoresis, respectively (Appendix 1: Section 4). A DNA standard control (ATCC Oral Microbiome Genomic Mix, MSA-1004), consistent with benchmarking approaches discussed in [Subsection 1.9.1](#), was diluted with human DNA to generate mixtures containing 0%, 10%, 75%, and 90% human DNA (Appendix 1: Section 5). Libraries were prepared using the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) Rapid Sequencing DNA PCR Barcoding Kit (SQK-RPB004) (Appendix 1: Section 7; Appendix 2). Sequencing was performed locally on a bioinformatics workstation (AMD Ryzen 5 5600X, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti GPU, Ubuntu v20.04 LTS) with a MinION Mk1B with a FLO-FLG001 R9.4.1 Flongle flow cell, primed and loaded per kit protocol. Further details on sample collection, library preparation, and Nanopore sequencing are provided in [Section 3.2](#).

2.2.4 Workflow and environment management

All FAST5 files from ONT sequencing runs of libraries constructed in [Subsection 2.2.3](#) (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 2) were basecalled and demultiplexed with Guppy v6.0.6 on a local bioinformatics workstation using the high-accuracy model (Wick *et al.*, 2019) (Table 1.5). Outputs were analysed on an HPC cluster with the Metagenomic Microbiome Combination Analysis Workflow (MMCAW), a reproducible Snakemake v7.22.0 workflow (Mölder *et al.*, 2021) developed using the Snakemake GitHub template (Snakemake-workflows, 2024). Software environments were managed with Conda (Python v3.10.8) to ensure reproducibility and dependency control.

Input data included unblocked read ID lists, FASTQ files, Guppy sequence summaries, and a metadata file describing all samples and runs. Parameters and user-defined options (e.g., assembly, host removal, database creation) were set via the workflow configuration file. Analyses were executed on the University of Hull's HPC facility, Viper, with support from its technical team. MMCAW's functionality and computational requirements were optimized for efficient processing. Complete descriptions of the workflows, including parameters, outputs, and usage, are provided in Appendices 3–4 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17753185; DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752049) and the [GitHub user guides](#).

2.2.5 Read quality control and assembly

Standard metagenomic microbiome was executed using Snakemake on an HPC cluster and preprocessing included quality control, optional host filtering, and contig assembly. Quality control was performed using fastp v0.23.2 (Chen *et al.*, 2018) to filter sequencing reads based on quality and length, ensuring high-quality input data for downstream analyses. Host filtering, an optional preprocessing step, was conducted with Minimap2 v2.24 (Li, 2021) and SAMtools v1.16.1 (Li *et al.*, 2009) (Table 1.5), using The Human Genome Project (GRCh38.p14) human genome reference to identify and remove host-derived sequences. Following host filtering, Seqkit v2.3.1 (Li, 2024) was employed to convert files into FASTA format for subsequent assembly. For optional contig assembly, Flye v2.9.1 (Kolmogorov *et al.*, 2020) was used with the --meta option, optimized for metagenomic nanopore sequencing data as specified by the developers. Between these analysis steps, Seqtk was used to generate sequence statistics (Table 1.4) for all sequencing runs, for results on data quality and composition.

2.2.6 Taxonomic assignment of contigs

Assembled contigs were classified with CAT v5.2.3 (von Meijenfeldt *et al.*, 2019), Kraken2 v2.1.2 (Wood *et al.*, 2019), and BLAST v2.13.0 (Altschul *et al.*, 1990), which differ in methodology,

performance, and application (Table 1.5) (Table 2.3). Databases were generated in an MMCAW sub-workflow on an HPC cluster using default developer settings: Kraken2 included human, viral, archaeal, and bacterial genomes from the NCBI taxonomy database (O'Leary *et al.*, 2016); BLAST was based on NCBI NT; and CAT used NCBI taxonomy and protein databases (O'Leary *et al.*, 2016). BLAST outputs were processed with a custom Python script, adapted from MEGAN (Huson *et al.*, 2007), to implement a modified Lowest Common Ancestor (LCA) algorithm with adjustable parameters, followed by contig counts per taxonomy. CAT classifications were run with default settings, producing TSV-formatted reports summarized with Python scripts. Kraken2 results, also generated with default parameters, were exported in Kraken and TSV formats and contig counts calculated with Python scripts.

Results from all assigners were merged across samples and sequencing runs in R v4.2.2. Visualizations, including bar plots, stacked bar plots, heatmaps, and community analyses (alpha and beta diversity metrics) (Table 1.4) were performed with Python and R scripts on an HPC cluster (Appendices 4–5). Seqtk v2.3.1 (Li, 2024) was used throughout to compile sequence statistics.

Table 2.3 Description table of the three taxonomy assigners implemented, compared, and combined in MMCAW: Contig Annotation Tool (CAT), Kraken2, and Basic Local Alignment Search Tool (BLAST).

Feature	CAT	Kraken2	BLAST
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High accuracy for contigs due to protein-based classification Uses a weighted voting algorithm for robust taxonomic assignments Ideal for identifying conserved sequences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extremely fast and computationally efficient for high-throughput workflows Scalable to large datasets Effective for rapid profiling of raw sequencing reads 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly sensitive, capable of detecting distant homologs Flexible database selection allows for custom applications Provides detailed alignment information
Limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Computationally intensive and slow due to reliance on large protein databases Requires preassembled contigs, unsuitable for raw reads 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relatively lower sensitivity for sequences poorly represented in reference databases Dependent on database quality and coverage May struggle with novel or highly divergent taxa 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Output requires manual interpretation Detailed, small-scale analyses requiring high sensitivity Computationally intensive due to extensive pairwise alignments
Database Usage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relies on protein databases, such as NCBI NR, and corresponding taxa IDs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Databases are user-customizable but need optimization for specific studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allows use of specialized or highly curated custom databases
Speed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slow due to computational demands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Optimized for high-speed analyses in large-scale studies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depends on the size of the database and number of query sequences
Sensitivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extremely high sensitivity for contigs, especially conserved sequences in protein databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderate sensitivity, highly dependent on the representation of references in the database 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Moderately high sensitivity, capable of detecting remote homologs through detailed alignments
Specificity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High specificity for correctly annotated sequences due to protein-level matching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High specificity for well-represented taxa, but risk of misclassification for poorly represented sequences 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly specific for close matches but may face ambiguity with distant relationships
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited scalability for large datasets due to slow processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Highly scalable, suitable for large datasets and real-time analyses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low scalability for bulk data processing due to computational intensity

2.2.7 Comparison of taxonomy results

Data from each assigner described in [Subsection 2.2.6](#) were transformed and standardized for community analysis and comparison. Bash and R v4.2.2 scripts were used to analyse taxonomic abundance and diversity metrics, with outputs visualized as tables, principal component analysis (PCA) plots, and scatterplots (Table 1.4) (Appendices 4–5). Alpha diversity, reflecting species richness and evenness, was calculated with the Shannon index, a widely used ecological metric (Jost, 2007; Walters and Martiny, 2020; Kers and Saccenti, 2022). Beta diversity, assessing community differences between samples, was measured with Bray–Curtis dissimilarity, which quantifies species abundance differences across samples (Table 1.4) (Whittaker, 1972; Jost, 2007; Walters and Martiny, 2020; Kers and Saccenti, 2022). Custom Python v3.10.8 scripts, executed using Snakemake on an HPC cluster, calculated average contigs per taxonomy level, identified the most abundant taxa, and determined the percentage of contigs assigned to species and taxonomy richness. Diversity metrics, taxonomic abundance, and contig-level data were visualized with R v4.2.2 scripts (Appendices 4–5).

2.2.8 Assigner agreement and combination

Taxonomy names and table formats were standardized across outputs from CAT v5.2.3 (von Meijenfeldt *et al.*, 2019), Kraken2 v2.1.2 (Wood *et al.*, 2019), and BLAST v2.13.0 (Altschul *et al.*, 1990). CAT reports required no modification, while custom Python v3.10.8 scripts were used in Snakemake on an HPC cluster to assign taxonomy names to taxon IDs for BLAST and Kraken2 outputs. A second Python script compared taxonomy results from all assigners at each level using contig IDs from assembly (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17753185; DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752049; Appendices 3–4).

If at least two assigners agreed on a classification, that assignment was retained; if all three disagreed, the result was designated “no_agreement.” The script also recorded which assigners agreed or disagreed per contig. Percent agreement between assigners was calculated across taxonomy levels: complete agreement scored 100%, while partial matches (e.g., only kingdom and phylum) were assigned 33%. Agreement and disagreement results were summarized across all contigs and samples, generating detailed consensus tables (Appendix 4; Appendix 5: Section 1).

2.2.9 Large dataset and reproducibility testing

Datasets of varying complexity and size, including mock communities and skin and peri-wound samples with differing levels of human content and taxonomic diversity, were analysed. Performance metrics, such as average time to complete each workflow rule, total time for

analysis steps, and resource utilization, were systematically recorded by default in Snakemake v7.22.0 (Mölder *et al.*, 2021) workflow runs on an HPC cluster. Resource usage, including CPU and memory consumption, was benchmarked for each rule using Snakemake's built-in benchmarking feature (Appendix 4). The benchmarking outputs allowed for the evaluation of workflow efficiency across diverse input sizes, such as varying numbers and sizes of FASTQ files and differing amounts of metagenomic data (Lloréns-Rico *et al.*, 2021). The data generated included time-to-completion for individual rules and overall workflow steps, which was later correlated with input/output file sizes using a custom R v4.2.2 script (Appendix 5: Section 1).

2.2.10 Reproducibility and data availability

To promote transparency and facilitate reproducibility, all detailed protocols, scripts, and instructions for all wet and dry lab procedures described are available in Appendices 1-4 and archived in Zenodo repositories. Full description of all consumables, equipment, and kits used for wet lab methods are available on protocols.io (DOI:

10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1), as described in Appendix 1. Whenever feasible, all raw sequencing data produced and bioinformatic processes have been developed in reproducible workflows and/or scripts and archived (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17753185; DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752049; Appendices 3-4). All analysis results and scripts for taxonomy assigner results, practical reproducibility, workflow performance and scalability, and the corresponding figure scripts can be found in Appendix 5: Section 1 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007).

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Replication highlights practical barriers to reproducible pipelines

Replication efforts for two key skin microbiome metagenomic studies (Table 2.2), as described in [Subsections 2.2.1-2.2.2](#), emphasized four practical enablers of reproducibility: workflow management, rigorous data sharing and transparency, comprehensive archiving and documentation, and experimental flexibility. Despite their importance, none were fully implemented, and replication progress was limited to 30% of the workflow from Afshinnekoo *et al.* (2015) and 66% from Kang *et al.* (2018). These outcomes highlight how feasibility, time, and resources shape reproducibility and replicability, which require substantially greater investment than repeatability with the same researcher, data, and methods (Figure 2.1A).

Figure 2.1 Visual demonstration of practical reproducibility considerations for Afshinnekoo *et al.* (2015) and Kang *et al.* (2018). (A) The three levels of reproducibility based on the relative amount of effort and time required for each with the trustworthiness of results. (B) FAIR principles and the relative elements for each from Afshinnekoo *et al.* (2015) and Kang *et al.* (2018). (Appendix 5: Section 1)

Both studies illustrate how resource demands and barriers, such as software incompatibilities, missing intermediate datasets, and insufficient documentation, disrupt

replication even when FAIR principles of data sharing, transparency, and accessibility are followed (Figure 2.1B). Afshinnkoo *et al.* (2015) deposited raw sequencing data and geospatial metadata in public repositories, yet reliance on unavailable custom scripts created major barriers. Substituting incompatible software versions added complexity, while the absence of error analyses further limited reproducibility, particularly for groups with restricted computational resources. Kang *et al.* (2018) shared raw sequencing data and used containerized workflows (Docker and Singularity), but missing intermediate and processed datasets hindered full validation. Documentation gaps for resistome tools and parameters, alongside limited statistical reporting, including absent p-values and confidence intervals, further weakened robustness.

Together, these examples underscore systemic reproducibility challenges in metagenomic pipelines. In Afshinnkoo *et al.* (2015), reliance on non-public custom scripts, lack of workflow standardization, and substitution of resource-intensive tools such as BLAST exposed gaps in environment management. Sensitivity analyses, while identified as essential, were underutilized due to missing error analyses, limiting interpretability (Figure 2.2). Kang *et al.* (2018) advanced reproducibility with Docker and Singularity, improving cross-platform consistency, yet unclear documentation, incomplete metadata, and absence of comparative taxonomic analyses restricted robustness. Eight principles were defined from replication of the two studies and supporting literature, each qualitatively weighted based on their observed impact on replication feasibility during the reconstruction process. Reproducibility depended most on workflow management, data sharing and transparency, experimental flexibility, and rigorous archiving and documentation (Figure 2.2), as these factors consistently introduced the greatest practical barriers when absent or incompletely reported.

Figure 2.2 Bar plot of main reproducibility principles derived from practical replication of Afshinnekoo *et al.* (2015) and Kang *et al.* (2018), qualitatively weighted by their observed impact on replication feasibility. (Appendix 5: Section 1)

2.3.2 MMCAW achieves stable performance with efficient resource use

The performance of the Metagenomic Microbiome Combination Analysis Workflow (MMCAW) was assessed using Snakemake’s workflow statistics and benchmarking features (Mölder *et al.*, 2021) to evaluate execution times, step durations, CPU, and memory use. MMCAW demonstrated consistent robustness, achieving a 100% success rate across all rules and runs, underscoring its stability. To assess efficiency, execution times were grouped by analytical process, excluding intermediate steps requiring only a few seconds.

Among the most resource-intensive tasks, taxonomy assignment and contig assembly dominated, with execution times ranging from 300 to >2000 seconds. CAT was the slowest assigner, averaging several hours per sample; BLAST required 12–17 minutes; and Kraken2 was fastest at ~5 minutes. Human sequence removal was the next most demanding step at ~180 seconds per sample (Figure 2.3A). Other processes, including data transformation, plot generation, and read statistics, were lightweight, averaging <30 seconds and efficiently handled with R and Python scripts. Processing times were slightly longer for skin microbiome samples than for mock communities, reflecting lower DNA yields and greater host contamination (Figure 2.3A).

Scalability analyses showed that execution time and CPU load were not directly correlated: greater computational power did not always shorten run times. CAT and BLAST required the most resources, with BLAST showing the greatest variability (Figure 2.3B). Despite this, BLAST consistently outperformed CAT in speed. Assembly rules required long execution

times but relatively low CPU loads, while Kraken2 demonstrated the best scalability, maintaining consistent run times and CPU demands with minimal resources. Quality control steps completed quickly, though CPU use varied (Figure 2.3B).

Figure 2.3 Snakemake workflow performance metrics for MMCAW. (A) Average runtime in seconds for major analysis steps that took at least 3 seconds to complete for mock community and skin microbiome runs. (B) Execution time in seconds compared to average CPU load for all rules in workflow for mock community and skin microbiome runs. (C) Average CPU load for each major analysis step that took at least 3 seconds to complete for mock community and skin microbiome runs. (Appendix 5: Section 1)

CPU demands also varied by dataset type. Mock community samples displayed greater variability in CPU load than skin samples, though average loads were similar overall; only a few rules required more cores for skin data (Figures 2.3B, 2.3C). The highest CPU loads were observed for BLAST (25–425 cores), followed by CAT (~200 cores per step on average). BLAST

averaged closer to 300 cores, while Minimap2 for human sequence removal ranked third, near CAT levels. Most remaining steps consistently required <100 cores (Figure 2.3C).

2.3.3 Taxonomy assigners reveal complementary strengths and limitations

To compare assignments from BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2, outputs were standardized for downstream analysis, enabling direct evaluation of assignment patterns and their combined potential. Overlap analysis revealed substantial variation in the taxa identified by each assigner, reflecting methodological differences in classification strategies (Figure 2.4). Kraken2 identified the largest number of unique taxa (43; 41%), followed by CAT (25; 24%) and BLAST (18; 17%). The greatest overlap occurred between Kraken2 and BLAST (7; 7%), whereas CAT and BLAST shared no uniquely overlapping taxa. Despite these differences, 11 taxa (10%) were consistently identified across all three assigners, demonstrating a stable core of concordant classifications across methods.

Figure 2.4 Venn diagram showing the overlap in species-level taxonomic assignments among BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2. Number and proportion of unique and shared taxa identified by each assigner following standardisation of taxonomy outputs. Counts represent presence/absence of taxa (abundance ≥ 1) rather than read abundance, with ambiguous classifications excluded. (Appendix 5: Section 1)

Differences in assigner behaviour were also reflected in the number and distribution of taxonomic assignments across classification levels. BLAST assigned the highest average number of contigs across most taxonomic levels, while Kraken2 produced the most assignments at the species level. CAT generated fewer assignments overall but introduced the greatest variability, particularly at finer resolutions (Figure 2.5A). Additionally, distinct richness patterns emerged across tools. CAT showed steadily increasing richness at higher levels but a sharp decline at the species level. Kraken2 produced the highest richness at the species level but the lowest at broader levels, whereas BLAST followed an intermediate trajectory, with richness gradually decreasing across levels (Figure 2.5B).

Figure 2.5 Comparison of taxonomy assignment performance across taxonomy levels for BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2. (A) Number of contigs assigned to species, family, class, and kingdom taxonomy levels for each taxonomy assigner. (B) Richness, or number of taxa, assigned to species, family, class, and kingdom taxonomy levels for each taxonomy assigner. (C) Most common taxonomy assignment for species, family, class, and kingdom taxonomy levels for each assigner in mock community and skin microbiome runs. (Appendix 5: Section 1)

Despite differences among the tools, all three consistently identified Bacteria as the dominant kingdom. At finer scales, mock communities were dominated by Bacteroidia and Gammaproteobacteria at the class level, while skin microbiomes shifted toward Bacilli and Actinomycetes (Figure 2.5C). At the family level, Enterobacteriaceae prevailed in mock

communities, while Staphylococcaceae dominated skin datasets, consistent with host association. At the species level, *Staphylococcus aureus* was consistently detected across all assigners in skin samples, while mock communities retained broader species diversity (Figure 2.5C).

Clustering patterns further illustrated methodological diversity. BLAST produced compact clusters, indicating highly consistent assignments, while CAT and Kraken2 displayed broader distributions, reflecting flexibility in classification. All assigners clearly distinguished mock from skin microbiomes, consistent with underlying biological differences (Figure 2.6A). Skin samples consistently formed wider, more dispersed clusters than mock communities, aligning with their greater complexity. CAT and Kraken2 overlapped substantially, suggesting similar classification outputs, whereas BLAST showed more distinct separations, particularly in mock datasets (Figure 2.6A).

Shannon diversity scores reinforced these complementary outputs. In mock communities, Kraken2 achieved the highest scores with broad variability, BLAST yielded moderate scores with narrower ranges, and CAT produced the lowest with limited variability. In skin samples, Kraken2 again produced the highest scores and widest distributions, while BLAST and CAT returned lower but consistent values, with BLAST slightly broader than CAT (Figure 2.6B).

Figure 2.6 Comparison of species diversity metrics for BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2. (A) PCA plot of community dissimilarities of all taxonomic assigners for mock community and skin microbiome samples calculated with Bray-Curtis dissimilarity. (B) Shannon scores for mock community and skin microbiome samples from each taxonomy assigner. (Appendix 5: Section 1)

2.3.4 Consensus framework improves reliability across taxonomic resolutions

Taxonomic assignments generated by CAT, Kraken2, and BLAST were standardized with custom data transformation scripts to ensure consistent taxonomy formats across outputs (Appendix 4). This standardization enabled direct comparison of agreement levels among assigners at each taxonomic rank and the calculation of consensus results. Kraken2 and BLAST demonstrated the highest agreement percentages, while CAT showed lower agreement with both. Agreement between BLAST and CAT was the lowest, reflecting methodological differences across tools (Figure 2.7A).

Figure 2.7 Agreement among taxonomic assigners BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2. (A) Average percent of assignment agreement between each taxonomy assigner. (B) Average number of "no agreement" assignments among all taxonomy levels. (C) Assigner consensus results for species in mock community samples. (D) Assigner consensus results for species in skin microbiome samples. (Appendix 5: Section 1)

Examination of assignments with no agreement among all three assigners showed the highest levels of disagreement at the species level, followed by genus and family. Disagreement decreased steadily with broader classifications, with minimal discrepancies observed at class, phylum, and kingdom (Figure 2.7B). These patterns indicate that consensus stabilizes results at higher levels while exposing challenges in resolving fine-scale taxa.

Relative abundance profiles revealed consistent biological trends across sample types. In skin microbiome datasets, *S. aureus* frequently accounted for >50% of total abundance, with *Staphylococcus epidermidis* similarly dominant, together reflecting typical host-associated communities. Despite this dominance, large proportions of contigs in both mock and skin samples were classified as “unassigned,” “unidentified,” or “no agreement,” often exceeding 25% in skin datasets.

Mock communities displayed broader diversity, with *Fusobacterium nucleatum* and *Prevotella melaninogenica* contributing 10–20% in several samples (Figure 2.7C). *Veillonella parvula* was also prominent across both sample types, often representing >40% of relative abundance. Other samples showed more balanced distributions, with contributions from *S. aureus*, *Veillonella*, and “unidentified” sequences (Figure 2.7C).

Skin microbiome samples exhibited distinct species-level distributions. In some, *V. parvula* dominated (>60%), while others were more evenly split among *S. aureus* (30–40%) and *P. melaninogenica* (10–15%), with *Corynebacterium propinquum* detected at ~5–10% in specific cases. The “no agreement” category frequently exceeded 20% in high-complexity samples, underscoring variability in taxonomic assignments across tools (Figure 2.7D).

2.4 Discussion

Reproducibility remains a major challenge across microbiome research, shaped by biological complexity, methodological variability, and uneven adherence to best practices (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018; Knight *et al.*, 2017). Inconsistent protocols, incomplete documentation, and fragmented data management reduce comparability across studies, while limited integration of multi-omics and inconsistent metadata reporting further constrain progress (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016; Quinn *et al.*, 2018). Community efforts, including FAIR principles, workflow managers, and standardized reporting guidelines, have begun addressing these gaps, yet practical barriers persist, particularly in skin microbiome research where dynamic host–microbe interactions complicate reproducibility (Schloss, 2018; Grüning *et al.*, 2018).

To address these challenges, this study systematically evaluated reproducibility barriers through replication of two influential skin microbiome studies and the development of the Metagenomic Microbiome Combination Analysis Workflow (MMCAW). Built in Snakemake (Mölder *et al.*, 2021), MMCAW integrates BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2 into a consensus framework while embedding environment management, provenance tracking, and rigorous archiving. Benchmarking confirmed its reliability across datasets, while portability features such as containerization and workflow archiving supported transparent sharing and re-execution.

Despite the rapid expansion of microbiome research, few workflows directly address reproducibility in nanopore metagenomics or are tailored to skin ecosystems (Lloyd-Price *et al.*, 2016; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Prior studies remain difficult to replicate due to incomplete documentation, missing intermediates, and inconsistent reporting, limiting their broader impact (Ruuskanen *et al.*, 2022). By combining assigners with complementary strengths, systematically benchmarking performance, and replicating elements of published skin microbiome work (Lloréns-Rico *et al.*, 2021), this study demonstrates how reproducible frameworks can overcome these barriers. MMCAW improves reliability of taxonomic classification, reduces ambiguity through consensus, and provides a scalable, transparent platform that addresses critical gaps in microbiome bioinformatics and supports clinically relevant applications.

2.4.1 Reproducibility lessons from replication

Reproducibility in microbiome research depends on clear environment management, rigorous data tracking, comprehensive documentation and archiving, and robust comparative analyses. This study highlights both the barriers to and enablers of these practices. Replication attempts for two influential skin microbiome studies, “Geospatial Resolution of Human and Bacterial Diversity with City-Scale Metagenomics” (Afshinnekoo *et al.*, 2015) and “The Environmental Exposures and Inner- and Intercity Traffic Flows of the Metro System May Contribute to the Skin

Microbiome and Resistome” (Kang *et al.*, 2018), illustrated common challenges, as shown in Figure 2.2. The Afshinnkoo *et al.* workflow could only be reproduced to 30% due to software incompatibilities and insufficient documentation, while Kang *et al.* reached 66% before resource constraints prevented further progress. Despite addressing FAIR principles with accessible raw sequencing data and metadata (Figure 2.1), key components required for full reproducibility were not provided, including intermediate processing files, detailed parameter settings, and complete documentation of software versions, dependencies, and computational environments. Although the overall analytical workflows were described, the absence of these details introduced substantial ambiguity in implementation, requiring iterative optimisation and interpretation at multiple stages. These limitations created significant replication bottlenecks, demanding considerable expertise, time, and computational resources to approximate the original analyses.

Building directly on these lessons, the Metagenomic Microbiome Combination Analysis Workflow (MMCAW) was developed to address reproducibility gaps. By integrating BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2 within a modular Snakemake framework (Mölder *et al.*, 2021), MMCAW balances computational efficiency with reproducibility and improves reliability through complementary assigners. Standardized workflows, transparent provenance tracking, and methodological flexibility make the framework adaptable to diverse microbiome research needs. While tools such as Snakemake and Nextflow (Di Tommaso *et al.*, 2017) help address reproducibility, MMCAW extends these gains by embedding consensus-based taxonomy and comparative analyses.

The barriers observed here reflect systemic challenges across disciplines. In microbiome research, biological variability and methodological inconsistencies have long complicated reproducibility (Gilbert *et al.*, 2018; Knight *et al.*, 2017). More broadly, irreproducibility undermines research globally: Ioannidis (2016b) showed bias and selective reporting weaken reliability; Begley and Ellis (2012) found only 6 of 53 landmark preclinical cancer studies reproducible; and Nosek *et al.* (2015) reported just 39% of psychology studies consistent with prior findings. Irreproducible preclinical research alone costs an estimated \$28 billion annually in the U.S. (Freedman *et al.*, 2015).

Computational biology has responded by emphasizing workflow transparency and data stewardship. Sandve *et al.* (2013) outlined open data, documentation, and version control in “Ten Simple Rules for Reproducible Computational Research,” while the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) highlight the value of standardized data management (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016). These principles are especially critical in microbiome science, where community-driven standardization has been repeatedly called for (Franzosa *et*

al., 2018; Quinn *et al.*, 2018). Guided by these principles, MMCAW demonstrates how reproducibility can be strengthened in nanopore metagenomic analysis of human microbiome samples by integrating multiple assigners, addressing systemic barriers in documentation and environment management, and providing transparent, modular workflows.

2.4.2 Workflow scalability and efficiency gains

The Metagenomic Microbiome Combination Analysis Workflow (MMCAW) achieved a 100% success rate across all rules and runs, confirming its robustness, scalability, and reliability. Benchmarking with Snakemake (Mölder *et al.*, 2021), as depicted in Figure 2.3, showed predictable performance across datasets and identified resource-intensive steps users can anticipate when planning analyses. Taxonomy assignment and contig assembly were the most demanding: CAT required several hours per run, BLAST averaged 12–17 minutes, and Kraken2 was consistently the fastest at ~5 minutes per sample. Human sequence removal took ~180 seconds, while data transformation and visualization steps finished in under 30 seconds. Processing was slightly longer for skin microbiome datasets, reflecting lower DNA yields and higher host contamination (Figure 2.3A). Scalability tests indicated that CAT and BLAST consumed the most CPU resources, with BLAST showing greater variability, while Kraken2 maintained stable performance with minimal resources (Figure 2.3B). Together, these benchmarks demonstrate how MMCAW balances reproducibility with practical resource use, providing actionable guidance on where bottlenecks occur and how the user can allocate computing power efficiently.

The workflow also incorporated best practices that strengthen reproducibility. Version control with Git and software management with Conda ensured consistent environments (Ram, 2013). Automation supported reliable execution across platforms (Afgan *et al.*, 2018; Grüning *et al.*, 2018), while detailed documentation of tools, parameters, and datasets aligned with FAIR principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016; McQuilton *et al.*, 2016). Snakemake's `--archive` command packaged all data, code, environments, and configurations into a portable file, enabling seamless sharing on platforms such as Zenodo (Mölder *et al.*, 2021) and supporting verifiable reruns.

MMCAW builds on a growing ecosystem of modular, reproducible workflows that enhance flexibility and interoperability. Platforms such as Nextflow, Snakemake, and Galaxy (Di Tommaso *et al.*, 2017; Mölder *et al.*, 2021; Afgan *et al.*, 2018; Amstutz *et al.*, 2016) have underpinned pipelines from *nf-core* genomics (Ewels *et al.*, 2020) and QIIME 2 microbiome analysis (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019) to Broad's GATK workflows for variant discovery (Auwera and O'Connor, 2020). Genome assembly workflows integrating SPAdes and Prokka similarly leverage workflow engines for scalability (Bankevich *et al.*, 2012; Di Tommaso *et al.*, 2017).

MMCAW extends these advances by specifically targeting nanopore metagenomics and combining multiple taxonomic assigners into a consensus framework, while remaining modular for future tool integration.

Detailed performance metrics highlight computational trade-offs. CAT and BLAST were the most resource-intensive; BLAST required more variable CPU loads, averaging ~300 cores compared to CAT's ~200. Minimap2 host filtering ranked third in CPU demand, while assembly required longer runtimes but fewer cores. In contrast, Kraken2 scaled efficiently, maintaining low CPU requirements with stable run times (Figure 2.3C). Memory demands and large reference databases, particularly for BLAST and CAT, added additional challenges, consistent with other workflows (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Di Tommaso *et al.*, 2017). By contrast, quality control steps were more efficient, requiring minimal time and power.

These assessments show how modular, reproducible workflows can deliver efficiency alongside transparency. MMCAW balances scalability and resource demands while incorporating consensus assignments, containerization, and portable archiving, thereby enhancing reliability, fostering collaboration, and providing a practical framework for open, reproducible microbiome research.

2.4.3 Tool-specific strengths enhance assignment

The integration of complementary taxonomic assigners, Kraken2, CAT, and BLAST, demonstrated how reproducible workflows can strengthen reliability in microbiome studies. By combining these tools, MMCAW increased reproducibility and improved resolution of taxonomic profiles across datasets. While all three produced consistent classifications, methodological differences revealed complementary strengths. As shown in Figures 2.6A and 2.4, Kraken2 and BLAST showed the highest overlap, reflecting similar strategies, whereas CAT diverged more strongly, particularly in mock communities, due to its protein-based approach. Kraken2 consistently produced higher alpha diversity scores in both skin and mock datasets, highlighting sensitivity, while BLAST and CAT returned lower, more constrained values (Figure 2.6B).

Skin microbiome samples were dominated by host-associated taxa such as *S. aureus*, whereas mock communities revealed broader microbial diversity (Figure 2.5C). These patterns illustrate how assignments are shaped by tool-specific methodologies and dataset composition. Kraken2 and BLAST offered greater flexibility for sensitivity and confidence thresholds, while CAT was less adaptable but contributed improved specificity and distinct perspectives. Taxonomy assignment is central to bioinformatics and metagenomics, structuring sequences for downstream ecological inference, diversity analyses, and functional profiling (Thompson *et al.*,

2017; Hugerth and Andersson, 2017). Reliable classification prevents misleading interpretations (Meyer *et al.*, 2022), yet no single best practice exists. Tool selection influences outcomes, such as Kraken2 being optimized for speed and large-scale studies, BLAST providing accuracy at the cost of scalability, and frameworks such as QIIME 2 or RDP Classifier balancing usability and precision (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Wood *et al.*, 2019; Altschul *et al.*, 1990).

Database quality also plays a decisive role with RefSeq and GTDB providing comprehensive references (O'Leary *et al.*, 2016), but tools leverage these differently: CAT uses weighted majority voting on protein annotations, Kraken2 employs a k-mer approach for rapid profiling, and BLAST relies on local alignments for high accuracy and sensitivity (von Meijenfeldt *et al.*, 2019; Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Wood *et al.*, 2019). Performance comparisons reinforced these distinctions. BLAST excelled at detecting novel taxa through detailed alignments, whereas Kraken2 struggled in datasets with high novelty (Figure 2.5). CAT offered intermediate performance, evaluating multiple hits but with accuracy tied to database completeness and annotation integration (Zhou *et al.*, 2023; Wood *et al.*, 2019).

CAT and BLAST achieved high resolution, while Kraken2's k-mer strategy risked misclassification in complex communities (Hleap *et al.*, 2021; Wood *et al.*, 2019). Combining these assigners leveraged their complementary strengths, CAT contributed protein-level depth, Kraken2 provided scalability, and BLAST refined ambiguous classifications. Together, their integration mitigated individual limitations and produced more comprehensive and reproducible taxonomic profiles. This approach demonstrates how MMCAW delivers flexibility and robustness for diverse microbiome research contexts, ensuring classifications remain both accurate and reproducible (Thompson *et al.*, 2017; Bolyen *et al.*, 2019).

2.4.4 Consensus improves accuracy and confidence

Integrating CAT, Kraken2, and BLAST into a consensus framework proved highly effective for resolving methodological discrepancies and improving accuracy. In mock communities, as seen in Figure 2.7C, consensus results closely matched expected ATCC compositions, validating the approach. Skin microbiome datasets, as shown in Figure 2.7D, including peri-wound sites, produced distinct profiles dominated by *S. aureus* and *V. parvula*, while mock communities displayed broader diversity. These findings demonstrate the practical utility of consensus assignments for both complex clinical samples and reference datasets. Importantly, combining assigners reduced the prevalence of “unassigned” and “no agreement” categories, often exceeding 25% in skin samples (Figure 2.7), helping address persistent challenges in resolving ambiguous or poorly characterized sequences.

Most existing workflows rely on a single method for efficiency (Sczyrba *et al.*, 2017; Wood *et al.*, 2019). Examples include MetaPhlAn's marker-gene profiling (Truong *et al.*, 2015) and Kraken2's k-mer classification, which lacks secondary alignment, while MG-RAST simplifies by recommending one algorithm despite trade-offs (Meyer *et al.*, 2008; Bazinet and Cummings, 2012; Vervier *et al.*, 2016). Each approach carries limitations: Kraken2 provides speed but struggles with novel taxa (Bazinet and Cummings, 2012), BLAST achieves high accuracy but lacks scalability (Altschul *et al.*, 1990), and CAT offers contig-level robustness through weighted protein voting but lacks lower-level resolution (von Meijenfeldt *et al.*, 2019). Reconciling these differences is non-trivial, but consensus reduces bias and enhances reproducibility.

In MMCAW, consensus aligned strongly with expected profiles at higher taxonomic ranks (phylum and class), where database annotations are most consistent, while variability remained greatest at genus and species (Figure 2.7B). This outcome illustrates both the challenge of fine-scale resolution and the stabilizing effect of combining assigners. BLAST provided accurate alignments, Kraken2 contributed rapid profiling, and CAT added depth from protein annotations. Together, their integration reduced "unclassified" outputs, improved resolution, and generated more reliable profiles.

Consensus also enables flexible tool use: Kraken2 can provide rapid initial classifications, BLAST can refine low-confidence assignments, and normalization across methods yields more accurate composite results (Vervier *et al.*, 2016). Emerging hybrid frameworks such as OPAL (Meyer *et al.*, 2019) show how integration can be scaled further, complementing established approaches like MetaPhlAn and assembly-based profiling (Truong *et al.*, 2015; Mande *et al.*, 2012). Such modular strategies are increasingly recognized as essential for reproducible and comparable metagenomic analyses (Quince *et al.*, 2017; McIntyre *et al.*, 2017).

The biological and clinical relevance of this approach was reinforced by skin microbiome findings, dominance of *S. aureus* and *V. parvula* in peri-wound and skin datasets reflected known host-associated taxa (Byrd *et al.*, 2018). Thus, while variability remains at the species level, consensus clearly enhanced accuracy, reduced uncertainty, and enabled robust characterization of complex and clinically important microbial communities.

2.4.5 Limitations and future research directions

Hybrid taxonomy assignment approaches in microbiome research remain constrained by several challenges, yet these also highlight clear opportunities for improvement. In this study, only two workflows were reproduced within a limited timeframe, MMCAW was evaluated on small sample batches, and host filtering relied on GRCh38 rather than the more advanced Telomere-to-Telomere (T2T) assembly. These study-specific constraints mirror broader issues

in metagenomics, including dependence on incomplete or evolving databases (Hugerth and Andersson, 2017; Almeida *et al.*, 2021), high computational demands requiring HPC infrastructure, and the substantial time requirements of hybrid methods despite their ability to parallelize tasks (McIntyre *et al.*, 2017; Milanese *et al.*, 2019). Continued workflow optimization can reduce some burdens, while reproducibility, often the most difficult barrier, can be strengthened by modular and transparent approaches (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016).

Reproducibility is also shaped by data processing variability and privacy regulations. Legal frameworks such as HIPAA and GDPR require removal of human sequences to protect privacy, yet this step can introduce inconsistencies across studies (Fricker *et al.*, 2019; Wang *et al.*, 2025). Host contamination remains difficult, human DNA removal often leads to microbial read loss or analytical bias, reducing accuracy and reproducibility (Ganda *et al.*, 2021). Variability in workflows, software tools, and parameter choices adds further complexity (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Ruuskanen *et al.*, 2022). Addressing these issues requires scalable infrastructure, but MMCAW's modularity already demonstrates how expanding with additional assigners such as PhyloPhlAn and Sourmash can further diversify algorithms, strengthen consensus, and increase robustness against database limitations (Garrido-Oter *et al.*, 2018; Rausch *et al.*, 2019; Knight *et al.*, 2018).

Taxonomic resolution and functional annotation remain limited by incomplete reference databases (Almeida *et al.*, 2021). Integration of metagenomics with other omics layers, such as metatranscriptomics and metabolomics, is further complicated by data heterogeneity and the absence of standardized tools (Martin, 2019; Chetty and Blekhman, 2024). Software variability adds another layer of difficulty, as different parameter choices often yield divergent outcomes. These obstacles underscore the need for scalable algorithms, standardized workflows, and interoperable formats to enable reproducible multi-omics integration (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Meyer *et al.*, 2022). Planned additions to MMCAW, including functional analysis modules, represent a key step forward, enabling links between microbial identity and function. This will allow higher-resolution assignments, deeper functional interpretation, and richer cross-dataset comparisons, capabilities increasingly central to multi-omics research.

Future progress can build on these directions by prioritizing reproducibility, scalability, and standardization. Clear documentation of parameters and tools, open-access data sharing, and ongoing curation of reference databases will continue to improve taxonomic resolution and functional annotation (Bolyen *et al.*, 2019; Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016; Almeida *et al.*, 2021; Nayfach *et al.*, 2021). With additional assigners and functional modules, MMCAW is positioned to evolve into a versatile framework that adapts to emerging demands in microbiome science.

Emerging sequencing technologies provide further growth opportunities. Nanopore adaptive sequencing enables selective sequencing of microbial DNA while excluding host contamination, reducing downstream computational burdens (Payne *et al.*, 2021). By focusing on specific reads during sequencing, researchers can generate more precise datasets and improve reproducibility (Martin, 2019; Lloréns-Rico *et al.*, 2021). Standardized pipelines and universal data formats will be essential for integrating multi-omics datasets (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Franzosa *et al.*, 2018), while advances in real-time processing and data storage will improve usability (Wood *et al.*, 2019; Ondov *et al.*, 2016). Finally, cross-disciplinary collaborations, including machine learning experts and clinical researchers, will be critical to extending impact. Combining reproducible modular workflows like MMCAW with adaptive sequencing and collaborative frameworks positions microbiome research for substantial growth, enabling more reliable, scalable, and translational insights with applications in medicine, agriculture, and beyond (Zhang *et al.*, 2019; Nadarajah and Rahman, 2023; Kim *et al.*, 2024).

2.5 Conclusion

Research on the skin microbiome requires reproducibility, robust bioinformatics, and streamlined workflows, yet variability in experimental and computational methods complicates validation. While bioinformatics tools have advanced insights into microbial diversity, workflows often lack standardization for skin-specific studies, limiting translation into therapies for conditions such as atopic dermatitis, acne, and wound treatment. This study reproduced elements of influential research and distilled practical lessons on environment management, data tracking, documentation, and comparative analyses. Guided by these insights, MMCAW, a reproducible workflow was developed to integrate BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2 to generate consensus-based assignments. By balancing efficiency with transparency, MMCAW demonstrates how adaptable workflows can enhance microbial identification, improve reproducibility, and enable clinically relevant applications, supporting future innovation in dermatology and wound care.

Chapter 3 Optimizing adaptive sequencing for host DNA depletion in skin microbiome metagenomic analysis

3.1 Introduction

The human skin, spanning $\sim 1.8 \text{ m}^2$ and hosting up to ~ 1 million microbes per cm^2 , is one of the body's largest and most biologically rich interfaces (Yang *et al.*, 2022; Loomis *et al.*, 2021). Its microbiome is central to health, acting as both a physical and microbial barrier that protects against pathogens and supports immune function (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023). Accurate characterisation is therefore essential for understanding host–microbe interactions and their roles in infections and chronic wounds (Smythe and Wilkinson, 2023; Moskovicz *et al.*, 2020); however, metagenomic sequencing of skin samples is often dominated by host DNA, reducing microbial read depth and limiting both taxonomic and functional resolution (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Kong *et al.*, 2017). Traditional depletion methods, including enzymatic and chemical treatments, can mitigate this issue but risk biasing microbial structure and add laboratory steps (Marotz *et al.*, 2018; Thoendel *et al.*, 2016). Adaptive sequencing offers a promising alternative by enabling real-time rejection of human reads, providing a scalable route to improve skin microbiome profiling (Payne *et al.*, 2021).

3.1.1 Ecological complexity

One major challenge in studying the skin microbiome is the stark variation in microbial community composition across body sites (Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023). This diversity stems from physiological differences between skin environments, typically categorized as dry, moist, or oily, each supporting distinct microbial communities adapted to their specific niches (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Moskovicz *et al.*, 2020). The skin's direct exposure to the external environment, along with hygiene products and cosmetics, further introduces physical and chemical pressures that continually shape its microbial landscape (Smythe and Wilkinson, 2023; Moskovicz *et al.*, 2020).

Compounding this complexity is the high degree of inter-individual variability, which presents significant challenges in identifying consistent relationships between microbiome composition and disease. It remains unclear whether such compositional shifts are a cause or consequence of disease states (Moskovicz *et al.*, 2020). The influence of external factors on a healthy skin microbiome also remains largely unknown due to the intricate and dynamic nature of microbial interactions on the skin (Moskovicz *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, most current studies rely on relative abundance profiling, often overlooking microbial functions such as antimicrobial resistance, toxin production, or biofilm formation (Kong *et al.*, 2017; Langille, 2018). Functional

analysis of skin microbiota could elucidate the ecological interactions and structural dynamics of skin microbial communities, providing deeper insight into their roles in health and disease (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Kong *et al.*, 2017).

3.1.2 Long-read potential

Understanding the relationship between the skin microbiome and health may enable therapeutic manipulation of microbial communities to treat disease. Advances in shotgun metagenomic sequencing now allow analysis of entire microbial genomes and their functional roles within communities (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Almeida *et al.*, 2019); however, this approach presents challenges in data accuracy, processing, and volume (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Knight *et al.*, 2018). Traditional short-read sequencing fragments DNA into small segments for efficiency but requires complex assembly that often introduces errors, limiting analyses to partial genomes and hindering species-level resolution (Kong *et al.*, 2017; Quince *et al.*, 2017; Knight *et al.*, 2018).

Long-read sequencing technologies, such as Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT), overcome these limitations by generating longer DNA sequences, enabling the reconstruction of complete microbial genomes and improving taxonomic resolution. This is critical for distinguishing pathogenic from non-pathogenic strains in clinical contexts (Amarasinghe *et al.*, 2020; Almeida *et al.*, 2019); however, long-read sequencing produces massive data volumes, often terabytes per run, creating significant bottlenecks in processing, storage, and analysis (Tedersoo *et al.*, 2021; Amarasinghe *et al.*, 2020). These demands restrict accessibility and reproducibility, as the computational resources and expertise required present barriers to widespread adoption.

Improving sequencing efficiency, developing optimized algorithms, and creating accessible tools are essential to address these challenges and facilitate meaningful microbiome insights (Berger and Yu, 2023; Knight *et al.*, 2018; Almeida *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, despite their advantages, long-read platforms like ONT are prone to higher basecalling error rates than short-read technologies, introducing uncertainties that require further computational correction (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Wick *et al.*, 2019). These steps increase computational burden and may slow progress, particularly in settings lacking infrastructure, and pose challenges for high-precision applications such as strain-level identification or clinical diagnostics (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Almeida *et al.*, 2019).

3.1.3 Host contamination

A major challenge in microbiome research is host DNA contamination, which can comprise 90–99% of sequences in microbiome samples (Byrd *et al.*, 2018). Removing human

sequences is essential to reduce data size and comply with industry standards prohibiting the publication of human DNA for privacy protection (Goodman, 2016); however, this process is labour-intensive and typically occurs after preprocessing, limiting reproducibility in human microbiome studies (D'Argenio, 2018). Because most datasets are shared only after human reads have been removed, reproducibility is constrained to post-preprocessing stages that significantly influence downstream outcomes (Hwang and Hong, 2015; Schloss, 2018).

To mitigate this bottleneck, enzyme-based depletion methods are often used during DNA extraction to reduce host DNA prior to sequencing. While effective to a degree, these methods do not eliminate human DNA, which still constitutes 60–70% of reads after analysis (Marotz *et al.*, 2018; Gan *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, enzymatic depletion can introduce biases that distort microbial community composition, such as increasing *Streptococcus* and *Staphylococcus* representation while reducing *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Thoendel *et al.*, 2016; Marotz *et al.*, 2018; Nelson *et al.*, 2019). These distortions complicate the interpretation of microbial dynamics and underscore the need for bias-free alternatives.

Adaptive sequencing offers a novel solution by addressing host contamination during sequencing itself, selectively depleting or enriching genetic regions or organisms of interest (Kong *et al.*, 2017). In real time, reads matching the human genome can be identified and rejected, allowing sequencing resources to focus on microbial content (Payne *et al.*, 2021). This targeted approach reduces data volume, lowers costs, enhances reproducibility, and eliminates extensive preprocessing steps, making it a promising and efficient tool for routine use in microbiome research.

3.1.4 Adaptive sequencing

ONT is currently the only sequencing platform capable of adaptive sequencing, enabled by its real-time data acquisition and development of “ReadUntil” scripts that allow DNA or RNA molecules to be ejected mid-sequencing (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Adaptive sequencing software utilizes this capability to selectively include or exclude genetic regions or organisms, though the mechanisms and decision-making strategies vary by tool (Table 1.5) (Gamaarachchi *et al.*, 2020; Payne *et al.*, 2021). Typically, the software compares actively translocating sequences against a user-defined reference, and based on sequence similarity and user parameters, instructs the device to either “unblock” the pore, ejecting the read, or continue sequencing (Figure 3.1) (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Earlier tools relied on matching raw electrical signals, which proved computationally demanding and constrained by reference availability (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 3.1 Example process of adaptive sequencing using ReadFish to deplete reads that have one or more hits to a reference genome.

Recent advancements introduced basecalling, the translation of raw signals into nucleotide sequences, prior to comparison against reference genomes (Figure 3.1). Early basecalling-dependent tools were also computationally intensive and unable to handle large references like the human genome (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022). ReadFish was the first to overcome this, enabling real-time comparison against large references and thus becoming the first practical tool for adaptive sequencing (Table 1.5) (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Since then, additional tools such as ReadBouncer (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022) and ONT’s in-house adaptive sampling software have been developed; however, application of these tools remains limited, especially in metagenomic studies of the human microbiome. Most existing research has focused on host DNA depletion, often combining enzymatic and adaptive methods. Of these, one study targeted eukaryotic viruses (Hewel *et al.*, 2024), while others focused on bacterial and microbial communities of the respiratory (Gan *et al.*, 2021; Cheng *et al.*, 2022) and reproductive systems (Marquet *et al.*, 2022).

This study addresses a major limitation in skin microbiome research: the dominance of host DNA, which reduces microbial resolution and constrains downstream analysis. In line with the overarching aim of this thesis to improve reproducibility and diagnostic capacity, this work focuses on the application and optimisation of adaptive sequencing for selective human DNA

depletion in skin microbiome samples. Using portable nanopore sequencing platforms, the study aims to evaluate the performance of adaptive sequencing tools and develop a structured framework for analysing both accepted and rejected reads in real time. By systematically assessing computational strategies and experimental design, this chapter explores how sequencing outputs can be actively shaped to enhance microbial signal while maintaining community integrity. In doing so, it advances adaptive sequencing as a practical and accessible approach for improving the quality and interpretability of host-associated metagenomic data.

3.2 Methods and materials

Ethical approval was provided by the Hull Royal Tissue ethics committee (REC: 19/NE/0150) and the Faculty Ethics Committee for the Faculty of Science and Engineering at the University of Hull.

3.2.1 Sample collection and extraction

Skin microbiome samples were collected from a 3.8 cm² area on the upper or lower forearm of a healthy volunteer using FLOQSwabs® dipped in sterile normal saline (0.9% NaCl). A previously collected *Escherichia coli* isolate from wound swabs, described in [Subsection 4.2.1](#), was used as a positive control and cultured on nutrient agar following the “Sample collection, preparation, and sequencing protocols for developing metagenomic approaches in skin and wound microbiome analysis” (DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1; Appendix 1: Sections 1-2). A human alveolar epithelial cell subculture (ATCC CCL-185) was maintained and passaged using Thermo Fisher Scientific’s cell culture protocol. DNA was extracted from all samples using a modified Mu-DNA protocol (Sellers *et al.*, 2021) (Appendix 1: Section 3).

DNA concentration, purity, and fragment length were assessed using Qubit dsDNA HS assay (Invitrogen, 2024), NanoDrop spectrophotometry (Thermo Scientific, 2006-24), and GelRed® agarose gel electrophoresis, respectively (Appendix 1: Section 4). The Oral Microbiome Genomic Mix (ATCC MSA-1004), a standard metagenomic control as described in [Subsection 1.9.1](#) (Chung *et al.*, 2020), was diluted with purified human DNA to generate samples containing approximately 0%, 10%, 75%, and 90% human DNA (Appendix 1: Section 5).

3.2.2 Software installation and configuration

Human genome references were obtained from the RefSeq database (O’Leary *et al.*, 2016), including GRCh38.p14 (The Human Genome Project) and T2T-CHM13v2.0 (T2T Consortium) on a local bioinformatics workstation (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 6: Section 1). In-house ONT adaptive sequencing experiments were conducted on a GridION Mk1 platform (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, UK) using MinKNOW v5.2.2 (Table 1.5), configured according to manufacturer instructions. Sequencing parameters specified GRCh38.p14 as the reference genome, set reads matching the reference to be unblocked (rejected), and excluded the use of a Minimap2 index or BED file, as the entire genome was targeted.

MinKNOW was installed on a local bioinformatics workstation (AMD Ryzen 5 5600X, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti GPU, Ubuntu v20.04 LTS), as adaptive software requirements were not provided by developers. ReadBouncer v1.2.1 and dependencies were compiled from source and tested per Ulrich *et al.* (2022) (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 7).

Software parameters were specified in a configuration file detailing MinKNOW API settings, data transfer size and speed, and reference targets for enrichment or depletion (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 8). MinKNOW's data output was reduced to 0.4 seconds, and Guppy's decision speed was increased as described in Payne *et al.* (2021) and Ulrich *et al.* (2022).

Adaptive sequencing with ReadFish v0.0.2 required installation of Guppy v6.0.6 (Wick *et al.*, 2019), Minimap2 v2.26 (Li, 2021) and ReadUntil v3.0.0 (Oxford Nanopore Technologies) via a custom Conda environment (Python v3.7) using Miniconda (Table 1.5) on a local bioinformatics workstation (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 9). The human genome references were indexed using Minimap2. Python v3.7 scripts were used to extract contig IDs from fasta files (Appendix 6: Sections 3–4), and ReadFish configuration files were created for each run (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 10: Section 1), then validated in ReadFish per Payne *et al.* (2021).

3.2.3 Library preparation and sequencing

Libraries for each dataset (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 2: Section 1) were prepared from samples described in [Subsection 3.2.1](#) using the ONT Rapid Sequencing DNA PCR Barcoding Kit (SQK-RPB004) following the manufacturer's protocol (Appendix 1: Section 7). For sequencing, a FLO-FLG001 R9.4.1 Flongle flow cell was inserted into a MinION Mk1B (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, UK), primed, and loaded with the prepared library per the same protocol.

Sequencing was initiated in MinKNOW v5.2.2 on a local bioinformatics workstation with the following parameters: DNA sequencing mode, minimum read length of 20 bp, library kit set to SQK-RPB004, live basecalling disabled, and output in FAST5 format (Appendix 1: Section 8). For control and in-house ONT adaptive sequencing runs, the procedure was repeated using a FLO-MIN106 R9.4.1 MinION flow cell on a GridION Mk1 platform, with identical library preparation and sequencing parameters.

3.2.4 Program initiation and optimization

Approximately 24 hours before each adaptive sequencing run, a control run was performed using the same bioinformatics workstation, final library, equipment, and parameters as the corresponding adaptive detection run. For runs using ONT's in-house adaptive software, the options described in [Subsection 3.2.2](#) were selected. Due to limited configurability, such as the lack of Flongle support, mapping threshold customization, or adjustable parameters, externally developed software became the primary focus of this study.

Adaptive sequencing with external software involved using a fresh Flongle flow cell, launching a Guppy basecalling server, and activating either ReadBouncer or ReadFish once sequencing began on a local bioinformatics workstation (Appendix 1: Section 9). Because developer guidelines for optimal software performance and computational requirements were not provided, playback runs were first conducted to evaluate software behaviour, as described in Payne *et al.* (2021) (Appendix 1: Section 9), followed by experimental runs to optimize host depletion.

Optimization involved adjusting various Guppy v6.0.6 parameters (Table 3.1) (Benton, 2021), and monitoring GPU usage, basecalling time, and read quality per the ONT Guppy protocol (vGPB_2003_v1_revAX_14Dec2018) (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 11). Due to ReadBouncer’s high temporary memory demands exceeding available RAM, ReadFish was used for all subsequent adaptive sequencing experiments.

Table 3.1 GPU optimization tests performed with increasing Guppy parameters to examine GPU demands during adaptive sequencing.

GPU test	Configuration file	Chunk size	Number of callers	Runners per device
Test 1	even_faster	1000	4	8
Test 2	fast	1000	4	8
Test 3	fast	1000	8	16
Test 4	fast	1000	8	64
Test 5	fast	2000	4	8
Test 6	hac	1000	8	16

3.2.5 Host removal experiments with ReadFish

Optimization of ReadFish for human sequence depletion was conducted using the first final library prepared in [Subsection 3.2.3](#), employing default settings to unblock (i.e., reject) reads matching the human reference from [Subsection 3.2.2](#) and to continue sequencing reads lacking one or more hits (Payne *et al.*, 2021) (Figure 3.1). To evaluate the impact of reference genome size and completeness, a combined index of GRCh38.p14 and T2T-CHM13v2.0 was created and used as the depletion target (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 12); however, a maximum size threshold for ReadFish Minimap2 indices was identified, limiting further host depletion runs to the GRCh38.p14 genome. The resulting optimal parameters and reference genome were then applied to all subsequent sequencing runs using final libraries from [Subsection 3.2.3](#), which included both skin microbiome samples and human mock communities (Appendix 2: Section 1).

3.2.6 Adaptive sequencing analysis workflow

All ONT FAST5 files were basecalled and demultiplexed using Guppy's high-accuracy model v6.0.6 (Wick *et al.*, 2019) on a local bioinformatics workstation, and the resulting outputs processed on an HPC cluster through the Adaptive Sequencing Analysis Workflow (ASAW) (Figure 3.2). ASAW, a Snakemake-based pipeline v7.32.4 built using the Snakemake GitHub template (Snakemake-workflows, 2024), was developed to compare control and experimental runs of adaptively sequenced human metagenomic microbiome samples using ReadFish. The environment was managed with Conda (Python v3.10.8), and inputs included unblocked read ID lists, Guppy-generated fastq and sequence summary files, and a metadata file detailing all samples and runs (Table 1.5). Workflow configuration-controlled parameters, input specifications, and user options including assembly steps, control inclusion, and standard analyses. Each sample was fully analysed to assess software performance, track rejected reads, and compare adaptive versus control runs. Development and execution of ASAW required high-performance computing and was carried out on the University of Hull's Viper HPC system with technical support. A full description of ASAW functionality and outputs is provided in Appendix 13 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752062) and the [GitHub user guide](#).

Figure 3.2 Bioinformatics processing post Nanopore sequencing for adaptive sequencing analysis, divided into two stages: Input data processing performed locally on a bioinformatics workstation, and ASAW execution conducted on an HPC cluster, as indicated by the grey dashed boundary. (Appendix 13)

3.2.7 Full microbiome sample analysis

Using ASAW on an HPC cluster (Figure 3.2), standard metagenomic microbiome analysis began with quality control using fastp v0.23.4 (Chen *et al.*, 2018), followed by optional contig assembly with Flye v2.9.5 (Kolmogorov *et al.*, 2020). Optional host filtering was performed using Minimap2 v2.28 (Li, 2021) and SAMtools v1.16.1 (Li *et al.*, 2009) to remove sequences mapping to the GRCh38.p14 human reference (Table 1.5). Taxonomic assignment was conducted with Kraken2 v2.1.3 using its standard database, which includes reference genomes for human, viral, archaeal, and bacterial domains (Wood *et al.*, 2019; O’Leary *et al.*, 2016).

Taxonomy outputs were automatically integrated into ASAW's downstream modules for community analyses, including alpha and beta diversity metrics (Table 1.4), implemented through bash and R scripts v4.2.2 (Appendix 5; Appendix 13). Sequence statistics were compiled throughout with Seqtk v1.4 (Li, 2024).

3.2.8 Rejected read separation and analysis

ASAW also incorporated a dedicated module for handling rejected reads, those mapped by ReadFish to the human genome during adaptive sequencing using the read ID list generated during sequencing (Figure 3.2). For ONT in-house adaptive runs, a custom bash script was executed using Snakemake on an HPC cluster to extract rejected read IDs from the nanopore adaptive sampling report. After preprocessing with fastp v0.23.4 (Chen *et al.*, 2018), rejected read datasets were passed through ASAW's analysis steps, which included summarizing sequence statistics from Guppy outputs and tracking rejected read locations post-demultiplexing, which assigns reads to samples based on barcoded adapters. Taxonomic classification of rejected reads was performed using Kraken2 v2.1.3 with its standard database (Wood *et al.*, 2019). Sequence statistics across rejected and retained datasets were compiled using Seqtk v1.4 (Li, 2024) (Table 1.4; Table 1.5), ensuring consistent comparison across adaptive and control runs.

3.2.9 Control and adaptive run comparison

Finally, ASAW incorporated modules to directly compare control and adaptive sequencing runs (Figure 3.2). Sequence and barcode statistics from Guppy outputs were summarized with bash scripts, while Kraken2 taxonomy assignments were analysed with R scripts to quantify differences in taxonomic abundance and diversity metrics (Table 1.4) using Snakemake on an HPC cluster. Alpha diversity (species richness and evenness) was evaluated with the Shannon index, one of the most widely used metrics in ecological and microbiome research (Jost, 2007; Kers and Saccenti, 2022; Walters and Martiny, 2020). Beta diversity (inter-sample variation) was assessed using the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity metric, a common ecological index that measures inter-sample variation based on shared species abundances (Table 1.4) (Whittaker, 1972; Jost, 2007; Kers and Saccenti, 2022; Walters and Martiny, 2020). Embedding these comparative analyses directly within ASAW ensured all outputs were reproducible, standardized, and directly linked to the workflow framework (Lloréns-Rico *et al.*, 2021) presented in Figure 3.2 and described Appendix 13 . [GitHub user guide](#).

3.2.10 Reproducibility and data availability

To promote transparency and facilitate reproducibility, all detailed protocols, scripts, and instructions for all wet and dry lab procedures described are available in Appendices 1-13 and archived in Zenodo repositories. Full description of all consumables, equipment, and kits used for wet lab methods are available on protocols.io (DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1), as described in Appendix 1. Whenever feasible, all raw sequencing data produced and bioinformatic processes have been developed in reproducible workflows and/or scripts and archived (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendices 6-13). This includes ASAW, which is fully documented and archived alongside these materials to ensure reproducibility of all analyses on GitHub (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752062; Appendix 13). All analysis results and scripts to create figures for optimization and experimental runs and the corresponding figure scripts can be found in Appendix 5: Section 2 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007).

3.3 Results

All results in this study were generated through the Adaptive Sequencing Analysis Workflow (ASAW), a modular Snakemake pipeline constructed for this study to evaluate adaptive sequencing performance on microbiome samples (Figure 3.2). The workflow processed ONT data end-to-end, including rejected read tracking, taxonomic assignment, and downstream analysis, ensuring consistent handling across experimental and control runs. This enabled direct comparison of host depletion efficiency, community composition, and sequencing metrics, while also capturing detailed statistics on rejected reads. By providing a reproducible framework for these analyses, ASAW underpinned the findings reported below and highlighted the feasibility of adaptive sequencing for skin microbiome research.

3.3.1 Adaptive sequencing optimized with ReadFish and GPU tuning

To optimize adaptive sequencing for human DNA depletion from skin microbiome samples on a desktop computer, sequencing runs were conducted on forearm swabs using various basecalling parameters based on Guppy v6.0.6 protocol recommendations (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, UK; Appendix 11). Initial tests included ReadBouncer, ONT's in-house adaptive sequencing, and ReadFish, all using the same final library, identical parameters, and reference for human sequence depletion. ReadBouncer was excluded from further analysis, as all test runs exceeded the available memory of the bioinformatics workstation described in [Subsection 3.2.2](#), preventing successful execution. ONT's in-house software offered limited flexibility, with parameter settings too rigid for effective optimization. Although both ReadFish and ONT software reduced human reads by over 40% on average, ReadFish consistently yielded a greater reduction (Figure 3.3A). Consequently, ReadFish was selected for all subsequent adaptive sequencing experiments.

Additional optimization runs (Tests 1–6) evaluated the impact of increasing graphics processing unit (GPU) demands during adaptive sequencing, as measured by GPU wattage draw from the Guppy basecalling server. Parameters adjusted included data transfer size, number of GPU threads, estimated median read accuracy, and the number of parallel basecallers (Table 3.1; Appendix 11). Basecalling time increased minimally with higher GPU power until high read accuracy was applied in Test 6 (Figure 3.3B). Among lower-accuracy settings, Test 1 used the least power, completed fastest (Figure 3.3B), and yielded the lowest average read quality (Figure 3.3C).

Figure 3.3 Summary of ReadFish and ONT in-house adaptive sequencing software for optimization runs. (A) Comparison of the number of human reads in control and adaptive sequencing runs using ONT in-house and ReadFish software. (B) Time in seconds it took to complete basecalling and the amount of power (W) from the GPU for Guppy in test runs 1-6. (C) The average read quality score after basecalling for GPU optimization runs with a diamond marking the median quality score for each. (Appendix 5: Section 2)

Test 2 showed minimal increase in basecalling time relative to power usage and achieved improved read quality. Test 3 showed a higher power-to-time ratio without substantial gains, and subsequent tests showed little change until Test 6, which significantly increased both time and quality. Thus, increasing GPU power beyond a threshold did not substantially improve basecalling speed or read quality. Test 2 provided the optimal balance of power consumption, processing time, and read quality (Table 3.1) and was selected for all subsequent ReadFish adaptive sequencing runs (Appendix 11).

3.3.2 Host DNA halved with improved microbial evenness and diversity

Skin microbiome samples from forearm swabs and mock communities diluted with human DNA were adaptively sequenced using the optimal Guppy settings (Table 3.1; Appendix 11) and ReadFish was configured to unblock, or remove, any sequences mapping to the human reference genome. The most pronounced effect of host depletion was a consistent reduction in the proportion of human sequences, which decreased by over 50% on average across all

adaptively sequenced samples. This reduction was observed regardless of the initial human DNA content or sample type, including diluted mock communities, left forearm skin, and right forearm skin samples (Figure 3.4A).

The overall bacterial community composition in skin samples remained largely unchanged following human depletion, though evenness improved (Figure 3.4B). Species-level trends showed some influence from ReadFish, such as *Cutibacterium acnes* decreasing in relative abundance across skin samples where it previously comprised the majority of bacterial sequences. Similarly, samples containing *Acinetobacter* species exhibited a relative decline in reads from this genus after adaptive sequencing (Figure 3.4B).

Figure 3.4 Taxonomy results and changes in microbial communities across skin samples in control and adaptive sequencing runs to remove host contamination. (A) Average percentage of reads belonging to *Homo sapiens* across all left forearm, right forearm, and mock community samples from control and adaptive sequencing runs. (B) Taxonomy assignments for the fifteen most abundant species in skin samples from the control and human depletion runs. (Appendix 5: Section 2)

Alpha and beta diversity metrics were assessed for all samples from control and ReadFish host depletion runs. Within-sample diversity (alpha diversity), measured using the Shannon index, varied between control and adaptive sequencing runs and generally increased across all sample types following host depletion (Figure 3.5A). The largest increases were observed in skin microbiome samples compared to mock communities diluted with human DNA

([Subsection 1.9.1](#)). Notably, samples with higher initial host contamination and greater baseline diversity, such as those from the left and right forearms, exhibited a greater average increase in diversity after adaptive sequencing (Figure 3.5A).

Between-sample diversity (beta diversity) was more strongly influenced by sample type than by the application of adaptive sequencing. In skin microbiome samples, host depletion led to more consistent species diversity, reducing variation between samples of the same type. In contrast, mock community samples showed a slight increase in diversity variation between samples when adaptive sequencing was applied (Figure 3.5B).

Figure 3.5 Alpha and beta diversity results in microbial communities across skin and mock community samples in control and adaptive sequencing runs to remove host contamination. (A) Shannon scores across all left forearm, right forearm, and mock community samples from control and adaptive sequencing runs. (B) PCA plot of community dissimilarities of adaptive versus control mock community and forearm skin microbiome samples calculated with Bray-Curtis dissimilarity. (Appendix 5: Section 2)

3.3.3 Rejected reads largely human with minimal impact on analyses

Sequences mapped to the human genome by ReadFish (i.e., rejected reads) were evaluated for taxonomy, demultiplexing outcome, and read statistics following high accuracy basecalling and demultiplexing with Guppy. Although these reads were rejected for mapping to the human reference during adaptive sequencing, post-quality control and taxonomic

assignment showed that only 66.8% were classified as human. Few rejected reads remained in final sample analyses, and most of those belonged to *C. acnes* or human, although various other taxa were also marked for rejection (Figure 3.6A).

Demultiplexing outcomes revealed that ~2% of rejected reads appeared in final analyses. Of all rejected reads, ~85% were unclassified, and ~13% failed Guppy's initial quality check, approximately half the failure rate observed among reads not unblocked by ReadFish. Reads not mapped to the human reference genome during adaptive sequencing (i.e., not unblocked) showed a similar distribution, with roughly one-third each unclassified, assigned to samples, or failing quality control (Figure 3.6B).

Read statistics were generally consistent between reads rejected and not rejected by ReadFish during adaptive sequencing for host depletion. Metrics such as average read quality, read length, and front and rear barcode lengths showed minimal variation. Front barcode quality scores were similarly stable across read types, with the lowest average scores observed in reads that failed Guppy's quality check, and higher scores in both classified and unclassified reads regardless of rejection status. Rejected unclassified reads had front barcode quality scores comparable to those not marked for rejection; however, non-rejected unclassified reads exhibited a slight reduction in average front barcode quality and a lower proportion of high-quality barcodes (Figure 3.6C).

In contrast, rear barcode quality scores were consistently lower for reads rejected by ReadFish, regardless of classification or quality status. Among reads not marked for depletion, rear barcode quality varied: the lowest scores were observed in unclassified reads and those that failed the Guppy quality check, while classified reads not rejected by ReadFish showed the highest average rear barcode quality (Figure 3.6D).

Figure 3.6 Outcome of reads marked for rejection by ReadFish across all adaptive sequencing runs to deplete human sequences. (A) Taxonomy assignment of all reads rejected by ReadFish that were unclassified and found in skin samples. (B) Comparison of the average percentage of reads that failed initial barcoding quality control, were barcoded into samples, and were unclassified after demultiplexing for reads not marked for rejection by ReadFish compared to those that were. (C) Quality of front sequence barcodes from reads not marked for rejection by ReadFish compared to those that were and failed initial barcoding quality control, were barcoded into samples, or were unclassified after demultiplexing. (D) Quality of rear sequence barcodes from reads not marked for rejection by ReadFish compared to those that were and failed initial barcoding quality control, were barcoded into samples, or were unclassified after demultiplexing. (Appendix 5: Section 2)

3.3.4 Sequencing performance remains robust despite modest metric shifts

The overall condition of sequencing reads changed slightly following the application of ReadFish for depletion of sequences mapping to the human genome. Notably, adaptive sequencing runs had a higher proportion of unclassified reads, those not assigned to any sample, and a significantly lower percentage of reads assigned after demultiplexing; however, the proportion of reads that were too low quality to be basecalled or demultiplexed remained similar between control and adaptive runs (Figure 3.7A). Adaptive sequencing also impacted average read quality: after quality control with ASAW, reads that were successfully basecalled, demultiplexed, and assigned to samples exhibited lower average quality in adaptive runs compared to controls (Figure 3.7B).

Read length was similarly affected. Classified reads from control runs averaged ~2500 bp in length (Figure 3.7C) and included a higher number of sequences ≥ 5000 bp than adaptive runs (Figure 3.7D). In control runs, failed and unclassified reads had average lengths similar to classified reads (~2500 bp) but also showed a notable spike in read counts at ~200 bp (Figure 3.7C). In contrast, failed and unclassified reads from adaptive sequencing runs averaged ~1500 bp, while classified reads maintained the ~2500 bp average. Additionally, the spike in read counts for failed and unclassified adaptive reads occurred at 400–500 bp and was substantially higher than in control runs (Figure 3.7D).

Figure 3.7 Comparison of sequencing summaries for control and adaptive sequencing runs to remove host contamination. (A) Comparison of the average percentage of reads that failed initial barcoding quality control, were barcoded into samples, and were unclassified after demultiplexing in control and adaptive sequencing runs. (B) Average read quality across all samples from adaptive sequencing and control runs. (C) Lengths of all reads from control runs that failed initial barcoding quality control, were barcoded into samples, or were unclassified after demultiplexing. (D) Lengths of all reads from adaptive sequencing runs that failed initial barcoding quality control, were barcoded into samples, or were unclassified after demultiplexing. (Appendix 5: Section 2)

3.4 Discussion

The skin microbiome plays a central role in health yet remains underrepresented in research compared to other body sites due to its complexity, high inter-individual variability, and strong influence from host and environmental factors (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Moskovicz *et al.*, 2020; Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023). While long-read sequencing has improved resolution, it also generates vast data volumes dominated by host DNA, creating analytical bottlenecks and undermining reproducibility (Kong *et al.*, 2017; Goodman, 2001). Addressing these barriers requires new approaches and practical workflows designed for host depletion in skin microbiome studies.

Adaptive sequencing offers one promising solution by selectively rejecting human DNA in real time, reducing sequencing burden and redirecting resources toward microbial reads (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Early studies have focused on respiratory, gut, or reproductive samples but none have applied this strategy to skin microbiomes, used the compact Flongle device, or systematically evaluated feasibility on standard desktop hardware (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Gan *et al.*, 2021; Hewel *et al.*, 2024). Moreover, the absence of dedicated workflows for adaptive sequencing data has limited uptake and reproducibility in human microbiome research (Martin *et al.*, 2022).

This study introduced the Adaptive Sequencing Analysis Workflow (ASAW), a modular Snakemake pipeline specifically designed to process, evaluate, and compare adaptive sequencing runs. ASAW was essential for generating all results, enabling integrated analyses of host depletion, rejected reads, and microbiome composition across paired experimental and control runs (Figure 3.2). Forearm skin microbiome samples and mock communities were sequenced using ReadFish under optimized software conditions, with analyses tailored to test feasibility on standard workstations. The workflow halved host contamination while preserving overall microbial community structure, increasing diversity metrics, and improving recovery of skin-associated taxa. Importantly, ASAW not only allowed systematically evaluated software configurations but also provided a reusable and transparent framework for future adaptive sequencing studies. Together, these results demonstrate both the feasibility and practical utility of adaptive sequencing for human DNA depletion in skin microbiome research, while showcasing ASAW as a generalizable tool for reproducible analysis.

3.4.1 Optimised basecalling time and read quality

Currently, no detailed guidelines exist regarding computational requirements, such as GPU, CPU, or hardware configurations, for running adaptive sequencing software on a desktop computer. This gap is particularly critical in the context of Guppy, which is the most

computationally intensive component of adaptive sequencing and whose rapid decision-making depends on fast basecalling (Wick *et al.*, 2019; Ulrich *et al.*, 2022). Predicting optimal GPU parameters is inherently challenging due to factors such as inefficient memory access and highly variable, non-uniform read lengths (Gamaarachchi *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, the recommended strategy, as implemented here, is to conduct iterative tests while adjusting Guppy parameters to optimize throughput, minimize runtime, maximize read quality, and balance GPU usage without over- or underutilization (Weilguny *et al.*, 2023; Gamaarachchi *et al.*, 2020; Benton, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2021).

Among studies that report GPU parameters, few depart from default configurations, and those that do typically focus on different software than used here (Lemon *et al.*, 2017; Weilguny *et al.*, 2023; Gamaarachchi *et al.*, 2020) or make only minor changes, often limited to a single parameter (Payne *et al.*, 2021). One frequently adjusted parameter is Guppy's predicted read accuracy, which significantly impacts basecalling performance. A median predicted accuracy above 90% is considered high (Wick *et al.*, 2019; Perešini *et al.*, 2021) and is generally reserved for high-performance computing systems (Nakamura *et al.*, 2024; Ewels, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2024; Vries *et al.*, 2022); however, this setting is impractical for most ONT devices and desktop workstations, requiring approximately 5–8 times longer processing time (Wick *et al.*, 2019). More commonly, fast configurations, with predicted read accuracies ranging from 78–85% or 85–92%, are employed (Wick *et al.*, 2019; Perešini *et al.*, 2021; Munro *et al.*, 2023; Lin *et al.*, 2022; Yuen *et al.*, 2024; Grimes *et al.*, 2022). As depicted in Figure 3.3, optimization runs conducted on the desktop system in this study followed the same pattern: low settings yielded insufficient read quality, while high-accuracy configurations were prohibitively slow, confirming the critical trade-off between speed and quality in Guppy basecalling.

Additional parameters had minimal impact; therefore, the settings from Test 2 (Table 3.1; Appendix 11), which demonstrated the optimal balance of GPU power consumption, runtime, and read quality (Figure 3.3), were adopted for sequencing runs using ReadFish. While testing and optimization were attempted for other adaptive sequencing software, full sequencing runs could only be completed with ReadFish and ONT's in-house software. Although the experiments conducted were not intended as a benchmark comparison between different adaptive sequencing tools, the workflows and outcomes of these two approaches were evaluated. As reported in previous studies, ONT's in-house MinKNOW software is user-friendly for simple samples but offers limited configurability, which constrains its application to more complex microbiome datasets (Ulrich *et al.*, 2024; Payne *et al.*, 2021). The sequencing runs using ONT's in-house software applied the same adaptive sequencing parameters and human

reference genome as the ReadFish runs, with both also sharing the optimized GPU configuration from Test 2 (Table 3.1).

On average, both methods achieved over a 40% reduction in human sequences; however, as shown in Figure 3.3A, samples processed with ReadFish exhibited approximately half the number of human reads compared to those sequenced with the in-house software. These optimizations not only improved computational efficiency but also enhanced microbial sequence recovery by effectively minimizing host contamination. By reducing runtime and optimizing GPU utilization, the workflow supported the routine implementation of adaptive sequencing for complex microbiome samples. The capacity to adjust key parameters, such as predicted read accuracy and sequencing speed, enabled a customized approach to address the unique challenges of microbiome sequencing, including data quality and computational load. As a result, this strategy offers a scalable and reproducible framework that facilitates the broader application of adaptive sequencing in microbiome research and improves the reliability of microbial community analyses.

3.4.2 Improved microbial diversity and evenness

Host depletion using ReadFish was successful across all skin microbiome samples examined in this study, yielding an average reduction of over 50% in human sequences and a consistent increase in microbial diversity and evenness, as illustrated in Figures 3.4 and 3.5. These effects were observed regardless of the initial level of human DNA or sample type. While comparable studies have reported similar outcomes, the use of adaptive sequencing in human microbiome research remains limited. Marquet *et al.* (2022), for example, applied ReadFish in combination with enzymatic host depletion to vaginal microbiome samples and observed a reduction in human reads from 87% to approximately 35%. Similar findings were reported by Gan *et al.* (2021) and Cheng *et al.* (2022) in respiratory infection samples, where human DNA was reduced by 35–40% using enzymatic and in-house adaptive sequencing methods. To date, the only other human microbiome study employing adaptive sequencing targeted eukaryotic viruses, achieving enrichment of monkeypox virus despite the presence of >99.5% human DNA (Hewel *et al.*, 2024).

Some minor community shifts were also detected. For example, a slight but consistent decrease in the relative abundance of *C. acnes* and certain *Acinetobacter* species was observed in skin samples, although no evidence of systematic bias was introduced (Figure 3.4B). Marquet *et al.* (2022) similarly noted changes in *Escherichia* and *Luteimonas* genera and attributed these shifts to experimental variation. Potential causes for the taxonomic changes seen here may include such variation, human-microbe co-evolution, contamination within reference genomes,

or GC content-related mapping bias. For instance, the GRCh38 human reference genome has a GC content of 41% (O'Leary *et al.*, 2016), while *Acinetobacter* species range from 39–47% GC and possess high genomic plasticity (Salto *et al.*, 2018; Muzahid *et al.*, 2023). Because GC content influences fragment mapping density, it can confound interpretation by introducing artificial peaks (Benjamini and Speed, 2012); however, *C. acnes* has a GC content of approximately 60% (Beig *et al.*, 2024), making GC bias an unlikely explanation for its observed decline.

Host depletion continues to demonstrate clear benefits even when complete removal of human sequences is not achievable, with approximately 25% of human reads typically remaining unrejected (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Marquet *et al.*, 2022), and consistently improves the recovery of microbial community information. Across published studies, adaptive sequencing has been shown to enhance taxonomic classification sensitivity, increase microbial read yield, and improve community diversity relative to control runs (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Gan *et al.*, 2021; Cheng *et al.*, 2022). This study observed analogous improvements with microbial diversity significantly increasing in all samples following host depletion (Figure 3.5A). Samples with initially higher levels of human DNA showed the greatest gains in microbial diversity, a trend consistent with prior findings (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Gan *et al.*, 2021). Notably, as in comparable studies, the overall microbial community composition remained stable following adaptive sequencing, with no loss of low-abundance taxa and generally improved taxonomic evenness (Figure 3.4) (Marquet *et al.*, 2022).

3.4.3 Rejected reads were human and unassigned

Despite the majority of reads rejected by ReadFish being correctly identified as host and removed, not all rejected reads were of human origin. The remaining taxonomic assignments illustrated in Figure 3.6A included a similar variety of bacterial species found in non-rejected reads. Notably, the *Acinetobacter* genus did not show an increased proportion of rejected reads relative to other taxa, suggesting that its inconsistent abundance changes are likely due to factors beyond adaptive sequencing. In contrast, most rejected bacterial reads belonged to *C. acnes* (Figure 3.6A), indicating that it was consistently mapped to the human reference genome during sequencing and improperly depleted, as evidenced by its underrepresentation in final community profiles (Figure 3.4). The precise cause of this misclassification is unclear, potentially stemming from basecalling errors, mapping inaccuracies, or reference genome limitations (Payne *et al.*, 2021).

Overall, host depletion accuracy appeared to depend heavily on read length. As shown in Figure 3.7, the proportion of human reads among those rejected increased to 99% for reads longer than 5000 bp, and human reads that were correctly unblocked were on average longer

than those allowed to complete sequencing (Gan *et al.*, 2021; Marquet *et al.*, 2022). In contrast, read quality likely had minimal influence on rejection accuracy. Rejected reads were more likely to pass Guppy's initial quality check than non-rejected reads, and most reads unblocked by ReadFish were ultimately unclassified, i.e., not assigned to any sample. Approximately 2% of rejected reads passed quality control and were included in final sample analyses (Figure 3.6B). Although software developers acknowledge that adaptive sequencing is not 100% accurate (Payne *et al.*, 2021), the frequency with which unblocked reads are too low quality, unclassifiable, or retained in analyses remains largely unaddressed in the literature. While read length influences unblocking decisions (Marquet *et al.*, 2022), no significant differences in length were observed between rejected and non-rejected reads from adaptive sequencing runs in this study.

The only consistent difference in read statistics was in rear barcode quality. Reads not marked for depletion had expected barcode quality values and resembled control run reads. Similarly, rejected reads exhibited typical front barcode quality; however, as depicted in Figure 3.6C and 3.6D, rear barcode quality in reads unblocked by ReadFish was consistently and significantly lower across all outcomes. This issue has not been discussed in prior developer or research literature, though one study reported variable pore selection and uneven read degradation during sequencing (Danilevsky *et al.*, 2022).

This reduction in rear barcode quality may indicate that, rather than immediately terminating sequencing, Nanopore's ReadUntil functionality tapers sequencing when a read is unblocked. This could allow the read to pass through at reduced quality after rejection. Although the effect on pore health and data output remains unclear, the consequence is that unblocked reads are not discarded but retained as unclassified. While these reads are not typically analysed post-demultiplexing, they remain in the raw data. Prior studies have noted that reads intended for removal can sometimes be retrieved (Nakamura *et al.*, 2024), though their origin remains uncertain. This may, however, offer an advantage in microbiome studies. For example, researchers studying fragile communities or low-abundance taxa could investigate unclassified reads after demultiplexing to recover high-quality, rejected reads that are assignable to samples.

3.4.4 Decreased sequence quality and lengths

While rejected sequences were largely removed from the final sample analysis, they still influenced the overall distribution of read outcomes when comparing adaptive sequencing to control runs (Figures 3.7A and 3.7B). The proportion of unclassified reads nearly doubled in adaptive sequencing runs, and the percentage of reads ultimately assigned to samples after demultiplexing was significantly lower than in controls; however, the percentage of reads too

low in quality to be basecalled or demultiplexed was nearly identical between the two conditions (Figure 3.7A). Although few studies report the outcomes for all reads, it has been noted that host depletion typically results in more rejected than accepted reads (Gan *et al.*, 2021; Marquet *et al.*, 2022). Consequently, adaptive sequencing affected the final analysed reads by contributing to a general decline in read quality.

Given that only 2% of rejected reads remained in final analyses, it is unlikely that their inclusion significantly impacted overall read quality. The observed drop in quality may instead reflect experimental variation, the adaptive sequencing process itself, or the condition of the sequencing pores, particularly as Flongle flow cells were the primary variable differentiating control and adaptive runs. The average read length for classified reads was similar between conditions, although control runs produced more reads over 5000 bp (Figure 3.7), lengths optimal for mapping to the human reference genome (Marquet *et al.*, 2022). Previous host depletion studies in human microbiome research reported shorter average read lengths, around 2100 bp, with adaptive sequencing runs yielding even shorter reads than controls (Gan *et al.*, 2021; Cheng *et al.*, 2022).

The most substantial shift in read length occurred in the unclassified reads, which showed a marked increase in the number of reads around 400 bp (Figure 3.7D). This suggests rapid unblock decisions and reflects adequate power supplied to the adaptive sequencing software. A length spike in the 400–800 bp range is typical of adaptive sequencing, irrespective of the software used (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Payne *et al.*, 2021). At the optimal speed of under 500 bp, unblock decisions are made within approximately two seconds after a DNA molecule enters the pore (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022), and ReadFish has demonstrated the capability to correctly map 90% of reads at an average speed of 360 bp. While this response time is relatively fast with current technology, the sequencing and computational resources expended on these short, unwanted reads remain a limitation, diverting efforts away from target microbial sequences (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Ulrich *et al.*, 2022).

3.4.5 Limitations and future research directions

The limitations of response time and dependence on read length appear consistently across adaptive sequencing, regardless of software, settings, or approach, highlighting areas for improvement in this relatively novel technique (Martin *et al.*, 2022; Hewel *et al.*, 2024). For instance, the use of Minimap2 for alignment has been identified as a constraint in both ReadFish and ONT in-house software due to its computational demands, slower speed, and limited mapping accuracy for human genome alignment (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Marquet *et al.*, 2022). Alternative tools, such as ReadBouncer, are developing faster methods based on k-mer

classification with pre-indexed databases (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022); however, these approaches present their own practical limitations concerning excessive CPU usage, as described in [Subsection 3.2.4](#). Additionally, ONT's ReadUntil capability may contribute to increased pore blockage during adaptive sequencing, potentially impacting read quality (Hewel *et al.*, 2024; Cheng *et al.*, 2022).

Any reference-based depletion strategy depends on high-quality, organism-specific assemblies, which remains a limiting factor (Hewel *et al.*, 2024; Ulrich *et al.*, 2022). Most current references were developed for human genetics rather than microbial applications, reducing their suitability for host depletion in metagenomic contexts (Quince *et al.*, 2017). GRCh38 is still the most widely used human reference due to computational efficiency, but its mosaic structure and potential microbial sequence inclusion, through assembly errors or co-evolution, introduce risks of misclassification and microbial read loss (Schneider *et al.*, 2017; Yang *et al.*, 2015). The recently released T2T-CHM13 assembly provides the first complete, gapless human genome, including telomeres and centromeres (Nurk *et al.*, 2022; Miga and Wang, 2021); however, its size and computational burden make it impractical for real-time adaptive sequencing, which requires rapid mapping (Nurk *et al.*, 2022). These challenges are especially acute in conserved or repetitive regions where human and microbial sequences overlap, and in fragmented genomes or low-abundance taxa (Nearing *et al.*, 2021). Such factors may explain cases like the apparent misidentification of *C. acnes* during host depletion in this study, although without comparative analyses the cause remains uncertain.

Future directions in adaptive sequencing will depend on algorithmic innovation and improved reference resources. Lightweight computational strategies based on k-mer matching, hashing, and other rapid classification methods are likely to reduce response time and power requirements, ultimately making depletion faster and more scalable. Parallel efforts to build more representative reference resources, including human pangenomes that capture genomic diversity across populations (Eizenga *et al.*, 2020), will improve the accuracy and reliability of host depletion. Together, these developments will enhance the feasibility of adaptive sequencing for microbiome research and its broader adoption in clinical and ecological applications (Miga and Wang, 2021; Yang *et al.*, 2015).

Researchers are also exploring combined enzymatic and adaptive sequencing strategies for human DNA removal, which may increase sensitivity in clinical metagenomics (Gan *et al.*, 2021; Marquet *et al.*, 2022). Yet, this approach risks reintroducing biases inherent to DNA extraction-based depletion methods (Nearing *et al.*, 2021). Future progress will depend on broader investigations across diverse cohorts and body sites, alongside the development of specialized laboratory protocols, refined bioinformatic pipelines, and improved software

configurations (Vollmers *et al.*, 2017). The most promising advances are likely to come from algorithmic innovation, particularly faster, more efficient mapping methods such as k-mer or hash-based strategies, that could overcome current computational bottlenecks and make adaptive sequencing broadly accessible. With these improvements, adaptive sequencing has the potential to become a routine, bias-minimized tool for high-resolution and reproducible microbiome analysis.

Microbial enrichment offers another route to reducing host contamination in skin microbiome studies, though it can alter community composition and limit depletion efficiency (Marquet *et al.*, 2022). A more powerful direction lies in integrating host depletion with targeted enrichment, using adaptive sequencing to recover clinically relevant features such as pathogens, antimicrobial resistance genes, and virulence factors (Cheng *et al.*, 2022; Gan *et al.*, 2021). Developing strategies that combine both functions could overcome current limitations, aligning adaptive sequencing more closely with clinical diagnostic needs while also supporting broader applications in environmental microbiology, public health surveillance, microbial ecology, and real-time monitoring of complex microbial communities (Cheng *et al.*, 2022; Payne *et al.*, 2021).

3.5 Conclusion

Host contamination poses a persistent barrier in skin microbiome research, reducing microbial resolution and reproducibility. This study addressed the challenge by developing ASAW and applying it to evaluate and optimize adaptive sequencing tools for host depletion. ReadFish emerged as the most effective approach, consistently achieving ~50% reduction in human DNA while preserving microbial community structure and enhancing both diversity and evenness across all sample types. Importantly, the workflow ensured transparent, reproducible analyses and demonstrated feasibility on a standard workstation, lowering the barrier to routine implementation. While some rejected reads were not fully excluded, the overall results highlight adaptive sequencing as a practical, scalable strategy. By directly improving host depletion in skin samples, this work advances microbiome profiling and supports broader applications in clinical research, public health, and microbial ecology, alongside the development of medical interventions that enhance quality of life and save lives.

Chapter 4 Adaptive detection of clinically relevant pathogens and ARGs in metagenomic sequencing

4.1 Introduction

Chronic skin wounds affect over 20 million people globally and cost an estimated \$31 billion USD annually, presenting a major healthcare burden (Li *et al.*, 2021; Sen, 2021). These wounds reduce quality of life and elevate infection risk, often involving complex microbial communities that influence healing outcomes (Spanos *et al.*, 2017; Canchy *et al.*, 2023). Accurate detection of key pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) is therefore critical. Although culture-based tools are routinely used to identify microbes in skin and wound environments, these traditional approaches face important limitations in profiling resistance and taxonomic resolution (Chiu and Miller, 2019; Tomic-Canic *et al.*, 2020). While metagenomic sequencing offers broad insights into microbiome composition, its utility in skin samples is limited by high levels of host DNA, which reduce microbial read depth and diagnostic efficiency (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Charalampous *et al.*, 2019). Adaptive sequencing, a method that selectively retains or rejects DNA molecules in real time, has the potential to overcome these challenges by enriching for target species and ARGs while depleting human DNA (Payne *et al.*, 2021).

4.1.1 Antimicrobial resistance

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a critical challenge in both global health and wound management, where it contributes to wound chronicity and complicates treatment strategies. Addressing AMR requires not only identifying resistant pathogens but also understanding the underlying resistance mechanisms at the genetic level (George *et al.*, 2022). At the core of AMR surveillance is the detection of ARGs, which provide insight into resistance potential and enable more precise strain-level differentiation (Nayak *et al.*, 2023). Sequencing-based methods are essential for this purpose, as non-sequencing approaches, including many traditional diagnostics, lack the resolution needed to accurately characterise ARG presence or diversity (Liu *et al.*, 2020).

Among non-sequencing approaches, culture-based diagnostics stand out for their limitations, as they often provide only narrow resistance profiles and cannot capture the broader antimicrobial resistance potential (ARP), defined as the abundance of ARGs relative to host-associated microbial taxa (Forslund *et al.*, 2013). Additionally, clinically significant pathogens are frequently defined by their resistance genes, such as *Staphylococcus aureus* carrying *mecA*, which classifies the strain as methicillin-resistant (MRSA) (Wielders *et al.*, 2002). Therefore, comprehensive AMR detection requires a dual focus on both taxonomic identity and

ARG content. Integrating these elements supports a more complete understanding of infection dynamics and informs treatment decisions in complex microbiomes such as chronic wounds.

4.1.2 Traditional diagnostics

In practice, many clinical diagnostics and microbiome assessments continue to rely on culture-based methods, which provide biochemical characterization and limited antimicrobial resistance profiling (Avershina *et al.*, 2022; Hassall *et al.*, 2024); however, these methods fail to capture the broader resistome, the complete repertoire of ARGs within the host-associated microbiome, which is critical for understanding resistance potential and guiding treatment strategies (Forslund *et al.*, 2013; Kim and Cha, 2021). Culture-based approaches are also constrained by long turnaround times, high false-negative rates, and a reliance on culturable organisms, a bias that can lead to incomplete or misleading microbial profiles (Liu *et al.*, 2020; Rhoads *et al.*, 2012; Nayak *et al.*, 2023).

In wound diagnostics specifically, the effectiveness of culture-based approaches is further diminished by media preferences and the often-low abundance of target organisms, resulting in failure to detect up to 95% of wound-associated bacteria (Rhoads *et al.*, 2012; Nayak *et al.*, 2023; Li *et al.*, 2021). These methods also rarely account for non-bacterial organisms such as fungi, which can dominate chronic wound environments, or viruses, which modulate bacterial virulence and biofilm formation (Dowd *et al.*, 2011; Messad *et al.*, 2015). Together, these limitations highlight the need for more comprehensive diagnostic strategies that can accurately and efficiently characterise the diverse microbial communities associated with skin and wound infections.

4.1.3 Molecular methods

Molecular diagnostics offer a culture-independent alternative for characterizing wound microbiomes. Among these, high-throughput sequencing (HTS) enables broad taxonomic and functional profiling, including the detection of novel or unexpected organisms and ARGs (Sprockett *et al.*, 2015; Dowd *et al.*, 2011; Liu *et al.*, 2020). By bypassing the selective pressures of culture, HTS captures a more complete picture of microbial communities, including fungi and viruses that may play key roles in wound pathophysiology (Watts and Hurwitz, 2020; Morsli *et al.*, 2024); however, standard metagenomics has practical limitations in clinical contexts.

Skin samples typically contain high levels of host DNA, often exceeding 90%, which reduces microbial read depth and inflates sequencing costs (Byrd *et al.*, 2018). The resulting data can be difficult to interpret and resource-intensive to process, particularly when rapid identification of key pathogens or ARGs is required (Oh *et al.*, 2014). The difficulty of interpreting sequencing data is further compounded by the need to separate clinically relevant

signals from background microbiota (Burnham *et al.*, 2020). Targeted molecular platforms such as multiplex PCR panels offer faster pathogen detection but are restricted to predefined organisms and limited in taxonomic resolution (Candel *et al.*, 2024).

Among available platforms, the bioMérieux BioFire FilmArray system highlights the trade-offs of multiplex PCR, while effective for common pathogens and ARGs, it may fail to detect divergent strains or rare organisms and typically excludes many non-bacterial taxa (Esteban *et al.*, 2023; Honaker *et al.*, 2016). As sequencing technologies advance, tools that combine the broad scope of metagenomics with improved specificity are increasingly important (Chiu and Miller, 2019). In particular, approaches that can prioritize clinically significant taxa or genes while reducing irrelevant data are needed, motivating the development of adaptive sequencing strategies.

4.1.4 Targeted enrichment

Adaptive sequencing is an emerging approach that enables real-time selection of DNA molecules for sequencing based on user-defined targets, offering a way to enrich for clinically relevant information while reducing sequencing burden (Kong *et al.*, 2017). Using tools such as ReadFish, this method can reject unwanted reads, such as those matching the human genome, and preferentially retain reads aligning to a reference of interest (Payne *et al.*, 2021) (Table 1.5). In the context of wound diagnostics, this capability allows for simultaneous enrichment of pathogenic bacterial species and ARGs, both of which are central to clinical decision-making. By concentrating sequencing effort on these targets, adaptive sequencing has the potential to increase diagnostic sensitivity while reducing background noise and data volume.

Although still relatively new, adaptive sequencing has been applied in a small number of microbiome studies. Most have focused on host DNA depletion (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Ong *et al.*, 2022; Gan *et al.*, 2021; Hewel *et al.*, 2024), while others used bioinformatics workflows to retrospectively identify pathogens and ARGs in enriched datasets (Cheng *et al.*, 2022). A few studies have targeted specific bacterial taxa (Ulrich *et al.*, 2024) or resistance genes (Viehweger *et al.*, 2023). To date, however, adaptive sequencing has not been applied to skin or wound microbiomes, where host contamination is especially high and clinical relevance is immediate. Moreover, no previous work has combined depletion of host DNA with targeted enrichment for both ARGs and pathogens.

This study extends adaptive sequencing beyond host depletion to address a key challenge in clinically relevant microbiome analysis: the simultaneous recovery of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance determinants from host-dominated samples. In line with the overarching aim of this thesis to improve reproducibility and diagnostic capacity, this work

focuses on the development and evaluation of an adaptive sequencing strategy that combines selective host depletion with targeted enrichment of clinically relevant organisms and ARGs. Using both controlled mock communities and complex skin and peri-wound samples, the study aims to assess how adaptive sequencing can be directed to enhance detection of priority targets while preserving broader community context (Figure 4.1). By integrating experimental design with structured bioinformatic workflows, this chapter explores the potential of adaptive sequencing to support more sensitive, targeted, and clinically meaningful metagenomic analysis.

Figure 4.1 Methods process for developing, optimizing, testing, and implementing adaptive detection of clinically relevant pathogens and antibiotic resistance genes.

4.2 Methods and materials

Ethical approval was provided by the Hull Royal Tissue ethics committee (REC: 19/NE/0150) and the Faculty Ethics Committee for the Faculty of Science and Engineering at the University of Hull.

4.2.1 Human sample collection

Swabs of skin microbiome samples were collected from the right and left forearms of a healthy volunteer and extracted using a modified Mu-DNA extraction protocol (Sellers *et al.*, 2021), as described in [Subsection 3.2.1](#) (Appendix 1: Sections 1-3). Swabs of the peri-wound area from chronic antibiotic-resistant wounds, which were previously collected and subjected to DNA extraction using the DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kit (Qiagen 2013-24), were cultured to isolate bacterial strains (Appendix 1: Section 2).

4.2.2 Bacterial and human cell culturing

Two bacterial species, *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, were selected from the molecular diagnostic tool BioFire FilmArray Blood Culture Identification 2 Panel (BCID2), which targets a broad range of clinically relevant gram-positive and gram-negative bacterial species and associated ARGs (Table 4.1; Table 4.2) (Murphy *et al.*, 2020; Senok *et al.*, 2023). These species were selected because both are clinically important pathogens with well-characterised resistance profiles, extensive publicly available reference genomes, and relevance to wound and skin-associated infections. Inclusion of both a gram-positive and gram-negative organism also enabled evaluation of adaptive detection across differing genomic and resistance characteristics (Murphy *et al.*, 2020). The reference control strains *Escherichia coli* (NCTC 13351) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (NCTC 13373) were ordered from the UK Health Security Agency's Culture Collections. ARG selection was guided primarily by the resistance profiles of the reference and clinical isolates, with emphasis placed on ARGs represented within the BioFire BCID2 panel to maintain clinical relevance and enable comparison with established molecular diagnostic targets.

Table 4.1 Table of gram-positive and gram-negative bacterial species on the BCID2 BioFire panel.

Gram-negative bacteria	Gram-positive bacteria
<i>Acinetobacter calcoaceticus-baumannii complex</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>
<i>Bacteroides fragilis</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>
<i>Enterobacter cloacae complex</i>	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
<i>Klebsiella aerogenes</i>	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	<i>Staphylococcus lugdunensis</i>
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae group</i>	<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>
<i>Salmonella spp.</i>	<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>
<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	
<i>Haemophilus influenzae</i>	
<i>Neisseria meningitidis</i>	
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>	

Table 4.2 Table of corresponding antimicrobial resistance genes to the bacterial species on the BCID2 BioFire panel.

Resistance type	Gene
Carbapenemase	<i>IMP</i>
Carbapenemase	<i>KPC</i>
Carbapenemase	OXA-48-like
Carbapenemase	<i>NDM</i>
Carbapenemase	<i>VIM</i>
Colistin resistance	<i>mcr-1</i>
Extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL)	<i>CTX-M</i>
Methicillin resistance	<i>mecA/C</i>
Methicillin resistance	<i>mecA/C</i> and MRSA right-extremity junction (MREJ)
Vancomycin resistance	<i>vanA/B</i>

Previously collected bacterial wound swab isolates from [Subsection 4.2.1](#) were initially assessed using VITEK 2 (Ligozzi *et al.*, 2002) and selected as resistant clinical alternatives to reference strains (Table 4.3), including one *E. coli*, one methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA), and one *S. epidermidis* isolate. All reference strains and clinical isolates were cultured on nutrient agar and processed following protocols detailed in “Sample collection, preparation, and sequencing protocols for developing metagenomic approaches in skin and wound microbiome analysis” (DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1; Appendix 1: Section 2). A human alveolar epithelial cell subculture was grown and passaged according to Thermo Fisher Scientific’s protocol using ATCC primary cells (CCL-185). DNA collection, extraction, and quantification for all cultures were carried out using a modified Mu-DNA extraction protocol (Sellers *et al.*, 2021) as described in Appendix 1, Sections 3–4.

Table 4.3 Selected clinical strain antimicrobial resistance prediction results from VITEK 2 analysis (NT=Not Tested, R=Resistant, I=Intermediate, S=Susceptible, +=Resistance induced, -=No resistance induced).

Resistance	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i> (MRSA)	<i>E. coli</i>
Amikacin	NT	NT	S
Amoxicillin/Clavulanic Acid	NT	NT	R
Ampicillin	NT	NT	R
Aztreonam	NT	NT	S
Benzylpenicillin	R	R	NT
Cefepime	NT	NT	S
Cefoxitin Screen	+	+	NT
Cefotaxime	NT	NT	S
Ceftazidime	NT	NT	S
Cefuroxime	NT	NT	S
Cefuroxime Axetil	NT	NT	S
Chloramphenicol	S	S	NT
Ciprofloxacin	R	R	S
Clindamycin	R	S	NT
Daptomycin	S	S	NT
Ertapenem	NT	NT	S
Fusidic Acid	S	R	NT
Gentamicin	I	S	S
Inducible Clindamycin Resistance	+	-	NT
Linezolid	S	S	NT
Meropenem			S
Mupirocin	NT	R	NT
Oxacillin	R	R	NT
Piperacillin/Tazobactam	NT	NT	I
Rifampicin	S	S	NT
Teicoplanin	I	S	NT
Tetracycline	R	S	NT
Tigecycline	S	S	S
Tobramycin	NT	NT	S
Trimethoprim	R	S	S
Vancomycin	S	S	NT

4.2.3 Microbiome DNA standard

The Oral Microbiome Genomic Mix from ATCC (MSA-1004), a DNA standard of mixed microbial community based on oral microbiome composition (Chung *et al.*, 2020), was used as a standard control to mimic a metagenomic sample as outlined in [Subsection 1.9.1](#). Few of the species present in this sample are listed on the BioFire BCID2 panel (Table 4.1) or typically

found in skin or wound microbiomes. This mock community contains genomic DNA at 1.2×10^8 genome copies/vial ± 1 log from six different bacterial strains all in equivalent amounts of approximately 16.7%, *Schaalia odontolytica* (ATCC 17982D-5), *Prevotella melaninogenica* (ATCC 25845D-5), *Fusobacterium nucleatum* subsp. *nucleatum* (ATCC 25586D-5), *Streptococcus mitis* (ATCC 49456D-5), *Veillonella parvula* (ATCC 17745D-5), and *Haemophilus parainfluenzae* (ATCC 33392D-5) (Chung *et al.*, 2020).

4.2.4 Sample spiking and dilution

Extracted DNA from the bacterial strains described in [Section 4.2.2](#) was compared to the oral microbiome DNA standard, described in [Subsection 4.2.3](#), to ensure similar fragment lengths. DNA from all five bacterial strains and the human cell culture was diluted in elute to match the concentration of the mock community. Each strain of interest was added to the mock community at a 1:6 ratio, matching the relative abundance of other species. This was done for five mock communities, each spiked with *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), clinical *E. coli*, *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373), clinical *S. aureus*, or clinical *S. epidermidis*. Each spiked sample was then serially diluted with pure human DNA to reach ~0%, 10%, 75%, and 90% host DNA content (Appendix 1: Section 5).

A portion of forearm skin microbiome samples had been sequenced prior to this experiment ([Section 3.2](#)), revealing each bacterial species comprised ~0.01% of total DNA per swab. Each strain of interest was further diluted to match this concentration (Appendix 5: Section 2). Skin microbiome samples were divided into four equal parts and spiked with *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), clinical *E. coli*, *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373), or clinical *S. aureus* (Appendix 1: Section 6). Spiking calculations and sample design followed Venkataraman *et al.* (2018) for genomic DNA addition in metagenomic workflow testing.

4.2.5 Software installation and configuration

ReadFish v0.0.2 and its dependencies, including Guppy v6.0.6 (Wick *et al.*, 2019), Minimap2 v2.26 (Li, 2021), and ReadUntil v3.0.0 (Oxford Nanopore Technologies), were installed on a local bioinformatics workstation (AMD Ryzen 5 5600X, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti GPU, Ubuntu v20.04 LTS) via Anaconda (Python v3.7) in a dedicated Conda environment (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 9) and tested following Payne *et al.* (2021) (Table 1.5). Dependency configurations were modified per Payne *et al.*, including reducing MinKNOW v5.2.2 data transfer to 0.4 seconds and accelerating Guppy basecalling decisions. The ReadFish reference index was built using Minimap2 from RefSeq genomes (O'Leary *et al.*, 2016) for human (GRCh38.p14), all BCID2 panel pathogens (Table 4.1), and the full Comprehensive Antibiotic Resistance Database (CARD) homolog database v3.2.7 (Alcock *et al.*, 2023) on a local

bioinformatics workstation (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 6: Sections 1–3). Python scripts generated contig and sequence ID lists from *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, all BCID2 pathogen genome assemblies, and two sets of ARG IDs: one for all CARD entries and one limited to BCID2 ARGs (Appendix 6: Section 4). A custom ReadFish configuration file was created and validated for each sequencing run (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 10: Section 2) per Payne *et al.* (2021).

4.2.6 Library preparation and sequencing

Libraries for each dataset (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007; Appendix 2: Section 2) were constructed from samples prepared in [Subsections 4.2.1-4.2.4](#) according to the ONT Rapid sequencing DNA PCR Barcoding (SQK-RPB004) kit library preparation protocol (Appendix 1: Section 7). Overall, there were ten final libraries constructed, five of the spiked mock communities, four of the spiked forearm skin swabs, and one final library of all four peri-wound samples. Sequencing was performed on a local bioinformatics workstation using the Flongle FLO-FLG001 R9.4.1 flow cell in the MinION Mk1B device (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, UK) and was primed and loaded with the prepared library according to the library preparation protocol. The sequencing procedure was then initiated on MinKNOW v5.2.2 using the parameters as described in [Subsection 3.2.3](#) (Appendix 1: Section 8).

4.2.7 ReadFish initiation and optimization

Approximately 24 hours prior to each adaptive sequencing run, a control run was conducted using the same bioinformatics workstation, final library, MinION device, computer, MinKNOW settings, and Flongle adapter (Appendix 1: Section 8). Adaptive sequencing runs differed by using a fresh Flongle flow cell, launching a Guppy basecalling server, and activating ReadFish upon sequencing initiation (Appendix 1: Section 9). ReadFish optimization for adaptive detection of resistant pathogens was performed on mock community libraries spiked with *E. coli* (NCTC 13351) and varying human DNA levels. Initial enrichment targeted the *E. coli* reference genome and the full CARD homolog database (Alcock *et al.*, 2023), using default settings to unblock non-matching reads and sequence those with at least one match (Payne *et al.*, 2021). To optimize the hit threshold, a parallel experiment retained only reads with multiple matches. Reference specificity was tested by limiting enrichment to ARGs listed in the BCID2 panel (Table 4.2). Human DNA depletion was incorporated by assigning additional ReadFish conditions for host sequence removal to the same flow cell channels used for enrichment (Appendix 10: Section 2).

4.2.8 Adaptive detection experiments

All subsequent adaptive detection experiments used strict parameters, requiring multiple matches to pathogen(s) and the full homolog CARD database, while depleting any read with a single match to the human genome reference. Initial experiments targeted *E. coli* in mock community samples spiked with *E. coli* (NCTC 13351) and varying levels of human DNA, followed by the same procedure with the clinical *E. coli* isolate (Appendix 10: Section 2). This was repeated for *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373) and its clinical isolate, again using mock communities diluted with human DNA. Additional mock communities spiked with clinical *S. epidermidis* were also sequenced, targeting *S. aureus* (Appendix 10: Section 2). The same procedures were applied to forearm skin microbiome samples spiked with the corresponding reference and clinical strains, each enriched for their target species. For all nine experimental groups, one sample per set was additionally sequenced to enrich for all BCID2 panel bacteria (Table 4.1). Finally, previously collected peri-wound swabs were adaptively sequenced to first target all BCID2-listed bacteria and then specifically enrich for *S. aureus* (Appendix 10: Section 2).

4.2.9 Bioinformatics processing and analysis

All ONT FAST5 files were basecalled and demultiplexed using Guppy v6.0.6 high-accuracy mode (Wick *et al.*, 2019) on a local bioinformatics workstation, then processed on an HPC cluster with the Adaptive Sequencing Analysis Workflow (ASAW), a Snakemake-based workflow v7.32.4 (Mölder *et al.*, 2021) designed to compare control and experimental adaptive sequencing runs of human metagenomic microbiome samples using ReadFish. Full analysis, as detailed in [Subsections 3.2.6–3.2.9](#), was conducted for each sample to assess software performance, classify rejected reads, and evaluate adaptive sequencing outcomes. Standard microbiome analyses included quality control with fastp v0.23.4 (Chen *et al.*, 2018), host filtering via Minimap2 v2.28 (Li, 2021) and SAMtools v1.16.1 (Li *et al.*, 2009), contig assembly using Flye v2.9.5 (Kolmogorov *et al.*, 2020), taxonomic classification with Kraken2 v2.1.3 (Wood *et al.*, 2019), and downstream community analysis (Table 1.4) using bash and R scripts v4.2.2 (Table 1.5).

ASAW's workflow structure, functions, and outputs are detailed in [Subsections 3.2.6–3.2.9](#) and the [GitHub user guide](#) (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752062; Appendix 13). Antimicrobial resistance profiling was subsequently performed on an HPC cluster with the Resistance Gene Identifier (RGI v4.0.3) from the CARD database (Alcock *et al.*, 2023) on all samples and unclassified reads. All analyses were executed on the University of Hull's Viper High-Performance Computing cluster with technical support from its team.

4.2.10 Reproducibility and data availability

To promote transparency and facilitate reproducibility, all detailed protocols, scripts, and instructions for all wet and dry lab procedures described are available in Appendices 1-13 and archived in a Zenodo repositories. Full description of all consumables, equipment, and kits used for wet lab methods are available on protocols.io (DOI: 10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1), as described in Appendix 1. Whenever feasible, all raw sequencing data produced and bioinformatic processes have been developed in reproducible workflows and/or scripts and archived (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) (Appendices 6-13). This includes ASAW, which is fully documented and archived alongside these materials to ensure reproducibility of all analyses on GitHub (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752062; Appendix 13). All analysis results and scripts to create figures for the workflow and RGI results for optimization and experimental runs and the corresponding figure scripts can be found in Appendix 5: Section 3 (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007).

4.3 Results

4.3.1 Optimizing ReadFish for combined enrichment and host depletion

Optimization test runs were conducted to determine the ideal parameters for ReadFish adaptive detection using mock community samples spiked with *E. coli* (NCTC 13351) and diluted with varying amounts of human DNA. Three experimental conditions were tested: (1) default enrichment of *E. coli* and the full CARD homolog database; (2) strict hit parameters requiring multiple matches to enrich for *E. coli* and the full CARD database; and (3) combined human DNA depletion with enrichment for *E. coli* and selected ARGs from CARD. In control runs, *E. coli* accounted for ~15% of classified reads. All adaptive runs increased this to ~30%, more than doubling the relative abundance of *E. coli*, with minimal variation across the three test conditions (Figure 4.2A). Human-assigned reads averaged 50% in control samples. Optimization runs one and two reduced human reads by ~10%, while test three, incorporating both enrichment and depletion, achieved the greatest reduction, lowering human sequences by approximately 40% (Figure 4.2A).

Figure 4.2 Comparison and overall performance of ReadFish optimization runs for adaptive detection development. (A) Average percentage of sequences assigned to *E. coli* and human in the control, test one, test two, and test three adaptive sequencing runs. (B) Stacked bar plot of sequence counts belonging to the 15 most abundant taxonomies in rejected reads from adaptive sequencing test runs one, two, and three. (C) Heatmap of the number and type of antimicrobial resistance gene strict hits from RGI across the control, test one, test two, and test three adaptive sequencing runs. (Appendix 5: Section 3)

Taxonomic classification of reads rejected by ReadFish across the three adaptive sequencing runs showed differences in quantity but not in taxa detected. The majority of

rejected reads were human, with the remainder, approximately half, assigned to other mock community microbes (Figure 4.2B). Run two had the highest number of rejected reads (~20,000), nearly double that of run one (~12,000), while run three had the fewest (~8,000), though a greater proportion were human derived. Test run two also showed a higher percentage of rejected *Prevotella* spp. and human reads, whereas tests one and three had similar distributions across rejected bacterial taxa (Figure 4.2B).

ARG profiling with RGI revealed that run two retained more ARGs overall, including most of those identified in the control, though low-abundance genes, such as *TEM*, were less frequently detected in all adaptive runs. Run one had the fewest ARG hits overall and the lowest detection of *E. coli*-associated genes. Test run three showed a reduced total number of ARGs compared to the control but had a slightly higher yield than test one (Figure 4.2C).

4.3.2 Targeted enrichment preserves microbial community composition

Mock community samples spiked with target strains and diluted with human DNA underwent three adaptive detection types using strict hit parameters from optimization test run 2: targeting *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, or all bacteria listed in the BCID2 panel (Table 4.1), while simultaneously depleting sequences matching the human genome reference. Community composition remained consistent between control and adaptive runs, with the six core species from the DNA standard detected at expected relative abundances ([Subsection 1.9.1](#)). Adaptive runs showed enrichment of the target strains, although targeting all BCID2 species yielded smaller increases in target abundance and more even species distribution (Figure 4.3A).

In spiked skin microbiome samples processed under the same adaptive parameters, greater variation was observed across detection types. Species identified in control runs remained detectable in adaptive sequencing, with no loss of taxa (alpha diversity, Figure 4.3D) or large shifts in community structure (similar beta-diversity scores, Figure 4.3E) aside from enrichment of targeted strains. As with the mock community, BCID2-targeted runs in skin samples showed more even species distributions and smaller increases in targeted strains, with a notably higher abundance of *Dolosigranulum pigrum* relative to other non-targeted taxa (Figure 4.3B).

Figure 4.3 Microbial community profiling and changes across all samples and adaptive detection runs. (A) Taxonomy assignments for the 9 most abundant species, excluding human, in mock community samples from the control and *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and all pathogen enrichment runs. (B) Taxonomy assignments for the 9 most abundant species, excluding human, in skin microbiome samples from the control and *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and all pathogen enrichment runs. (C) Taxonomy assignments for the 9 most abundant species, excluding human, in peri-wound samples from the control and *S. aureus* and all pathogen enrichment runs. (D) Shannon scores of the mock community, skin microbiome, and peri-wound samples from the control and *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and all pathogen enrichment runs. (E) PCA plot of community dissimilarities of adaptive versus control mock community, skin microbiome, and peri-wound samples calculated with Bray-Curtis dissimilarity. (Appendix 5: Section 3)

Peri-wound samples were sequenced using the same adaptive parameters, targeting either *S. aureus* or all BCID2 pathogens (Table 4.1). Community composition shifts varied by the dominant species in each sample. Samples dominated by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed minimal differences between control and adaptive runs, while those containing *S. aureus* exhibited increased *S. aureus* abundance without loss of other taxa. Overall compositional changes mirrored those from enrichment for all pathogens, with negligible differences between detection types (Figure 4.3C).

Species diversity was more sensitive to detection type. Mock communities showed consistent diversity across runs, with a slight increase following all adaptive detection types and a mild decrease when targeting *S. aureus*. Skin microbiome samples exhibited greater variation, including diversity decreased with *S. aureus* targeting, increased with *E. coli* targeting, and remained stable with BCID2 enrichment. In peri-wound samples, diversity increased under both adaptive detection conditions (Figure 4.3D). Community dissimilarity was driven primarily by sample type, either mock, skin, or peri-wound, rather than detection type. Adaptive sequencing did not significantly alter inter-sample similarity but did reduce variability among replicates within each group (Figure 4.3E).

4.3.3 Improved pathogen recovery and substantial host DNA reduction

Adaptive detection doubled the average percentage of sequences assigned to enriched strains of interest (*E. coli* NCTC 13351, clinical *E. coli*, *S. aureus* NCTC 13373, or clinical *S. aureus*). In contrast, samples containing *S. epidermidis* showed minimal change when enriched for *S. aureus* or all BCID2 pathogens (Table 4.1). *E. coli* enrichment outcomes varied slightly by enrichment type, with an average 22% increase in sequence assignment; clinical *E. coli* had a higher overall percentage than the reference strain, though both increased similarly. For *S. aureus*, enrichment produced similar relative increases across runs, but the clinical strain showed a 5% greater increase than the reference. In peri-wound samples with *P. aeruginosa*, adaptive detection targeting all BCID2 pathogens yielded little change (Figure 4.4A).

The number of sequences assigned to strains of interest did not always match the increases observed in their percentage within samples. In adaptive sequencing runs, the number of *E. coli* reads was consistently lower than in control runs by 100–300 reads, with clinical *E. coli* showing the greater decrease. In contrast, sequences assigned to *S. aureus* increased by approximately 300 reads for both clinical and reference strains. *S. epidermidis* showed minimal change, while *P. aeruginosa* reads decreased by an average of ~750 (Figure 4.4C).

Figure 4.4 The increase in relative and absolute amounts of the strains of interest after adaptive detection. (A) The average percentage of sequences assigned to *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), clinical *E. coli*, *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373), clinical *S. aureus*, clinical *S. epidermidis*, and *Pseudomonas* in all control runs compared to all adaptive detection runs. (B) The percentage of sequences assigned to *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), clinical *E. coli*, *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373), clinical *S. aureus*, clinical *S. epidermidis*, and *Pseudomonas* in all control runs compared to all adaptive detection runs. (C) The average number of sequences assigned to *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), clinical *E. coli*, *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373), clinical *S. aureus*, clinical *S. epidermidis*, and *Pseudomonas* in all control runs compared to all adaptive detection runs. (Appendix 5: Section 3)

In skin swabs adaptively sequenced to enrich for all target pathogens and ARGs with host depletion, bacterial read counts decreased by ~1,500 compared to control; however, in peri-wound swabs sequenced under the same conditions, the number of bacterial reads approximately doubled, with the exception of one *P. aeruginosa*-dominant sample, which showed a slight decrease. A pure *S. epidermidis* sample enriched for *S. aureus* yielded ~4,000 reads in both control and adaptive runs (Figure 4.4C).

Combining enrichment with simultaneous human DNA depletion using ReadFish consistently reduced human read percentages by ~50% (Figure 4.5A), a result maintained across all adaptive runs following final optimization (Subsection 4.3.1). Most reads rejected during adaptive sequencing were correctly classified as *Homo sapiens*, with the remainder varying by adaptive detection type. Rejected reads included all species in the microbial communities except the targeted bacterial strains. For *E. coli* enrichment, more human sequences were removed, while enrichment for all BCID2 panel bacteria led to a higher rejection of *Pseudomonas* sequences (Table 4.1; Figure 4.5B).

Figure 4.5 The effectiveness of host depletion after adaptive detection. (A) The average percentage of human sequences in mock community, skin microbiome, and peri-wound samples from the control and *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and all pathogen enrichment runs. (B) The ten most abundant taxonomies of rejected reads from the mock community, skin microbiome, and peri-wound samples from the *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and all pathogen enrichment runs. (Appendix 5: Section 3)

4.3.4 Resistance gene detection remains robust with gains in clinical strains

ARGs in all samples, including rejected reads from adaptive detection runs, were predicted using RGI. ARG profiles varied by drug class, mechanism, and gene family, with the primary determinant being the strain of interest. Differences between control and adaptive runs were mainly in the number of ARG hits. Samples containing *E. coli* (NCTC 13351) showed fewer ARGs after adaptive detection than in controls, whereas clinical *E. coli* samples exhibited an

increase in both ARG types and abundance. Both *S. aureus* strains showed increased ARG concentration and diversity after adaptive detection (Figure 4.6).

Notably, *mecR1* and *ANT* genes were unique to *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373), while genes shared with the clinical strain were more abundant in the latter. *S. epidermidis* samples had fewer total ARGs overall but showed increased ARG types and concentrations following adaptive detection (Figure 4.6). The average number of strict ARG hits increased in most adaptive detection runs. Although *E. coli* (NCTC 13351) samples had a higher ARG count than clinical *E. coli*, they showed a reduction post-adaptive sequencing, while clinical *E. coli* exhibited a modest increase.

Figure 4.6 The most prevalent strict hits of ARGs found by RGI. Abundance of ARGs in samples containing *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), clinical *E. coli*, *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373), clinical *S. aureus*, clinical *S. epidermidis*, and *P. aeruginosa* in control and all adaptive detection runs. (Appendix 5: Section 3)

Samples containing clinical *S. aureus* had a higher average number of ARGs than those with *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373) but showed a smaller increase from control. The highest ARG count, and largest adaptive sequencing increase occurred in samples with *S. epidermidis*. In contrast, peri-wound samples dominated by *Pseudomonas* had the fewest ARGs and showed a slight decrease after adaptive detection (Figure 4.7A).

Figure 4.7 Counts and types of antimicrobial resistance genes found in samples containing the strains of interest and rejected reads. (A) The number of strict hits for ARGs found in samples containing *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), clinical *E. coli*, *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373), clinical *S. aureus*, clinical *S. epidermidis*, and *P. aeruginosa* compared between control and all adaptive detection runs. (B) The distribution of strict hits of the twenty most abundant ARGs from the BCID2 panel across all types of adaptive detection runs, control runs and rejected reads. (Appendix 5: Section 3)

ARG hits from the BCID2 panel (Table 4.2) varied by adaptive detection type. *S. aureus*-enriched samples had the highest number of ARGs overall, though fewer ARG types, mainly *mecA* and *S. aureus Lmr*. Their corresponding rejected reads also contained *mecA* and *S. aureus Lmr*, along with more ARG types and total hits. Some expected ARGs, such as *CTX-M 6* (Tables 4.2 and 4.3), were not detected in enriched samples but were found in the rejected reads of *E. coli*-targeted runs. *E. coli* enrichment yielded more ARG diversity but fewer total hits than *S. aureus* enrichment. The fewest ARGs were found in samples enriched for all BCID2 bacteria. Rejected reads from these runs also had fewer BCID2 ARGs, though *mecA* remained present (Figure 4.7B).

4.4 Discussion

Diagnosing skin wound infections remains a major global health challenge, with significant financial and quality-of-life burdens (Järbrink *et al.*, 2017; Esteban *et al.*, 2023). Clinical diagnostic methods are often slow, limited, and lack precision (Canchy *et al.*, 2023; Nayak *et al.*, 2023). Molecular diagnostics offer promising solutions, improving pathogen identification, resistance detection, and time to intervention (Liu *et al.*, 2020; Misic *et al.*, 2014; Tomic-Canic *et al.*, 2020), though their availability and affordability remain limited (Liu *et al.*, 2020; Mulcahy-O'Grady *et al.*, 2016).

This study addressed these challenges by developing a molecular method that simultaneously adaptively detects clinically relevant antibiotic-resistant pathogens (Senok *et al.*, 2023) and depletes host sequences from emulated mixed microbial wound samples. Sample sets were designed to evaluate factors influencing performance, including comparison of reference versus clinical strains, varying levels of host contamination, and the method's impact on microbial community composition and ARG profiles. The study also assessed the method's effectiveness in low-yield DNA samples, its capacity to distinguish closely related species, and its performance in enriching target organisms from clinical peri-wound swabs.

Few studies have applied adaptive sequencing to microbiome data, and even fewer to metagenomic sequencing. Most existing work has focused on host sequence depletion (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Ong *et al.*, 2022; Gan *et al.*, 2021; Cheng *et al.*, 2022; Hewel *et al.*, 2024), while others have targeted gene or genomic region enrichment (Kipp *et al.*, 2023; Wrenn and Drown, 2023; Viehweger *et al.*, 2023), specific species (Ulrich *et al.*, 2024; Lin *et al.*, 2023), or balancing representation of low-abundance taxa (Martin *et al.*, 2022); however, no published studies to date have combined these approaches, few have tested them on mixed microbial communities, and only one has attempted adaptive sequencing on a Flongle device (Wrenn and Drown, 2023), the most rapid and cost-effective Nanopore option (Avershina *et al.*, 2022). The present study advances this field by implementing adaptive sequencing on a Flongle to simultaneously enrich for all clinically relevant ARGs and pathogenic species in mixed microbial communities while depleting host sequences.

4.4.1 Optimised parameters, references, and depletion

As the methods implemented here are novel, optimization was essential and involved evaluating ReadFish hit parameters, refining target reference specificity, and integrating host depletion. Prior studies using adaptive sequencing on microbiome data have not reported modifying the default ReadFish criteria for defining a hit, typically a single match to the reference genome (Cheng *et al.*, 2022; Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Ong *et al.*, 2022; Gan *et al.*, 2021;

Hewel *et al.*, 2024; Ulrich *et al.*, 2024; Viehweger *et al.*, 2023). Thus, the influence of hit sensitivity on species enrichment in complex microbial communities remains largely unexamined. In this study, as depicted in Figure 4.2, stricter hit parameters requiring multiple matches to the reference (Payne *et al.*, 2021) led to an average 10% increase in enrichment of the strain of interest, *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), compared to the default settings. This configuration also doubled the number of rejected reads, none of which were classified as *E. coli* (Figure 4.2B). The improved enrichment may reflect enhanced exclusion of shorter reads that typically lack confident taxonomic assignments (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022), or more precise targeting of sequences aligning to both bacterial genomes and ARG references.

The ARG target set was then narrowed from the full CARD database to include only those listed in the BioFire BCID2 panel (Table 4.2), to assess whether a more specific reference would improve the software's ability to select only relevant strains or resistance genes. This refinement was hypothesized to enhance enrichment by limiting matches to genes of interest while excluding non-target strains or, alternatively, by reducing the reference size and shortening decision time (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Ulrich *et al.*, 2022); however, this adjustment had no effect on the quantity of *E. coli* (NCTC 13351) sequences and resulted in fewer ARGs identified by RGI. The detected ARGs had fewer high-quality matches, with only one low-quality hit corresponding to *E. coli* (NCTC 13351), and no measurable decrease in ReadFish decision time was observed (Figure 4.2C). Consequently, all subsequent experiments used the full CARD homolog database as the reference for ARGs.

Human sequence depletion was also evaluated to assess whether the added computational load affected ReadFish's response time or enrichment performance. This modification nearly doubled the number of rejected sequences relative to the initial test run, with most being human. Fewer bacterial species were rejected, and the increase in the proportion of *E. coli* sequences remained consistent (Figure 4.2B). Overall, the percentage of human sequences decreased by approximately 50% (Figure 4.2A). Therefore, all subsequent adaptive detection runs employed parameters requiring multiple mapping hits for enrichment, targeting *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, or all pathogens in the BCID2 panel (Table 4.1), as well as all ARGs in the CARD database, while concurrently depleting any sequence with at least one match to the human reference genome.

4.4.2 Community composition and increased diversity

The application of adaptive sequencing to simultaneously enrich and deplete organisms in mixed microbial samples inevitably alters community composition (Cheng *et al.*, 2022; Hewel *et al.*, 2024; Ulrich *et al.*, 2024). While reductions in host DNA and increases in targeted

organisms were anticipated, additional analyses confirmed that no species were lost, and that adaptive detection accurately reflected the original microbial community. Overall, adaptive detection consistently increased species diversity across all sample types (Figure 4.3D). Across experimental runs, sample origin, mock community or human swab, had a greater influence on inter-sample variation than the use of adaptive sequencing (Figure 4.3E). Moreover, community composition remained stable across all sequencing and sample types, with bacterial species present in approximately the same relative abundances, aside from an increased proportion of sequences belonging to the targeted strain (Figures 4.3A, 4.3B, and 4.3C). Differences in the effects of adaptive detection between sample types were largely attributable to the initial proportions of human and bacterial DNA.

In DNA standard mock communities spiked with strains of interest, adaptive detection generally led to a reduction in the number of bacterial sequences; however, this loss was not observed when the same samples were diluted with human DNA (Figure 4.5A), likely because, in the absence of host DNA, more bacterial sequences were misidentified as human and removed (Breitwieser *et al.*, 2019). Community composition in mock samples aligned with expectations ([Subsection 1.9.1](#)), except for *Schaalia odontolytica*, which was consistently underrepresented in both control and adaptive runs (Figure 4.3A). This finding, also reported in previous studies (Chung *et al.*, 2020), likely reflects factors unrelated to adaptive sequencing, as its relative abundance remained stable across conditions.

The skin swab samples lacked an expected community profile. Nevertheless, adaptive detection successfully enriched bacterial sequences in mixed, low-yield, host-contaminated samples, regardless of whether a strain of interest was added. On average, bacterial sequence proportions increased from 3% to 95% following adaptive detection, with enrichment levels positively correlating with DNA yield (Figure 4.5A). Changes in skin microbiome composition varied depending on the enrichment target and whether a strain of interest was spiked. For instance, in samples that naturally contained *E. coli*, adaptive detection eliminated all other microbial members. In contrast, samples lacking *E. coli* showed increased species richness and a more even community distribution compared to control runs (Figure 4.3B). Species diversity also varied more across skin samples, with forearm swabs spiked with *S. aureus* exhibiting the only decrease (Figure 4.3D), likely due to strong enrichment and subsequent dominance of this species.

The peri-wound swabs sequenced with adaptive detection were unknown mixed microbial communities collected from infected leg wounds. Initial sequencing targeted human DNA depletion and enrichment of all bacterial pathogens listed in the BCID2 panel (Table 4.1), as well as all ARG homologs from CARD. These samples were primarily dominated by either *S.*

aureus or *P. aeruginosa*. Generally, adaptive detection resulted in a twofold increase in bacterial sequence counts, except in one *P. aeruginosa*-dominated sample, which showed a slight decrease (Figure 4.5A). Although *P. aeruginosa* is included in the BCID2 enrichment panel (Senok *et al.*, 2023), its relative abundance remained largely unchanged between control and adaptive runs. Conversely, samples dominated by *S. aureus* showed increases in both total bacterial sequences and the proportion of *S. aureus* (Figure 4.3C). The muted response in *P. aeruginosa*-dominated samples may be due to the challenges of sequencing this species with Nanopore devices (R9.4.1), which have been shown to yield lower categorical agreement and higher error rates for *P. aeruginosa* than for other clinically relevant pathogens (Harris *et al.*, 2024).

4.4.3 Doubled strains of interest and halved host

The differences observed between adaptive detection and control runs for enriched strains of interest and depleted host sequences were substantial. Nearly all host contamination was removed, with an average reduction in human sequences of approximately 50%, as shown in Figure 4.5, consistent with previously described runs (Section 3.3) and about 15–20% greater than reductions reported in earlier studies using host depletion (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Ong *et al.*, 2022; Gan *et al.*, 2021; Cheng *et al.*, 2022; Hewel *et al.*, 2024). The effectiveness of ReadFish in depleting host DNA was further supported by the taxonomy of rejected reads, which were predominantly human. Of the few bacterial reads rejected, none belonged to the targeted strain (Figure 4.5B). Enrichment of strains of interest nearly doubled their relative abundance, with an average increase of ~40% across strain types, species enriched, and sample types (Figure 4.4).

To evaluate whether species or bacterial type influenced enrichment efficiency, two clinically relevant pathogens were targeted. While relative abundances increased at similar rates, sequence counts varied. For instance, samples spiked with *E. coli* showed a slight decrease in the number of sequences across adaptive runs, whereas *S. aureus* consistently showed ~200 more sequences in adaptive runs compared to controls (Figure 4.4C). Alternative methods for isolating a specific bacterial species, such as culture or DNA amplification, may yield greater specificity, but are highly selective and can alter the rest of the microbial community (Kai *et al.*, 2019; Kong *et al.*, 2001; Bonnet *et al.*, 2020).

More traditional methods are also poorly suited to uncharacterized communities or unknown pathogens and require multiple preparatory steps prior to sequencing (Miller and Chiu, 2022; Wensel *et al.*, 2022). Currently, Nanopore adaptive sequencing is the only method that enables real-time, selective targeting of bacterial species during sequencing (Payne *et al.*, 2021). As such, adaptive detection remains the sole technique capable of significantly enriching

target organisms and depleting host sequences while preserving overall microbial community structure.

4.4.4 Differentiation of species and strains

A key concern in adaptive detection is the ability to distinguish closely related species, such as *S. aureus* and *S. epidermidis*. As depicted in Figure 4.4, when enriched for *S. aureus*, samples containing *S. epidermidis* showed no increase in either percentage or number of *S. epidermidis* sequences, and some reads were rejected. Similar results were observed during enrichment for all bacterial pathogens in the BioFire BCID2 panel (Table 4.1), which includes multiple *Staphylococcus* species but not *S. epidermidis*. This indicates that adaptive detection was specific enough to avoid enriching clinically relevant but often misclassified species. This distinction is particularly significant for skin microbiome metagenomic studies, where communities commonly contain *S. epidermidis* and *S. aureus*, which are notoriously difficult to differentiate using metagenomic methods (Sunagar *et al.*, 2013).

The ability to distinguish these species is critical, as they frequently cohabit similar environments but play opposing roles, with *S. epidermidis* typically inhibiting *S. aureus* colonization (Severn and Horswill, 2023; Canchy *et al.*, 2023). Another important consideration is how adaptive detection performs when targeting reference versus clinical strains, as the latter often diverge more from genome references (Van Rossum *et al.*, 2020). Enrichment results varied between the two species of interest. For example, although the clinical *E. coli* strain showed a substantial increase compared to its control, its percentage increase was slightly lower than that of *E. coli* (NCTC 13351) (Figure 4.4B). This may reflect differences in resistance profiles, as the clinical *E. coli* strain (Table 4.3) carries fewer predicted ARGs than the reference strain (Sirot *et al.*, 1987).

In contrast, clinical *S. aureus* had, on average, 10% more sequences than *S. aureus* (NCTC 13373) and four additional predicted resistances (Figure 4.4B), despite both being MRSA strains (Table 4.3). These findings suggest that the resistance profile of a target strain may influence enrichment, with greater enrichment observed for strains harbouring more ARGs; however, no enrichment was observed in *E. coli*-spiked samples when targeting *S. aureus*, or vice versa (Figure 4.3), indicating that ReadFish does not enrich resistant strains in the absence of a species-specific reference in the enrichment target.

4.4.5 Resistance genes targeted and reduced

The variety of strains tested provides insights not only into adaptive detection's capacity to enrich organisms with diverse genomic features, but also into its performance across varying resistance profiles relevant to clinical application. Overall, fewer ARGs were identified in

adaptive runs than in controls, and approximately half of the hits reported by RGI were categorized as “strict”, the category discussed here, as no perfect (100% exact match) hits were found (Figure 4.7A). Strict hits are used to identify modified antibiotic targets or ARG variants (Alcock *et al.*, 2023). All samples with CARD-matched ARGs displayed resistance to multiple antimicrobials, and strict ARG hits were consistently lower in adaptive detection runs than their respective controls, as shown in Figure 4.6.

Samples spiked with *E. coli* had fewer ARGs in both adaptive and control runs than those spiked with *S. aureus*. Among ARGs detected in controls but not in adaptive runs, most were associated with non-target community members, for example, *lmrB*, a *Bacillus* spp. gene (Yoshida *et al.*, 2004), and *Omp38*, from *Burkholderia* spp. (Siritapetawee *et al.*, 2004) (Figure 4.6). Some ARGs typically found in the strains of interest, such as *TLA-1* and various *TET* genes, were also identified only in controls (Poirel *et al.*, 2018; Mlynarczyk-Bonikowska *et al.*, 2022). However, in most samples, the anticipated ARGs were not fully recovered in either control or adaptive runs. For clinical *S. aureus*, most expected resistances (Table 4.3) were found in both sequencing types, yet despite higher ARG counts in control runs, more expected resistances were identified in adaptive runs (Figure 4.7B) (Hanif and Hassan, 2019). In clinical *E. coli* samples, resistance to ampicillin and amoxicillin was anticipated (Table 4.3), but corresponding ARGs were not detected in either condition (Figure 4.7B) (Wu *et al.*, 2021).

Since *E. coli* (NCTC 13351) is a TEM-3 extended spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) strain (Sirot *et al.*, 1987), an increase in *TEM* gene hits was expected, yet adaptive runs yielded fewer *TEM* hits than controls. Results for both clinical and reference *S. aureus*, *mecA*-positive MRSA strains (Dicks *et al.*, 2021), were similar, with fewer *mecA* hits in adaptive runs (Figure 4.6). Both *TEM* and *mecA* genes are frequently plasmid-borne or associated with other mobile genetic elements (MGEs) (Paterson and Bonomo, 2005; Wielders *et al.*, 2002), and the reduced recovery of these ARGs may stem from known challenges in extracting, preparing, and sequencing plasmids and MGEs from metagenomic samples (Ulrich *et al.*, 2024).

4.4.6 Limitations and future research directions

While adaptive detection with ReadFish can enrich for resistant pathogens and deplete host contamination in mixed microbial communities, some limitations remain. A key challenge during implementation was the complexity of software installation and configuration, as ReadFish is developed independently from ONT and depends on Guppy for live basecalling, which requires a high-performance GPU. As a reference-dependent method, it is also subject to limitations related to database selection, including variability in taxonomic resolution, the impact of curation and updates, and inherent bias toward species with more available reference

genomes (Breitwieser *et al.*, 2019; Sierra *et al.*, 2020; Dias *et al.*, 2020). Challenges specific to adaptive sequencing include minimal increases in the total number of bacterial sequences, variable enrichment and depletion efficiency depending on read length, and the inclusion of some rejected reads in final analyses. Nevertheless, as a novel and evolving technology, many of these issues are likely to be resolved over time.

Future research should address the current difficulty of ARG enrichment in microbiome samples. One potential solution is to incorporate plasmid references into the enrichment targets, as most ARGs are plasmid-associated, and prior studies have demonstrated that adaptive sequencing can significantly enrich for MGEs in metagenomic datasets (Ulrich *et al.*, 2024); however, plasmids and other MGEs remain challenging to extract, prepare, and sequence consistently from complex metagenomic samples, potentially limiting recovery of clinically relevant or novel ARGs. To partially mitigate this issue, broad metagenomic sequencing was retained alongside adaptive targeting to preserve wider genomic context and reduce dependence on predefined resistance targets alone. Continued large-scale surveillance and expansion of ARG reference databases will also remain essential for improving diagnostic reliability, particularly as novel and emerging resistance determinants continue to evolve. Additional steps include increasing the sample size to improve statistical power and better evaluate the method's applicability in clinical contexts.

There are broader challenges in applying high-throughput sequencing (HTS) as a molecular diagnostic tool, and previous studies remain divided on its clinical feasibility (Chen *et al.*, 2024). Although HTS is widely recognized as a rapid, culture-independent method for pathogen identification (Esteban *et al.*, 2023), its utility often depends on sample type and healthcare setting (Chen *et al.*, 2024). These factors limit the applicability of certain HTS approaches that are restricted to specific sample types or lack adaptability for diverse clinical scenarios. Adaptive sequencing presents a compelling alternative, enabling real-time initiation and parameter adjustment during sequencing to meet user-defined objectives (Cheng *et al.*, 2022). Targets for enrichment or depletion are specified in a single, modifiable file, allowing flexible adaptation of sequencing goals (Payne *et al.*, 2021). While cost remains a consideration (Meirelles *et al.*, 2024), ONT provides one of the most affordable HTS platforms. Use of small, low-cost flow cells such as the Flongle further reduces sequencing time and expense (Buytaers *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2021).

Molecular diagnostics platforms like the BioFire FilmArray have improved the speed and accessibility of pathogen detection but are constrained by key limitations. These include reliance on fixed detection panels, which prevent identification of novel or unexpected pathogens, and limited resolution at the strain level. BioFire also depends on positive culture

results, delaying diagnosis and excluding direct-from-sample applications (Esteban *et al.*, 2023; Kim *et al.*, 2024). High implementation costs, including equipment acquisition, infection-specific proprietary kits, and recurring per-test expenses, further hinder scalability, particularly in resource-limited settings (Mponponsoo *et al.*, 2022; Gor and Joshi, 2024). In contrast, the adaptive detection method developed in this study offers a next-generation alternative that maintains the comprehensive, unbiased scope of metagenomic sequencing while overcoming many traditional barriers to clinical adoption. Without compromising contextual insight into the broader microbial community, this approach enables selective enrichment of key pathogenic strains and antimicrobial resistance genes, while reducing host contamination by over 50%. By leveraging cost-effective nanopore platforms such as the Flongle and integrating open-source tools like ReadFish, the method provides a more scalable, flexible, and economically accessible model than closed-system diagnostics. For example, ONT MinION devices are available from approximately \$3,150 USD, with Flongle flow cells costing approximately \$90 USD per run (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, 2026), whereas reported BioFire FilmArray Torch instrument costs can exceed \$19,500 USD, alongside substantially higher proprietary consumable costs starting at \$155–417 USD (DiDiodato *et al.*, 2022). Rather than being limited by static detection panels, adaptive sequencing dynamically targets medically relevant content in real time, enhancing both diagnostic precision and taxonomic breadth. These features position adaptive sequencing as a powerful tool for advancing both the technical capacity and clinical viability of precision diagnostics.

By design, metagenomic sequencing captures all microbial taxa and their associated genetic elements, including antimicrobial resistance and virulence factors. While this breadth is a key strength, it is also perceived as a drawback due to high host contamination and the detection of clinically irrelevant organisms (Miller and Chiu, 2022). These issues increase computational burden and data processing time, further hindering clinical implementation (Wang *et al.*, 2021; Mulcahy-O'Grady and Workentine, 2016). Adaptive sequencing addresses these limitations by selectively enriching for clinically significant targets and depleting host DNA in real time. This not only reduces non-informative data but also improves interpretability of results, ultimately enabling faster and more actionable diagnostics. In doing so, adaptive detection helps overcome several persistent barriers to metagenomic HTS and presents a viable path toward its routine integration into clinical practice.

4.5 Conclusion

As demonstrated here, adaptive sequencing on a Nanopore Flongle device enables real-time, accurate detection of clinically important resistant pathogens within mixed microbial

communities. While this remains an emerging field with some limitations yet to be resolved, its growing utility, popularity, and continual refinement position it as a promising solution to the current challenges in skin and wound microbiome research and treatment. Because it is independent of culture, enables antimicrobial resistance profiling, and permits full community analysis, this method offers diagnostic insights unavailable through traditional techniques. Implementing such an approach could provide a low-cost, customizable, rapid, and informative diagnostic tool, delivering timely, targeted results to support clinical decision-making. With continued development, adaptive detection may help mitigate the substantial public health threat posed by wound infections and has the potential to transform modern medical diagnostics.

Chapter 5 Discussion

The skin microbiome represents a clinically significant yet technically demanding system, where host physiology and microbial activity intersect to influence immunity, wound healing, and infection risk (Grice and Segre, 2011; Smythe and Wilkinson, 2023). Disruptions in this ecosystem contribute to chronic wounds and opportunistic infections, but its analysis remains constrained by low microbial biomass, high inter-individual variability, and extensive host DNA contamination (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Zielińska *et al.*, 2023; Morsli *et al.*, 2024). Although metagenomic sequencing offers the resolution needed to study such complex communities (Bharti and Grimm, 2021; Chen *et al.*, 2023), persistent challenges in contamination control, reproducibility, and interpretability limit clinical translation. Overcoming these barriers requires approaches that integrate methodological rigor with diagnostic relevance (Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023; Forry *et al.*, 2024).

These constraints set the agenda for the research conducted here, which pursued three linked objectives: to overcome reproducibility barriers by embedding environment control, provenance tracking, and consensus-based classification within a reusable workflow; to optimise adaptive sequencing for selective host depletion on accessible hardware; and to evaluate whether these improvements increase recovery of clinically relevant signals, particularly pathogens and antimicrobial resistance determinants, within host-dominated, low-yield samples. Framed in this way, methodological rigor functions not as an endpoint but as the necessary precondition for scalability and, ultimately, for translating skin microbiome research into diagnostic and therapeutic contexts.

The research here advanced along a deliberate trajectory, from establishing methodological stability to testing translational potential. Reproducibility was the initial priority, addressing persistent concerns about variability and the reliability of computational workflows in skin microbiome metagenomics. On this foundation, adaptive sequencing was explored as a novel means of shaping sequencing outputs directly rather than passively accepting raw data streams. By reducing host DNA in low-biomass samples and stabilizing microbial read recovery, adaptive sequencing not only addressed long-standing bioinformatic obstacles but also strengthened reproducibility by producing outputs less vulnerable to stochastic noise.

Once feasibility and scalability were demonstrated, the approach was extended to proof-of-concept applications, including the targeted detection of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes. These studies represent complementary advances with reproducible frameworks making rigorous evaluation possible, while adaptive strategies in

turn reinforced reproducibility and expanded the range of clinically relevant insights. This trajectory highlights how methodological rigor provides the foundation for innovation, allowing adaptive sequencing to progress beyond technical constraint toward substantive analysis. Tested against the complexity of the skin microbiome, the integration of reproducibility and adaptability demonstrates how robust frameworks can transform challenging microbial systems into sources of broader scientific and translational relevance.

5.0 Reproducibility as a foundation

Reproducibility is the condition on which the credibility of metagenomic sequencing and microbiome research rests. Without rigorous consistency across wet-lab and computational workflows, results cannot be scaled, compared, or trusted, whether in research or in diagnostic contexts (Santiago-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2023). Sequencing technologies promise high-resolution insights into microbial communities, yet those insights carry little weight if they cannot be replicated across laboratories, cohorts, or time points (Galloway-Peña and Hanson, 2020). For example, studies of wound infections have shown that differences in bioinformatic pipelines can lead to conflicting identifications of pathogens or antimicrobial resistance genes, raising questions about whether such signals reflect biology or analytical artefact (Franzosa *et al.*, 2018; Knight *et al.*, 2018). Reproducibility therefore is not a peripheral safeguard but the foundation that transforms exploratory microbiome investigations into reliable, cumulative science and, ultimately, into knowledge that can inform clinical decision-making.

5.0.1 Overcoming reproducibility barriers with standardized workflows

The foundational role of reproducibility becomes most apparent when efforts are made to replicate existing studies. Attempts to reconstruct influential skin microbiome analyses in Chapter 2 exposed the depth of the reproducibility crisis, as incomplete documentation, missing intermediate files, inconsistent parameter reporting, and outdated software environments frequently obstructed progress. For one study, only partial replication was possible before technical incompatibilities halted further analysis; in another, few results could be reproduced but only at prohibitive computational and time cost. Such experiences illustrate how fragile microbiome research can become when workflows are opaque, especially in a domain already complicated by high-dimensional sequencing data and substantial biological variability.

In response to persistent inconsistencies in microbiome workflows, the Metagenomic Microbiome Combination Analysis Workflow (MMCAW) was developed as a reproducible, modular framework. Built in Snakemake (Mölder *et al.*, 2021), MMCAW integrated multiple taxonomic classifiers, BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2 (Altschul *et al.*, 1990; von Meijenfeldt *et al.*,

2019; Wood *et al.*, 2019), while embedding reproducibility safeguards such as environment control via Conda, provenance tracking of every analytical step, automated archiving of configuration files, and modularity for tool substitution. By combining complementary assigners, the workflow reduced ambiguity in taxonomic calls, and its standardized, well-documented structure enabled consistent execution and clear interpretation across datasets and computing platforms, supporting both reproducibility and accessibility of the analytical process. Importantly, MMCAW demonstrated that reproducibility can be deliberately engineered into microbiome workflows rather than retrofitted, creating stable and transparent pipelines that support both robust discovery and eventual translation.

Building on the reproducibility standards established in MMCAW, the Adaptive Sequencing Analysis Workflow (ASAW) was designed in Chapter 3 to extend those principles into adaptive sequencing experiments. Constructed in Snakemake and deployed on high-performance computing infrastructure, ASAW preserved environment control, provenance capture, and modular design, enabling host depletion experiments to be rerun and compared with full transparency. These safeguards were essential for evaluating adaptive sequencing, where methodological novelty often outpaces best practices. Host depletion results underscored the value of this approach in that adaptive sequencing reduced human reads by roughly half and increased microbial diversity, producing more stable profiles for downstream analysis. By ensuring that these outcomes were reproducible across runs, ASAW illustrated how adaptive sequencing both depends on and strengthens reproducibility, since selective depletion reduces technical noise and improves consistency of microbial signals.

ASAW was applied further into adaptive detection workflows focused on clinically relevant targets in Chapter 4. Selective enrichment of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes required not only sequencing innovation but also computational pipelines that consistently reproduced identifications across sample types. Incorporating the same safeguards, environmental standardization, transparent archiving, and consensus-based decision rules, ensured that enrichment outcomes were not idiosyncratic but verifiable. Demonstrations of reproducible enrichment of *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and resistance determinants in skin and peri-wound swabs illustrated how methodological rigor allows adaptive sequencing to move from proof-of-concept toward translational relevance. Only by embedding reproducibility can innovative sequencing methods evolve into reliable, operational practices for broader use.

5.0.2 Embedding reproducibility as an operational practice in sequencing

The progression from workflow development to adaptive sequencing underscores reproducibility as the principle that stabilizes microbiome research and enables methodological

advances to be meaningfully tested. As shown in Chapter 2, replication failures highlighted how environment control, provenance tracking, and modular architecture transform fragile, fragmented pipelines into infrastructures that support consistent evaluation. This is a prime example of how without such safeguards, host DNA depletion experiments in skin microbiome studies risk becoming anecdotal, dependent on hidden software or parameter variation. Transparent, rerunnable workflows instead enabled systematic benchmarking of adaptive sequencing, generating outcomes that could be validated across datasets and computing environments. Broader metagenomic research similarly emphasizes that reproducibility is central not only to credibility but also to scalability, with inadequate documentation and environment capture identified as key barriers to reliable inference (Grüning *et al.*, 2018; Mangul *et al.*, 2019; Sandve *et al.*, 2013).

Studies in human gut metagenomics and environmental microbiomes alike show that robust workflow design is critical for comparability across laboratories and for cumulative research progress (Pasolli *et al.*, 2017; Prodan *et al.*, 2020). Reproducibility safeguards also shaped adaptive detection workflows, where consistency is even more critical. Pathogen enrichment and antimicrobial resistance profiling require pipelines that remain stable across input variation and sequencing conditions. Embedding reproducible design features throughout Chapters 3 and 4 ensured that enrichment outcomes could be evaluated as methodological innovations rather than isolated demonstrations. Importantly, adaptive sequencing did not only rely on reproducible workflows; by selectively rejecting host DNA and redirecting effort to informative reads, it improved reproducibility itself, producing more reliable microbial detection in low-biomass, host-dominated contexts.

Similar patterns have been noted in cancer genomics and viral outbreak surveillance, where adaptive approaches combined with reproducible workflows reduced noise and stabilized outputs (Loose *et al.*, 2016; Payne *et al.*, 2021; Lin *et al.*, 2022). This dual role illustrates how technical novelty and methodological rigor can reinforce each other when reproducibility is deliberately embedded. Transforming reproducibility from an abstract ideal into operational practice required concrete mechanisms of accountability. Modular design, transparent versioning, explicit provenance capture, and systematic archiving enabled not only replication but also innovation, supporting comparative evaluations of depletion and enrichment strategies. These design choices shifted sequencing pipelines away from ad hoc implementations toward infrastructures capable of supporting long-term, cumulative inquiry.

Standardization initiatives in other areas of metagenomics underscore this trajectory, such as viral genomics which has been reshaped by reproducible pipelines such as nf-core/viralrecon, while large-scale gut microbiome studies rely on transparent, version-

controlled workflows to achieve comparability across cohorts and institutions (Ewels *et al.*, 2020; Almeida *et al.*, 2021). Within skin microbiome research, the operationalization of reproducibility principles proved particularly consequential. High host DNA content and biological variability amplify irreproducibility risks, making stable workflows essential for generating interpretable results. Provenance-enabled tracking of computational lineage further strengthened interpretability, ensuring that results could be traced, audited, and reused with confidence.

Equally important, these design features improved the clarity and accessibility of the workflows themselves, demonstrating that reproducibility depends not only on technical control but also on how methods are communicated and understood in practice. Experiences from Chapter 2 highlighted that even well-designed analyses become effectively irreproducible when key details are ambiguously reported, reinforcing the need for workflows that are both transparent and readily interpretable. By embedding reproducibility at every stage, microbiome research can be anchored in reliable and cumulative science and provide the conditions for methodological and translational advance. That foundation makes it possible to evaluate adaptive sequencing not as a novelty, but as a methodological shift with the potential to redefine how metagenomic data are generated.

5.1 Adaptive sequencing innovation

Adaptive sequencing marks a methodological shift in metagenomics, and with it, a conceptual reframing of sequencing as an active, goal-directed process rather than a passive act of data capture (Payne *et al.*, 2021). Conventional sequencing often yields datasets dominated by host DNA, requiring heavy downstream filtering and limiting reproducibility (Byrd *et al.*, 2018). By contrast, adaptive methods intervene during sequencing itself, rejecting or enriching molecules in real time according to predefined criteria. This active alignment of data generation with analytical aims transforms sequencing from passive recorder to strategic tool (Jain *et al.*, 2018; Loose *et al.*, 2016). Applied across contexts, including host depletion in skin microbiome profiling, optimization of parameters for complex communities, and enrichment of pathogens and resistance genes, adaptive sequencing demonstrated not an adjunct to existing workflows, but a new investigative mode that expands efficiency, reliability, and interpretability in microbiome research.

5.1.1 Advances in adaptive sequencing through reproducible workflows

The transformative potential of adaptive sequencing could only be evaluated against a stable, reproducible foundation. As shown in Chapter 2, workflows that enforced controlled

software environments, explicit provenance, modular design, and consensus-based taxonomic assignment created the conditions to separate genuine methodological gains from artefacts of version drift or undocumented parameters. Equally critical was consistency in wet-lab procedures, where sample processing, DNA extraction, and library preparation followed protocols refined during prior reproducibility assessments. These safeguards minimized laboratory-driven variability and ensured that downstream signals reflected biological or methodological effects rather than batch artefacts (Sinha *et al.*, 2017). Absent such scaffolding, improvements in host depletion, microbial diversity recovery, or pathogen enrichment would have been vulnerable to dismissal as pipeline idiosyncrasies rather than substantive advances.

With reproducible workflows, adaptive sequencing could be interrogated as an innovation in its own right in Chapter 3, and its effects attributed with confidence to the method rather than to confounding variability. Applied to the skin microbiome, adaptive depletion addressed the defining obstacle of overwhelming human DNA in low-yield samples. Real-time rejection of host reads reduced human contamination by ~50%, increasing microbial read depth and improving both diversity and evenness without distorting overall community structure. Crucially, these gains were delivered within reproducible workflows, enabling transparent reruns, like-for-like comparisons with control runs, and reliable cross-dataset evaluation. Optimization of basecalling and software configurations demonstrated that performance could be sustained on standard desktop systems as well as on high-performance infrastructure, lowering barriers to adoption and supporting consistent practice across laboratories with different resource profiles.

Adaptive sequencing showed greater utility when extended from depletion to dual-purpose selection. As described in Chapter 4, in defined communities and peri-wound swabs, targeted enrichment increased recovery of clinically important *S. aureus* and *E. coli* strains and improved detection of antimicrobial resistance genes, while preserving representation of the wider community. The resulting readouts were more informative with less host noise, clearer pathogen signals, and resistance profiles with greater interpretability for downstream analyses. Because these outcomes were generated within the same reproducible framework, environment control, provenance, modular integration of taxonomic and functional assigners, they could be replicated, audited, and fairly compared across runs and sample types.

In this configuration, reproducibility and adaptivity are mutually reinforcing. Reproducible design enables fair testing and reliable attribution of effect; selective sequencing, by directing effort toward informative molecules and away from human DNA,

improves the consistency of microbial signal recovery across runs and settings. Collectively they shift metagenomic practice from ad hoc experimentation toward standardized, evaluable methodology with depletion becoming quantifiable rather than anecdotal and enrichment becoming a calibrated intervention rather than a one-off success. This interdependence clarifies the trajectory for subsequent sections, a reproducible infrastructure makes it possible to optimize adaptive parameters, quantify trade-offs, and generalize findings, while adaptive control over data generation strengthens the repeatability and interpretability of skin microbiome analyses.

5.1.2 Adaptive sequencing as flexible and accessible microbiome approach

Adaptive sequencing therefore emerges as a flexible framework, moving from host depletion toward targeted enrichment and demonstrating how the same technology can be applied to distinct objectives within microbiome research. Reliable reduction of host DNA in Chapter 3 established the groundwork for enrichment by stabilizing downstream analyses and minimizing confounding noise, showing that selective capture of microbial sequences can be achieved with technical rigor. Once depletion was operationalized, enrichment of pathogens and resistance genes became both technically feasible and efficient, including on compact, low-cost devices such as the Flongle. This stepwise expansion illustrates adaptive sequencing as a flexible strategy that can be tailored to the constraints of low-biomass skin samples, scaled to more complex communities, or directed toward clinically relevant targets.

Importantly, as Chapter 4 demonstrates, the versatility of adaptive sequencing positions it not only as a refinement of sequencing practice but as a framework capable of supporting diverse investigative and translational priorities. Similar conclusions have been drawn in studies applying adaptive sequencing to viromes (Lin *et al.*, 2022) and plasmid recovery (Payne *et al.*, 2021), reinforcing its potential as a versatile method across microbial systems. A parallel emphasis has been placed on accessibility, with demonstrations of effective host depletion and enrichment on standard desktop systems showing that the approach is not confined to laboratories with extensive computational resources. Integration into reproducible, modular workflows described in Chapter 2 ensured that outcomes could be validated across datasets and environments, addressing long-standing reproducibility challenges that have hindered adoption of new methods in microbiome science.

This convergence of feasibility, transparency, and affordability highlights adaptive sequencing as a realistic option for laboratories aiming to generate robust results without reliance on high-performance infrastructure. Broader work has emphasized that portability and cost-effectiveness are key determinants for uptake in resource-limited settings (Boykin

et al., 2018; Oehler *et al.*, 2023), and adaptive sequencing aligns with these priorities by combining technical selectivity with operational accessibility. While challenges remain, such as reliance on comprehensive and up-to-date reference databases, computational latency in real-time mapping, and risks of misclassification in repetitive genomic regions (McIntyre *et al.*, 2017; Maranga *et al.*, 2023), the direction of travel in the field is clear.

Algorithmic refinements, the development of curated pangenomic and antimicrobial resistance resources, and steady declines in sequencing costs are reducing barriers for future applications (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022; Maranga *et al.*, 2023; Hewel *et al.*, 2024). Adaptive sequencing therefore represents not a static method but a rapidly evolving approach that benefits from, and contributes to, broader advances in sequencing technology and informatics (Yuen *et al.*, 2024; Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Kovaka *et al.*, 2021). In this context, reproducibility, host depletion, and targeted enrichment are not isolated demonstrations but sequential steps in a coherent progression. Each stage strengthens the reliability, interpretability, and utility of microbiome sequencing, collectively illustrating how adaptive approaches can extend the field beyond descriptive profiling toward targeted, goal-oriented analyses with translational relevance.

5.2 Skin microbiome applications

The skin microbiome exemplifies why such adaptive strategies are needed, as it is among the most technically demanding to characterise. Communities differ markedly across individuals and sites, shaped by physiology, environment, and transient colonisation, complicating efforts to define consistent taxonomic or functional baselines (Zielińska *et al.*, 2023; Gilbert *et al.*, 2018). Low microbial biomass further constrains analysis, as host DNA typically overwhelms microbial reads, reducing sequencing efficiency and obscuring signals (Selway *et al.*, 2020; Martin *et al.*, 2022). Adaptive sequencing mitigated this barrier by selectively depleting host content, increasing microbial depth and diversity without distorting community structure. Downstream interpretation, however, remains restricted by incomplete reference databases and variable annotation, challenges that reproducible workflows help to stabilise (Nayfach *et al.*, 2021; Almeida *et al.*, 2021). These biological and computational obstacles explain why skin microbiome sequencing has been slow to gain clinical translation but also highlight why it serves as a crucial proving ground for methodological innovation.

5.2.1 Integrating reproducibility and adaptivity to overcome skin barriers

Addressing the challenges of skin microbiome analysis required establishing a reliable analytical foundation capable of mitigating variability and ensuring interpretability. The development of MMCAW in Chapter 2 addressed these challenges by embedding environment control, provenance tracking, and archiving into a modular framework. A central feature was its consensus-based taxonomic strategy, which combined outputs from BLAST, CAT, and Kraken2 to mitigate the algorithmic inconsistencies that often undermine microbial profiling. This integration yielded more reliable species- and genus-level assignments, directly confronting the limited resolution that has constrained skin microbiome studies. Consensus classification has been increasingly recognized as a critical safeguard for accuracy in metagenomics, particularly where clinical interpretation may hinge on subtle taxonomic distinctions (McIntyre *et al.*, 2017; Meyer *et al.*, 2019).

Consequently, workflow design emerged as a determinant of biological credibility rather than a neutral technical choice, establishing a foundation upon which skin microbiome sequencing could progress toward clinically meaningful applications (Sinha *et al.*, 2017; Zielińska *et al.*, 2023). As shown in Chapter 3, adaptive sequencing extended this foundation by targeting one of the field's most persistent obstacles, human DNA dominance. Its first application to skin samples reduced host reads by approximately half, reallocating sequencing effort toward microbial content and improving both diversity and evenness without distorting community composition. The resulting datasets offered a more faithful representation of skin-associated taxa while reducing computational burden. Notably, these experiments were executed on standard desktop systems, lowering barriers to adoption and aligning with the practical realities of many laboratories.

Accessibility is particularly relevant for clinical translation, where solutions must be affordable, reproducible, and capable of scaling across diverse research and healthcare environments (Loose *et al.*, 2016). By coupling host depletion with reproducibility safeguards, adaptive sequencing transformed skin samples once considered analytically marginal into datasets suitable for systematic investigation, advancing the field toward diagnostic applicability (Martin *et al.*, 2022). The trajectory from host depletion to targeted enrichment in Chapter 4 demonstrated adaptive sequencing's capacity not only to alleviate technical barriers but also to deliver clinically relevant outputs. By uniting real-time rejection of human reads with enrichment of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes, the method enabled sensitive recovery of organisms, such as *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, directly from peri-wound swabs, alongside improved resolution of resistance determinants.

Overall, enrichment preserved the integrity of broader microbial communities, ensuring that ecological context was not sacrificed in pursuit of clinical signals. This dual functionality, enhancing pathogen detection while retaining community-level insight, aligns with the needs of infection surveillance and antimicrobial stewardship, where clinicians require both focused, actionable results and an understanding of broader microbial interactions (Didelot *et al.*, 2012; Hendriksen *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, the modifiable nature of adaptive sequencing parameters allows protocols to be tuned for different diagnostic priorities, positioning it as a versatile bridge between exploratory research and translational medicine.

5.2.2 From reproducibility toward clinical utility in skin microbiomes

Skin microbiome sequencing has long struggled to achieve clinical credibility, constrained by variability in sampling, overwhelming host DNA, and fragmented analytical practices (Byrd *et al.*, 2018; Vries *et al.*, 2022). As demonstrated in Chapter 2, reproducibility frameworks such as environment control, provenance tracking, and consensus-based classification directly addressed these issues, establishing conditions under which methodological advances could be evaluated with confidence. The importance of such rigor has been widely emphasized across microbiome and genomics fields, where reproducibility failures have undermined claims of clinical relevance (Mangul *et al.*, 2019; Lauder *et al.*, 2016). By embedding reproducibility into workflows, skin microbiome sequencing can progress from exploratory profiling to a domain capable of informing translational research.

Within this stabilized framework, adaptive sequencing provided an avenue to tackle skin-specific challenges while generating outputs of potential diagnostic value. The ability to reject host sequences in real time not only improved microbial recovery but also reduced the computational burden of downstream analyses, an important consideration for clinical deployment. Comparable benefits have been observed in other low-biomass contexts, where depletion strategies enhanced pathogen recovery and reduced false negatives (Eisenhofer *et al.*, 2019; Fierer *et al.*, 2025). For skin and wound samples, such improvements translate into clearer baselines for identifying clinically meaningful shifts in microbial communities.

Selective enrichment of pathogens and resistance genes extended this progress in Chapter 4, aligning data generation with pressing clinical concerns. Detecting *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and resistance determinants directly from wound-associated samples demonstrated that metagenomic sequencing can approach the sensitivity required for infection monitoring. This dual focus, targeted outputs combined with preserved ecological context, addresses the dual clinical need for actionable diagnostics and holistic understanding of wound microbiota (Liu

et al., 2020; Loesche *et al.*, 2017). In antimicrobial stewardship, where accurate detection of resistance genes informs treatment strategies, adaptive sequencing illustrates how real-time selection can enhance both speed and interpretability (Payne *et al.*, 2021).

Equally significant is the accessibility of these methods. Demonstrating feasibility on standard desktop systems and low-cost flow cells reduces the reliance on specialized infrastructures that have historically limited adoption. This aligns with broader efforts to democratize sequencing technologies and move toward portable, cost-effective diagnostic tools (Ewels *et al.*, 2020). For skin microbiome applications, accessibility is not peripheral, it determines whether methods remain academic prototypes or evolve into clinically integrated workflows. Ultimately, reproducibility and adaptive sequencing converge to reposition skin microbiome sequencing as a system with tangible clinical potential.

Clinical utility here is not claimed as an achieved outcome but framed as a credible trajectory with rigorous frameworks ensure reliability and adaptive methods expand interpretability. While further validation and scaling will be required, the findings point to a future in which skin microbiome sequencing contributes directly to diagnostic pipelines. By demonstrating a pathway from methodological rigor to translational promise, the work establishes skin microbiome research as a credible arena for precision approaches that were previously regarded as unattainable.

5.3 Limitations and opportunities

Positioning skin microbiome sequencing as a system with clinical potential also makes its constraints more apparent. The very features that complicate translation, including low microbial biomass, host dominance, and high variability, create persistent methodological challenges (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Johnson *et al.*, 2019; Callahan *et al.*, 2016). These difficulties are compounded by the rapid evolution of adaptive sequencing technologies, where software instability and incomplete reference resources remain limiting factors. Such constraints are not unique to this work but reflect obstacles encountered across microbiome science more broadly (Kovaka *et al.*, 2021; Meyer *et al.*, 2019). Yet acknowledging them is essential because they define where progress is most urgently needed and where methodological gains will have the greatest impact. In this way, limitations define the path for adaptive sequencing to move from proof-of-concept to routine diagnostic use.

5.3.1 Constraints shaping the scope and generalisability of findings

The progression toward greater application in this thesis was shaped by study-level limitations specific to the work presented here, which defined both the scope of analyses and

the strength of resulting conclusions. As discussed in Chapter 2, workflow reproducibility was evaluated through partial replications of two published datasets (Afshinnekoo *et al.*, 2015; Kang *et al.*, 2018) and small-scale sample batches, as realistic time and computational limits prevented broader validation. These demonstrations confirmed feasibility within the present research context but left questions about robustness across larger or more diverse cohorts. Additional limitations stemmed from reliance on the GRCh38 human reference for filtering in Chapter 3, which contains mosaic regions and microbial inclusions that risk misclassification. Although the more complete T2T-CHM13 assembly could mitigate these issues (Hugerth and Andersson, 2017; Almeida *et al.*, 2021), its computational demands made it impractical for live adaptive workflows under the conditions of this study.

Database reliance presented another constraint throughout the thesis, as consensus-based assigners reduced algorithmic variability, but outcomes remained limited by incomplete or inconsistently curated taxonomies (Gosalbes *et al.*, 2012; Ceccarani and Severgnini, 2023). Because classification, enrichment, and resistance detection all depended on reference quality, gaps in coverage constrained interpretability throughout the analyses conducted here. The scope was also restricted to DNA-based metagenomics. Integrating metatranscriptomics, metabolomics, or proteomics could have provided functional insight into host–microbe interactions (Franzosa *et al.*, 2018; Hasin *et al.*, 2017), but available resources limited the study to a single data layer. Similar methodological gaps have been reported elsewhere, narrowing biological interpretation (Franzosa *et al.*, 2018).

Additional limitations were associated with the mock microbial communities used during method development and optimisation. The ATCC oral microbiome DNA standard provided a controlled and reproducible system for evaluating sequencing performance, adaptive enrichment behaviour, and bioinformatic workflows independent of variability introduced during culture and DNA extraction as discussed in [Subsection 1.9.1](#) (Bokulich *et al.*, 2016; Nearing *et al.*, 2022); however, the mock community contained species at equal abundance, unlike the highly asymmetrical distributions typically observed in real microbiome samples, where dominant taxa coexist with low-abundance organisms (Amos *et al.*, 2020). In addition, no commercially available skin microbiome metagenomic DNA standards were available at the time of this study, requiring use of an oral microbiome reference community with limited overlap with skin-associated taxa. Future studies would benefit from more complex mock communities incorporating uneven abundance distributions, clinically relevant organisms, and extraction-derived variability to better reflect real-world microbiome conditions.

Adaptive sequencing introduced additional, study-specific challenges. Host depletion experiments used ReadFish and ONT's in-house software, as computational limits precluded implementation of faster rejection tools such as ReadBouncer (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Ulrich *et al.*, 2022); therefore, Minimap2-based alignment slowed rejection decisions, constraining efficiency under experimental conditions. Additionally, Flongle flow cells enabled cost-effective and desktop-compatible optimisation but offered limited throughput compared to MinION, restricting achievable sequencing depth (Lin *et al.*, 2023). Depletion was also incomplete, with human DNA persisting despite substantial reductions. As shown in Chapter 4, targeted enrichment highlighted further limitations encountered during this research. ReadFish required extensive optimisation and GPU support, complicating portability. It also is a great example of the broader issues associated with reference-based enrichment, reflected database biases and efficiency varied by species and read length.

Gains were minimal in some contexts, particularly in *Pseudomonas*-dominated samples sequenced with R9.4.1 chemistry, which is known to underperform for this organism (Quick *et al.*, 2016). Antimicrobial resistance profiling was likewise constrained, with plasmid- and mobile-element genes underrepresented due to recovery and alignment challenges. Finally, small sample sizes, especially peri-wound swabs, restricted validation power and limited generalisability across patient populations (Martin, 2019; Kashyap *et al.*, 2017). Collectively, these study-specific constraints delineate the practical boundaries within which the methodological advances of this thesis were tested, providing clear targets for refinement in future work.

5.3.2 Technical, biological, and translational constraints at the field level

At the field level, microbiome and adaptive sequencing research remains shaped by technical, biological, and structural constraints that extend well beyond the boundaries of individual studies. These limitations represent systemic challenges across the discipline, influencing how reliability, comparability, and clinical relevance are achieved in practice. On the technical side, nanopore sequencing continues to face field-wide challenges linked to pore chemistry, variable flow cell performance, and dependence on high-performance GPUs for adaptive basecalling and mapping (Martin *et al.*, 2022; Langmead and Salzberg, 2012; Satam *et al.*, 2023). Short read lengths remain prone to misclassification, while longer reads improve accuracy but reduce throughput. Although newer chemistries promise improved stability and lower error rates, sequencing variability still limits comparability across studies and complicates standardisation (Olm *et al.*, 2020; Quick *et al.*, 2016).

Biological heterogeneity further compounds these issues and remains a defining limitation across microbiome research. The skin microbiome, as one of the lowest-biomass and most host-contaminated niches, exemplifies the difficulty of establishing reproducible baselines that apply broadly across contexts. Substantial variation across body sites, individuals, and clinical settings restricts generalisability and undermines the translation of mock-community benchmarks into real-world samples (Bokulich *et al.*, 2016; Lloréns-Rico *et al.*, 2021; Nearing *et al.*, 2022). Beyond intra-study variation, progress across the field also depends on methodological standardisation between laboratories, where reproducible workflows must be validated on different platforms and under diverse environmental and clinical conditions rather than confined to proof-of-concept demonstrations. The inability to consistently harmonise methods across such heterogeneous systems remains a persistent limitation in microbiome research, despite advances in depletion and enrichment strategies (Morsli *et al.*, 2024).

Data and informatics add a third axis of constraint that affects the field at large. Reliance on incomplete and unevenly curated reference databases restricts taxonomic and functional resolution, particularly for non-model organisms and antimicrobial resistance genes (Gosalbes *et al.*, 2012). Frequent database updates improve coverage but alter baselines, reducing reproducibility across time (Maranga *et al.*, 2023). Moreover, metadata standards remain inconsistent, often lacking integration of clinical or environmental context, which further undermines cross-study comparability (Cernava *et al.*, 2022; Yilmaz *et al.*, 2011). Ethical concerns also persist across the discipline, as human-derived metagenomic datasets raise unresolved challenges of privacy, identifiability, and consent in both clinical and longitudinal settings (Fricker *et al.*, 2019; Wang *et al.*, 2025).

Taken together, these field-level constraints place microbiome and adaptive sequencing research in a transitional stage, where technical, biological, and informatic hurdles still temper progress (Amos *et al.*, 2020). Furthering the discipline will require advances in sequencing hardware, curated references, and consistent metadata standards (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016; Schloss, 2018; Quince *et al.*, 2017). Yet the identification of these limitations is not a critique of individual studies but a shared roadmap for collective progress. By clarifying where barriers persist, the field also reveals the strengths and strategies already emerging to address them.

5.3.3 Operational strengths and strategies for addressing limitations

A balanced appraisal of limitations must also recognise the strengths and design choices that shaped this research. Chief among these was the deliberate embedding of

reproducibility throughout all chapters, not as an abstract principle but as an operational framework. Modular workflows, controlled environments, and comprehensive provenance tracking ensured that analyses were consistently interpretable rather than ad hoc, providing the necessary foundation on which adaptive sequencing could be rigorously evaluated. The interdisciplinary scope, integrating wet-lab experimentation, computational optimisation, and clinically oriented applications, further reinforced this foundation by bridging domains that are often siloed, allowing technical advances to be tested in contexts with direct translational significance.

Several anticipated obstacles were mitigated through proactive strategies. Demonstrating feasibility on standard desktop hardware addressed computational barriers that often restrict adaptive sequencing to high-performance clusters, lowering the threshold for adoption in typical research environments. Chapter 2 demonstrated that workflow transparency, modularity, and clear documentation counters the opacity that frequently impedes replication in metagenomics (Langmead and Salzberg, 2012; Huttenhower *et al.*, 2012; Ewels *et al.*, 2020) and offers a template that others can extend. These measures did not eliminate constraints but ensured that within the boundaries of scope and resources, the outcomes remained robust, transparent, and transferable. Equally important is the recognition that many limitations identified here reflect the structural realities of the broader field rather than shortcomings unique to this work.

Dependence on evolving reference databases, variability across sequencing platforms, and the restricted size of most cohorts all shape current microbiome and adaptive sequencing research (Nearing *et al.*, 2021; Ziemann *et al.*, 2023; Payne *et al.*, 2021). Addressing them requires collective progress, but engaging with them directly situates this research within the forward momentum of the discipline. Seen in this light, limitations become markers of growth rather than signs of weakness. Their explicit acknowledgment highlights both the advances achieved, particularly in reproducibility and methodological accessibility, and the opportunities for refinement that will define the next phase of microbiome science. This dual perspective provides a foundation for future directions, where operational strengths can be leveraged to systematically close the gaps that still constrain translation.

The practical value of the methods developed in this thesis lies in their applicability across both research and clinical contexts. In research, adaptive sequencing provides a flexible and scalable framework for high-resolution analysis of microbial communities, supporting detailed investigation of microbial dynamics, antimicrobial resistance, and host–microbe interactions. In clinical settings, it enables real-time, sample-directed sequencing that can

prioritise clinically relevant organisms and resistance markers, creating opportunities for faster, more targeted interpretation of complex metagenomic data in time-sensitive scenarios. While interpretation requires careful consideration of factors such as colonisation versus infection and the clinical relevance of detected resistance genes, adaptive sequencing offers a powerful approach to enhancing diagnostic insight. As an enabling technology, it complements existing workflows while expanding the scope and precision of microbial detection. These applications and their associated considerations are explored further in Sections 5.5 and 5.6, where future research directions and pathways to clinical translation are discussed.

5.4 Future directions in research

The trajectory of this research illustrates how reproducibility, adaptive methodology, and clinical orientation can be integrated to advance microbiome science. Establishing reproducible workflows addressed barriers that had long undermined comparability, while adaptive sequencing demonstrated the technical feasibility of host depletion and targeted enrichment. Extending these approaches to proof-of-concept diagnostics positioned the skin microbiome as a tractable system with translational potential. From this foundation, future directions emerge, including refining workflows for greater scalability, validating across larger and more diverse cohorts, and expanding reference resources to improve accuracy and interpretability. By framing limitations not as endpoints but as starting points for innovation, the pathway forward builds directly upon the contributions of this work, moving from experimental feasibility toward clinical utility and, ultimately, a re-shaping of how metagenomics informs medicine.

5.4.1 Next steps in workflows, host depletion, and adaptive detection

Progress in this field depends on consolidating recent advances into more flexible and comprehensive pipelines. Expanding workflow capability is a priority, while MMCAW established reproducibility for taxonomic profiling in Chapter 2, extending it to functional inference would enable stronger links between microbial composition and biological activity. Incorporating classifiers such as PhyloPhlAn or Sourmash (Garrido-Oter *et al.*, 2018; Rausch *et al.*, 2019), alongside curated resources from RefSeq, GTDB, and growing metagenome-assembled genome catalogues, would substantially improve accuracy and comparability (Parks *et al.*, 2018; Quast *et al.*, 2013). Refinement of host read filtering also remains important. Adoption of complete human assemblies such as T2T-CHM13 could reduce

residual human DNA and sharpen microbial resolution, though computational demands must be carefully managed (Almeida *et al.*, 2021).

On the adaptive sequencing side, algorithmic performance continues to shape feasibility. Current mapping approaches introduce latency that constrains real-time rejection. As described in Chapter 3, hash- or k-mer-based methods such as ReadBouncer promise faster and more precise decision-making but require systematic benchmarking across species and contexts (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Ulrich *et al.*, 2022). Host depletion may also benefit from hybrid strategies, combining adaptive approaches with selective enzymatic removal to maximise microbial recovery while limiting bias (Ganda *et al.*, 2021; Wang *et al.*, 2025). Scaling beyond Flongle flow cells would increase throughput for large studies, yet ongoing optimisation of portable platforms remains equally important, particularly with new nanopore chemistries offering improved speed and accuracy (Lin *et al.*, 2023).

The adaptive detection of pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes in Chapter 4 will also require progress at both reference and computational levels. Expanded datasets of plasmids and mobile genetic elements could strengthen ARG recovery, while curated pangenome-based references and updates to resources such as CARD would mitigate uneven coverage (Alcock *et al.*, 2023). Advances in GPU optimisation, mapper efficiency, and response time will further improve the accuracy and stability of real-time enrichment (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Ulrich *et al.*, 2022). Collectively, these refinements define the next phase of development, such as expanding workflows to incorporate functional capacity, refining host depletion strategies, and optimising adaptive enrichment for pathogens and resistance genes. Pursued in combination, they provide the foundation for broader validation efforts and standardisation across laboratories, enabling progress toward more generalisable and scalable microbiome research.

5.4.2 Integrating multi-omics and comparative standards for broader use

Progress at the next stage depends on scaling methodological advances into larger and more heterogeneous contexts. Cohort expansion is central because workflows demonstrated on small datasets must be validated across multi-site, clinically diverse populations (Bowers *et al.*, 2017; Knight *et al.*, 2018), particularly in wound microbiomes where variability in aetiology, comorbidities, and treatment practices strongly shapes microbial composition (Smythe and Wilkinson, 2023; Forry *et al.*, 2024). Benchmarking across independent laboratories would further establish reproducibility and generalisability, addressing concerns that outcomes may be driven by site-specific protocols or computational environments rather than underlying biology (Moossavi *et al.*, 2021; Ziemann *et al.*, 2023). An

additional frontier lies in multi-omics integration. While metagenomics provides comprehensive taxonomic and resistome profiling, complementary layers such as metatranscriptomics, metabolomics, and proteomics capture microbial activity, metabolic output, and host–microbe interactions (Huttenhower *et al.*, 2012; Morsli *et al.*, 2024; Zhang *et al.*, 2019).

Studies have shown, for instance, that integrating metagenomics with metatranscriptomics clarifies the gap between microbial potential and realised function, while metabolomic coupling links microbial signatures to inflammatory states (Martin, 2019). These approaches are increasingly recognised as essential for clinical translation, but demand reproducible, standardised workflows capable of managing heterogeneous data types without eroding comparability (Chetty and Blekman, 2024). Advances in metadata harmonisation and interoperable formats will be crucial to ensure that multi-omics pipelines remain both powerful and sustainable across contexts (Quince *et al.*, 2017; Meyer *et al.*, 2022). Comparative evaluation against existing diagnostic standards also represents a necessary step. Adaptive sequencing must be benchmarked in organised studies alongside culture, PCR assays, and multiplex panels such as BioFire, with systematic attention to sensitivity, specificity, turnaround time, and cost-effectiveness.

Without structured assessment, novel methods cannot be realistically situated within diagnostic pathways or evaluated for their true translational impact (Yang *et al.*, 2022; Austin, 2021). Additionally, progress will hinge on software and algorithmic refinement. Greater efficiency in live read classification, potentially accelerated by machine-learning models, could improve both speed and accuracy (Ulrich *et al.*, 2022). Equally important are portability and usability, since current adaptive sequencing tools often require complex installation and high computational expertise, limiting adoption (Nakamura *et al.*, 2024). Streamlined, user-friendly platforms will be essential to broaden uptake, ensuring that methodological advances extend beyond proof-of-concept demonstrations toward consistent application across laboratories and clinical environments (Lin *et al.*, 2023; Patel *et al.*, 2022).

5.4.3 Future potential of adaptive sequencing in research and diagnostics

Looking further ahead, the trajectory of metagenomics and adaptive sequencing points toward a broader transformation in microbiome science and bioinformatics. Central to this horizon is the development of next-generation reference frameworks. Adoption of human pangenomes for host depletion would reduce biases tied to single linear assemblies, while comprehensive repositories of antimicrobial resistance genes, plasmids, and mobile elements could sharpen detection of clinically and ecologically significant features (Hugerth

and Andersson, 2017; Almeida *et al.*, 2021). On a wider scale, globally coordinated microbial reference catalogues would provide the foundation for standardised comparative metagenomics, enabling cross-study synthesis and advancing both basic and translational research (Nayfach *et al.*, 2021; Forry *et al.*, 2024).

Realising this vision will depend on parallel algorithmic advances. Ultra-fast classifiers based on k-mer hashing or machine learning could accelerate live sequencing decisions, while AI-driven pipelines might eventually manage read rejection, target prioritisation, and sequencing sufficiency autonomously (Ulrich *et al.*, 2024; Noé *et al.*, 2020; Bepler and Berger, 2021). Coupled with improvements in pore chemistry and hardware stability, such developments would shift adaptive sequencing from a technically promising tool into a mature, automated platform for both research and applied microbiology (Payne *et al.*, 2021; Kovaka *et al.*, 2021). The implications extend beyond clinical diagnostics. Enhanced reproducibility and adaptive selection would support deeper exploration of human-associated microbiomes, including gut, respiratory, and urogenital systems, and extend to environmental contexts such as soil and water, where dynamic host–microbe–environment interactions shape health and ecology (Marquet *et al.*, 2022; Nayfach *et al.*, 2021; Sansone *et al.*, 2019).

Multi-omics integration and real-time adaptive analysis could open new avenues for studying microbial function, evolutionary dynamics, and community resilience, positioning adaptive sequencing as a driver of discovery as well as application (Chetty and Blekhman, 2024; Chen *et al.*, 2023). Viewed in continuity with earlier priorities, the broader horizon is one in which reproducibility, adaptive methodology, and bioinformatic innovation converge. The ultimate outcome is not solely a clinical tool but a reimaged framework for microbiome science, one where microbial data can be generated, interpreted, and applied with unprecedented precision. Such advances hold implications from advancing basic microbial ecology to informing global health strategies, ultimately reshaping how microbial information contributes to both science and human wellbeing.

5.5 Clinical translation implications

Moving from broad trajectories of methodological development to the immediate question of clinical relevance requires narrowing the focus to how advances demonstrated here could translate into practice. The studies in this thesis show that reproducible workflows and adaptive sequencing can be applied to technically demanding niches such as the skin microbiome, reducing host interference and improving microbial signal in ways directly relevant to diagnosis. Crucially, these approaches demonstrate not only technical

feasibility but also the potential to deliver interpretable outputs in forms that could support clinical decision-making. Framed in this way, this work highlights how methodological rigor and innovation converge to create conditions under which microbiome sequencing may one day begin to inform diagnostics and infection management in realistic healthcare settings.

5.5.1 From modular workflows to proof-of-concept in wound diagnostics

The research presented throughout the chapters here demonstrates how reproducibility and adaptive sequencing can converge to create proof-of-concept diagnostic workflows for wound microbiomes. Rather than functioning as isolated technical demonstrations, reproducible pipelines and adaptive control collectively illustrate a viable pathway toward clinically relevant outputs. Achieving this, however, requires reconciling the two central imperatives, reproducibility and flexibility, in wound microbiome diagnostics. Conventional approaches such as culture, PCR, or fixed-panel assays like BioFire provide valuable information but remain constrained by their narrow scope and tendency to miss unexpected organisms or resistance elements (Clarridge, 2004; Lazarevic *et al.*, 2014).

Metagenomics offers broader coverage but has been undermined by inconsistent workflows, host contamination, and limited interpretability (Schloss, 2018; Nayfach *et al.*, 2021). By embedding reproducibility into modular pipelines and combining them with adaptive sequencing, the research throughout these chapters demonstrates a pathway where technical rigor and methodological adaptability operate in tandem to address these long-standing barriers. The skin and wound microbiomes exemplify some of the most technically demanding niches, characterised by low microbial biomass, high host DNA, and sharp variability across patients and wound types (Loesche *et al.*, 2017; Malone *et al.*, 2017). In such contexts, workflow design becomes as important as sequencing technology itself.

Consensus-based taxonomic assignment reduced algorithmic discrepancies in Chapter 2, while adaptive depletion in Chapters 3 and 4 increased microbial representation, together producing results less vulnerable to artefact or bias (Vries *et al.*, 2022; Schloss, 2018). The clinical significance lies not only in detecting pathogens such as *S. aureus* or *E. coli*, but also in maintaining ecological resolution, critical for understanding how wound communities shape infection trajectories and therapeutic outcomes (Grice and Segre, 2012). Equally important is accessibility, which is an essential consideration for scaling to clinical or resource-limited settings. Demonstrations on standard desktop systems highlight that sophisticated microbiome analyses can be achieved outside high-performance computing environments.

Beyond accessibility on standard desktop systems, broader calls for reproducible and portable workflows in diagnostic metagenomics highlight the conditions under which

adaptive approaches gain value (Ewels *et al.*, 2020). The integration of rigorous workflow design with adaptive flexibility represents more than incremental refinement; it illustrates how reproducibility can stabilize outputs while adaptive sequencing increases their relevance and interpretability and clinical relevance. In wound microbiome research, where diagnostic delays carry direct consequences (Ahmajärvi *et al.*, 2022), such strategies provide proof-of-concept for microbiome-informed diagnostics that move beyond descriptive profiles toward reproducible, targeted, and contextually rich readouts.

5.5.2 Making adaptive sequencing accessible and clinically feasible

A persistent barrier to clinical adoption of metagenomic sequencing has been the assumption that it requires high-performance computing and costly infrastructure, limiting use to specialist or reference laboratories (McIntyre *et al.*, 2017; Milanese *et al.*, 2019). Cost remains a non-trivial constraint, especially in resource-limited healthcare systems where diagnostic investments must be justified by clear evidence of cost-effectiveness (Quick *et al.*, 2016; Nakamura *et al.*, 2024). Chapters 3 and 4 demonstrated that adaptive sequencing can be performed on standard desktop hardware and low-cost flow cells, such as the Flongle, directly challenges this perception. By lowering both financial and logistical thresholds, the approach moves sequencing closer to realistic diagnostic use, particularly in wound care where rapid turnaround can determine outcomes.

The shift from centralized facilities to desktop-compatible platforms also broadens scalability. Decentralized, point-of-need sequencing could extend access beyond specialist centres to under-resourced environments, where infection burdens are often greatest (Quick *et al.*, 2016; Wang *et al.*, 2021). In this sense, accessibility is not only a technical gain but a prerequisite for equitable translation of sequencing into routine care. Early applications already demonstrate feasibility because host depletion increases microbial read depth, enhancing taxonomic resolution, while adaptive enrichment enables recovery of both pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes directly from peri-wound swabs. Importantly, these approaches preserve community-wide information, allowing pathogen detection to be contextualised within broader microbiome ecology (Loose *et al.*, 2016; Charalampous *et al.*, 2019). Despite these advances, adaptive sequencing remains positioned as proof-of-concept in clinical settings (Wang *et al.*, 2024).

As discussed in the limitations section, confidence in diagnostic integration will depend on validation in large, diverse cohorts, reproducibility across laboratories, and clear reporting standards (Schloss *et al.*, 2018; Grimes *et al.*, 2022; Yuen *et al.*, 2024). Reference databases for species and resistance determinants require continued expansion to minimise

misclassification, while interpretability must be improved through streamlined reporting tailored to clinicians and administrators (Chorlton, 2024). Training for pathologists and development of decision-support systems will be equally important for uptake (Locey and Lennon, 2016). Perhaps most critically, regulatory frameworks for sequencing-based diagnostics remain undefined, with approval pathways and quality assurance still to be established (Chiu and Miller, 2019). Positioned against these constraints, adaptive sequencing represents a promising but unfinished step being technically feasible, increasingly accessible, and clinically relevant, yet still requiring systematic validation and regulatory integration before adoption into routine diagnostics.

5.5.3 Interdisciplinary progress for microbiome science to diagnostics

The positioning of adaptive sequencing as a clinically promising technology in Chapter 4 is inseparable from the environment in which it was tested. The skin microbiome, with its low microbial biomass, high inter-individual variability, and substantial host DNA contamination, provided one of the most demanding contexts for method development as shown in Chapter 3. Meeting these challenges required workflows that were both reproducible and resilient to analytical constraints, as described in Chapter 2, establishing principles with relevance well beyond skin. The integration of transparent bioinformatics pipelines, host depletion, and adaptive enrichment creates a framework applicable to any host-associated microbiome where technical and biological noise limit diagnostic resolution.

Comparable challenges are encountered in the gut, respiratory tract, and reproductive systems. In the gut, host DNA and dietary residues obscure microbial signals, complicating efforts to monitor dysbiosis or resistance reservoirs (Wang *et al.*, 2025). Respiratory infections, such as in cystic fibrosis, illustrate how complex, polymicrobial communities and nosocomial exposure demand tools capable of profiling both pathogens and resistance determinants in real time (Zhao *et al.*, 2020). In the reproductive tract, diagnostic accuracy is undermined by strong inter-patient variability and low microbial biomass, highlighting a need for reproducible workflows that can move beyond culture-based assays (Chen *et al.*, 2020). Integrating multi-omics into these contexts would further enhance functional interpretation, advancing precision medicine strategies that adapt diagnostics to individual patients (Chen *et al.*, 2023).

The scope of application extends beyond bacteria. Adaptive frameworks can be extended to fungi, viruses, and emerging pathogens, providing flexibility to detect novel or unexpected agents that panel-based assays routinely miss. This adaptability has clear relevance for outbreak response and epidemiological surveillance, where portable nanopore

devices have already been deployed successfully in Ebola and COVID-19 (Quick *et al.*, 2016; Lin *et al.*, 2022; Bull *et al.*, 2020). In this way, the research here contributes simultaneously to microbiome bioinformatics, clinical microbiology, and translational genomics. Reproducible workflows advance methodological transparency; adaptive host depletion and enrichment overcome long-standing diagnostic bottlenecks; and desktop-compatible platforms align laboratory innovation with clinical feasibility. The strength of this trajectory lies in its interdisciplinarity, marking a substantive step toward positioning microbiome sequencing as a scalable diagnostic approach that bridges exploratory research and practical healthcare solutions.

5.6 Concluding remarks

This thesis has shown how methodological design can transform skin microbiome sequencing from a technically difficult pursuit into a framework with genuine translational potential. The starting point was the recognition that reproducibility is not an auxiliary feature but the foundation of credible analysis. By embedding modularity, provenance tracking, and consensus-driven taxonomic strategies, workflows were developed that directly addressed long-standing problems of inconsistency and interpretability in microbiome research. Establishing this methodological bedrock was essential because without reliability, neither innovation nor translation can hold. Building on this foundation, adaptive sequencing was introduced as a means to overcome the dominant technical barrier in skin microbiomes, the overwhelming presence of host DNA.

Demonstrations of host depletion on standard desktop systems and low-cost platforms illustrated that adaptive sequencing is not confined to high-resource laboratories but can be accessible, scalable, and practical. The methodological pivot from passive sequencing to real-time, goal-oriented control redefined what sequencing can accomplish, opening possibilities for both deeper microbial characterisation and targeted detection. The progression culminated in proof-of-concept applications where adaptive sequencing selectively enriched pathogens and antimicrobial resistance genes directly from peri-wound swabs. In this setting, the approach revealed not only technical feasibility but clinical promise in the possibility of diagnostic readouts that retain ecological breadth while capturing features central to infection management.

Crucially, the advances here were not isolated results but the outcome of integration, reproducible workflows enabling reliable testing, adaptive methods providing targeted resolution, and clinical framing ensuring relevance. Together they chart a pathway for how microbiome science can evolve into a diagnostic platform. Limitations inevitably shaped this

trajectory. Constraints in database completeness, computational efficiency, and cohort size restricted both validation and generalisability. Yet these limitations also highlight where progress will be most impactful, such as refining host references, standardising protocols across laboratories, and integrating multi-omics to capture microbial function alongside composition. The recognition of such boundaries should not be seen as diminishing the findings but as delineating the frontier where innovation is needed.

By showing that reproducibility can stabilise outputs, that adaptive sequencing can be deployed on accessible hardware, and that clinically relevant signals can be recovered directly from complex samples, this thesis establishes a practical framework for future development. The implications here extend across microbiome science, infection diagnostics, and translational genomics, offering principles that can be applied far beyond the skin. Ultimately, the contributions of this research demonstrate that reproducible, adaptive, and clinically oriented microbiome sequencing is not a distant aspiration but an achievable reality. What emerges is not only a vision for improving wound infection diagnostics but also a broader template for how microbiome science can mature into a reliable, interpretable, and actionable component of precision medicine.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Access to full wet lab protocol

The complete laboratory protocol, titled “Sample collection, preparation, and sequencing protocols for developing metagenomic approaches in skin and wound microbiome analysis”, used in this thesis, including sample collection, preparation, library construction, nanopore sequencing, and adaptive sequencing workflows, has been archived on protocols.io as a fully citable, version-controlled document. The online protocol includes the full step-by-step methods, reagent lists, troubleshooting guidance, metadata, safety notes, and configuration files required to reproduce all wet-lab and adaptive sequencing experiments described in Chapters 2-4. Because of its length and modular structure, the full protocol is not reproduced within this thesis. Instead, it is provided through an openly accessible DOI (10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1) on protocols.io (<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.5jyl88y1dl2w/v1>), in line with current reproducibility and FAIR data standards.

The protocol consists of the following sections:

1. Skin sample collection
2. Culturing & human cell harvesting
3. DNA extraction (Mu-DNA protocol)
4. DNA quality control
5. Mock community samples
6. Skin microbiome samples
7. Library preparation (SQK-RPB004)
8. Flow cell priming and loading
9. Sequencing & adaptive runs

A complete materials list, troubleshooting guidance, warnings, before-you-start instructions, and configuration file references are also included in the online protocol.

Appendix 2: Summary of sequencing libraries

This appendix summarises all sequencing libraries generated for the experiments described in Chapters 2-4. For readability, only short examples of the key identifiers and experimental classifications are included. Full sample metadata, including DNA concentrations, estimated fragment lengths, exact sequencing dates, barcode assignments, and run-level configuration details, are archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007).

Section 1: Libraries used in Chapter 3

Table i: Example rows showing the structure of the sequencing library metadata used for Chapter 3 experiments; full tables are available in chapter3_libraries.tsv (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007).

Run	Barcode	Sample_ID	Dataset
ONT_skin2_cont	barcode07	HM1C_cont	ONT_hummock_nostrain_control
ONT_skin2_cont	barcode08	HM2C_cont	ONT_hummock_nostrain_control
ONT_skin2_cont	barcode09	HM3C_cont	ONT_hummock_nostrain_control

Section 2: Libraries used in Chapter 4

Table ii: Example rows showing the structure of the sequencing library metadata used for Chapter 4 experiments; full tables are available in chapter4_libraries.tsv (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007).

Run	Barcode	Sample_ID	Dataset
ONT_mockecoli2_adapdet1	barcode10	CEG2_adap1	ONT_mock_clinicecoli_ecoliadapdet
ONT_mockecoli2_adapdet2	barcode10	CEG2_adap2	ONT_mock_clinicecoli_ecoliadapdet
ONT_mockecoli2_cont1	barcode10	CEG2_cont1	ONT_mock_clinicecoli_ecoliadapdet

Appendix 3: Operating database creation workflow

This appendix provides a brief overview of the Snakemake workflow used to build the reference databases required for taxonomic and alignment-based analyses. The workflow functions as a modular sub-workflow of the MMCAW pipeline and can be run independently or triggered automatically when executing the full workflow. The complete, executable version, including all Snakemake rules, configuration files, Conda environments, README documentation, and build scripts, is archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17753185) and is openly available on GitHub for versioned access and ongoing development (https://github.com/merfre/Database_Creation_Workflow). Only a high-level description is included here for clarity.

The workflow automates the generation of the three database types used throughout this thesis: a Kraken2 database for read-level taxonomic classification, a CAT database for contig-level annotation, and a BLAST nucleotide database for supplementary alignment-based identification (Table 1.5). It retrieves the required reference FASTA sequences and taxonomy files, builds each database using the appropriate tool-specific commands, and records versions and file checksums to ensure reproducibility. Snakemake manages rule execution, tracks all steps through logs and reports, and organises outputs into consistent subdirectories compatible with downstream components of MMCAW.

All configuration parameters, such as directory paths, software versions, and selected taxonomic sources, are defined in the accompanying config.yaml file and described in detail within the Zenodo archive. The user may enable or disable this module via a configuration option, making it possible either to rebuild the databases or to rely on previously generated versions. The workflow therefore provides a transparent, fully reproducible method for preparing the reference materials required for the analyses in Chapters 2-4. These outputs include the full standard Kraken2 database, CAT reference database, BLAST nucleotide database, and the GRCh38.p14 reference human genome. These databases, along with all metadata and documentation, are permanently archived and accessible via Zenodo.

Appendix 4: MMCAW access and overview

This appendix provides a summary of the Metagenomic Microbiome Combination Analysis Workflow (MMCAW), a reproducible Snakemake-based pipeline developed for the analyses in this thesis. The complete workflow, including all Snakemake rules, configuration files, Conda environments, Python and R scripts, documentation, example inputs, and full outputs, is archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752049) and is openly available on GitHub for versioned access and ongoing development (<https://github.com/merfre/MMCAW>), which should be consulted for implementation details. Only a high-level description is provided here to support understanding and reproducibility.

MMCAW processes Oxford Nanopore sequencing data starting from basecalled and demultiplexed FASTQ files, together with associated metadata such as sequence summaries and sample- and run-level information. Standard metagenomic preprocessing is implemented, including read quality control, optional host read removal, and optional contig assembly using established tools (e.g., fastp, Minimap2, SAMtools, Flye, Seqtk). Downstream, MMCAW integrates three taxonomic assignment strategies, CAT, Kraken2, and BLAST, using databases generated in a dedicated database-creation sub-workflow (Table 1.5). Outputs from these assigners are parsed and summarised with custom Python scripts, producing taxonomic abundance tables and related summaries across multiple taxonomic ranks.

Results from the different assigners are then standardised and combined to enable community analyses and comparison. Diversity metrics and taxonomic profiles are generated with R and Python scripts, and agreement between assigners is evaluated at the contig level to produce consensus classifications and explicit records of disagreement. The workflow also records benchmarking information for each rule, allowing assessment of performance across datasets of varying size and complexity. MMCAW is executed using Conda-managed environments on an HPC system to ensure controlled dependencies and full reproducibility. All components, configuration details, and example outputs referenced in this thesis are available in the accompanying Zenodo archive.

Appendix 5: Summary of figure scripts and inputs

This appendix provides a consolidated summary of all R scripts and input files used to generate the figures for Chapters 2, 3, and 4. The complete set of scripts, input tables, intermediate files, and associated documentation is archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) and organised within the directory structure `figure_scripts/chapterX_figures/`, where each chapter contains a folder of inputs and a folder of R scripts (Table 1.5). Each script is named according to the figure number(s) it produces (e.g., `Chapter3_figure3.R`) and was developed and executed in R v4.2.2 using a variety of widely used CRAN and Bioconductor packages. Only a high-level summary is provided here; all materials required to regenerate every figure in the thesis are contained in the Zenodo archive.

Section 1: Figures used in Chapter 2

The figures for Chapter 2 include reproducibility analyses, taxonomy-assigner comparisons from MMCAW, and workflow performance and scalability results. These scripts rely on input tables representing two repeated microbiome studies, MMCAW assigner outputs, contig-level summaries, metadata, and benchmarking files. The reproducibility figures include ribbon plots, FAIR-principle relationship diagrams, and bar plots. The taxonomy-assigner figures include heatmaps, PCA plots, violin plots, time-series line plots, and taxonomic bar plots generated from Kraken2, CAT, and BLAST outputs (Table 1.4). The MMCAW performance figures include scatterplots, violin plots, and bar plots summarising rule-level runtime, scalability, and other benchmarking metrics. All corresponding inputs and scripts are provided under `figure_scripts/chapter2_figures/`.

Section 2: Figures used in Chapter 3

The figures for Chapter 3 include GPU optimisation results and the human-depletion analyses generated with the ASAW pipeline. The GPU optimisation figures draw on tables of system-level performance measurements and produce scatterplots, bar plots, and violin plots comparing GPU configurations and run behaviour. The human-depletion figures use Kraken2 outputs, sequencing summaries, metadata tables, and ReadFish/ONT adaptive sequencing results to generate bar plots, violin plots, PCA plots, and histograms. For these analyses, the R scripts include an additional note describing the extra processing steps required for ONT in-house adaptive sequencing outputs, which differ slightly from the ReadFish-based workflow; this supplementary code is included as a comment within the relevant scripts. All corresponding inputs and scripts are located in `figure_scripts/chapter3_figures/`.

Section 3: Figures used in Chapter 4

The figures for Chapter 4 include those used to evaluate ReadFish optimisation experiments, adaptive-detection runs analysed with ASAW, and antimicrobial-resistance profiling results. Inputs consist of Kraken2 classification tables, ReadFish outputs, sequencing metadata, ASAW-generated summary tables, and RGI outputs for antimicrobial-resistance gene detection. The figure scripts generate bar plots, violin plots, PCA plots, scatterplots, boxplots, and heatmaps reflecting adaptive detection performance, taxonomic composition, read-level assignments, and ARG profiles across experimental conditions. All associated inputs and scripts are located in `figure_scripts/chapter4_figures/`.

Together, these materials constitute the full computational pathway from raw workflow outputs to final figures, enabling complete reproducibility and transparency. Users wishing to regenerate or adapt any figure should refer to the Zenodo archive for the scripts, data tables, and instructions required for execution.

Appendix 6: Summary of scripts for reference preparation

This appendix provides a concise overview of the scripts used to prepare reference FASTA files, contig-ID lists, and Minimap2 index files required for adaptive sequencing with ReadFish (Table 1.5). All scripts, input files, and intermediate outputs are archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) within the directory structure `adap_seq_setup/reference_prep`, where users may access the complete and executable versions. Only a high-level description is provided here to support understanding and reproducibility.

Section 1: Retrieving reference genomes

Reference preparation begins with a script that retrieves all FASTA files required for the adaptive sequencing experiments. This script uses `wget` to download assembled genomes for three human references (GRCh38.p14, the T2T CHM13 assembly, and the Human Pangenome Project reference), the bacterial species included in the BioFire FilmArray Blood Culture Identification 2 (BCID2) Panel, the reference control strains *E. coli* NCTC 13351 and *S. aureus* NCTC 13373, and the full set of homologous antimicrobial resistance gene (ARG) sequences from the CARD database. These FASTA files are in `adap_seq_setup/reference_prep/fast_files` and form the basis of the reference sets used for enrichment, depletion, and performance benchmarking across experiments.

Section 2: Formatting contig IDs

Because the FASTA files originate from multiple databases with inconsistent sequence naming conventions, a second script performs contig-ID standardisation. This lightweight Bash script reformats or shortens sequence identifiers where necessary, particularly for CARD entries, to ensure compatibility with ReadFish, which requires exact name matching when mapping read chunks against reference indexes or loading specific contig lists.

Section 3: Building Minimap2 indexes

The next step involves creating Minimap2 index (`.mmi`) files from the processed FASTA collections. A single script concatenates FASTA files used together as a unified reference (e.g., bacteria + CARD + GRCh38.p14) and then constructs `.mmi` indexes using Minimap2. Additional indexes are generated for alternative human references used during optimisation experiments. These `.mmi` files are in `adap_seq_setup/reference_prep/mmi_files` and represent the actual target libraries that ReadFish uses for real-time mapping during adaptive sequencing.

Section 4: Creating contig ID lists

Finally, a script generates the contig-ID lists required by ReadFish configuration files. This script extracts specific sequence identifiers from the reference FASTA files and organises them into lists corresponding to experimental targets, including *S. aureus* contigs, *E. coli* contigs,

and all pathogens covered by the BCID2 Panel. Two additional ARG-focused lists are produced: one containing all CARD ARG identifiers and a reduced list corresponding only to ARGs targeted by the BCID2 Panel. These lists were constructed by programmatically retrieving the relevant sequences from the CARD FASTA file, ensuring that the IDs in the lists exactly match the IDs present in the constructed .mmi files. These contig-ID lists are located in `adap_seq_setup/reference_prep/contig_ids` and directly inserted into the appropriate sections of the ReadFish .toml configuration files to define the enrichment or depletion behaviour for each experimental run.

All scripts described above are preserved in full within the Zenodo archive, along with their corresponding FASTA inputs, processed intermediate files, and example configuration templates used throughout the adaptive sequencing experiments.

Appendix 7: Summary of ReadBouncer installation

This appendix provides a brief summary of the software installation files used to install ReadBouncer and its dependencies for the adaptive sequencing experiments. All installation scripts, environment files, and supporting documentation are archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) under `adap_seq_setup/software_installation/readbouncer/`. Only a high-level description is provided here because the full installation instructions and executable files are preserved in the archive.

ReadBouncer v1.2.1 and all required dependencies were compiled from source following the developer instructions provided by Ulrich *et al.* (2022) and the official GitHub repository. A dedicated Conda environment (Python v3.7) was created using Miniconda to ensure controlled dependency management and reproducibility. The archived materials include the complete YAML environment file and the installation script used to build ReadBouncer from source, as well as notes on testing the installation to confirm correct functionality. All steps necessary to recreate the installation environment exactly as used in this thesis can therefore be reproduced directly from the Zenodo archive.

Appendix 8: ReadBouncer configuration files

This appendix summarises the configuration file(s) used for adaptive sequencing with ReadBouncer. All configuration files, including those used for optimisation and final adaptive runs, are archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) under `adap_seq_setup/config_files/readbouncer/`. Files with the suffix “_test.toml” correspond to optimisation runs performed prior to the final experimental sequencing runs.

The configuration structure follows the template and parameter descriptions provided in the ReadBouncer documentation and example `config.toml` on GitHub. Each TOML file specifies the usage mode (build, classify, or target), output and log directories, and an IBF block that defines the Interleaved Bloom Filter index. The IBF block includes parameters such as `kmer_size`, `fragment_size`, `threads`, and lists of `target_files` and/or `deplete_files`, which are provided as comma-separated FASTA or IBF files. In build mode, these reference files are used to construct IBF indexes; in classify and target modes, existing IBF or FASTA files are used together with additional parameters such as expected sequencing error rate, chunk length, and maximum number of chunks used for classification. For adaptive sampling (usage = "target"), the configuration also contains MinKNOW and Basecaller sections specifying the MinKNOW host, port, flow cell identifier, authentication token path, and the basecaller settings (choice of DeepNano or Guppy, basecalling host/port, and Guppy configuration name).

The version archived in Zenodo reflects the exact configuration used for the experiments described in Chapter 3 and includes all modifications made to adapt the generic ReadBouncer template to these data. Users wishing to reproduce or examine any adaptive runs should refer directly to the archived `.toml` file(s).

Appendix 9: Summary of ReadFish installation

This appendix provides a brief summary of the software installation files used to install ReadFish and its dependencies for the adaptive sequencing experiments. All installation scripts, environment files, and supporting documentation are archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) under `adap_seq_setup/software_installation/readfish/`. Only a high-level description is provided here, as the full installation instructions and executable materials are preserved in the archive.

ReadFish v0.0.2 required installation of Guppy v6.0.6 (Wick *et al.*, 2019), Minimap2 v2.26 (Li, 2021), and ReadUntil v3.0.0, all of which were set up within a dedicated Conda environment (Python v3.7) created using Miniconda to ensure controlled dependency management and reproducibility (Table 1.5). The archived materials include the complete YAML environment file and the installation script used to build and configure ReadFish, together with the notes and modifications based on developer instructions from the official GitHub repository and relevant installation discussions. All steps required to recreate the ReadFish installation exactly as used in this thesis can therefore be reproduced directly from the Zenodo archive.

Appendix 10: ReadFish configuration files

This appendix provides an overview of the configuration files used for adaptive sequencing with ReadFish. All TOML files, including those used during optimisation and final adaptive sequencing experiments, are archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) under `adap_seq_setup/config_files/readfish/`. Any file with the suffix “_test.toml” corresponds to optimisation runs performed prior to final data collection.

The configuration structure follows the template and parameter descriptions provided by the ReadFish developers on GitHub (Table 1.5). Each TOML includes: (i) connection information for MinKNOW (device, host, port, experiment name, and path to authentication token); (ii) basecalling settings specifying the Guppy server address and configuration file; (iii) paths to the reference .mmi index containing all target and deplete sequences; and (iv) one or more rule blocks defining enrichment and/or depletion behaviour. Each rule specifies lists of contig IDs to enrich or deplete, the mapping strategy (`map_strategy`), and parameters such as minimum match length and required mapping confidence.

Section 1: Configurations used in Chapter 3

The configuration files supporting Chapter 3 (host depletion experiments) are located in `adap_seq_setup/config_files/readfish/chapter3_config/`. These TOMLs implement depletion-only adaptive sampling, using the human reference genome (GRCh38.p14) as the depletion target with default ReadFish mapping thresholds. The purpose of this configuration set is to remove human-derived reads as early as possible while allowing bacterial reads to continue sequencing, enabling evaluation of host depletion using both ReadFish and ONT in-house adaptive sampling.

Section 2: Configurations used in Chapter 4

The configuration files supporting Chapter 4 (adaptive detection experiments) are in `adap_seq_setup/config_files/readfish/chapter4_config/` and include all optimisation TOMLs and all final experimental TOMLs for the chapter. These configurations include a mixture of depletion and enrichment rules, targeting different combinations of human, bacterial, and antimicrobial resistance gene (ARG) sequences. They also include modified mapping thresholds designed to enforce strict matches for bacterial and ARG targets while retaining default mapping behaviour for the human genome. The TOML filenames indicate the experimental focus, corresponding to enrichment of *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, or all pathogens on the BioFire BCID2 panel, respectively. These files represent the full range of adaptive detection strategies evaluated in Chapter 4.

Appendix 11: GPU and Guppy optimisation

This appendix summarises the benchmarking and optimisation procedures used to determine optimal GPU parameters for Guppy v6.0.6 basecalling. All raw notes, detailed test logs, and benchmarking scripts are archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) under `adap_seq_setup/guppy_gpu_optimisation/`. The experiments were conducted on a dedicated bioinformatics workstation (AMD Ryzen 5 5600X CPU, NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 Ti GPU, Ubuntu v20.04 LTS).

To assess the upper performance limits of the GPU prior to Guppy testing, the FurMark GPU stress-testing suite was used. FurMark benchmarking (NVIDIA RTX 3080 Ti) provided baseline information on thermal stability, core utilisation, and maximum sustained load, ensuring that subsequent Guppy optimisation steps were tested within safe and stable operating conditions.

Guppy optimisation followed the benchmarking strategy described by Sirselim (<https://gist.github.com/sirselim/2ebe2807112fae93809aa18f096dbb94>), adapted for the hardware configuration and for Guppy v6.0.6. A series of controlled tests were performed in which individual Guppy parameters were varied, including the number of callers, number of GPU runners per device, chunk size, and chunks per runner, while all other settings were held constant. Each run processed the same set of ONT FAST5 files, and completion time was measured as the primary performance metric. The aim was to identify parameter combinations that maximised basecalling throughput without reducing accuracy or causing GPU instability.

Because the optimisation process involved numerous iterations and extensive exploratory testing, the full benchmarking notes are not reproduced in this thesis. Instead, all raw results, run-by-run notes, and summary tables (exported directly from Notion as PDF) have been deposited in the Zenodo archive. The final Guppy command used for all basecalling and both adaptive and non-adaptive runs (Appendix 1: Section 9) in this thesis reflects the best-performing combination of parameters determined from these tests.

Appendix 12: Reference optimisation tests

This appendix summarises the evaluation of alternative human reference genome assemblies for adaptive detection with ReadFish. Tests assessed whether replacing GRCh38.p14 with the T2T-CHM13 assembly, the Human Pangenome Reference Consortium sequences, or combinations of human reference assemblies would improve mapping behaviour or adaptive decision accuracy. All reference preparation steps followed the process described in [Appendix 6](#) (Summary of scripts for reference preparation). The associated FASTA files, concatenated references, minimap2 index (.mmi) builds, and scripts used to run ReadFish are archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752007) under `adap_seq_setup/reference_tests/`.

These optimisation attempts were unsuccessful because ReadFish consistently returned fatal memory or indexing errors when used with any reference exceeding ~4 GB in FASTA size, and both the T2T and pangenome assemblies produced file sizes above this threshold. The archived folder includes the corresponding error logs and a README documenting the exact failure messages and conditions under which they occurred. As a result, GRCh38.p14 was retained as the human reference for all adaptive sequencing runs in this thesis.

Appendix 13: ASAW access and overview

This appendix provides a summary of the Adaptive Sequencing Analysis Workflow (ASAW), a Snakemake-based pipeline developed for the analyses in Chapters 3 and 4. The full workflow, including all Snakemake rules, configuration files, Conda environments, Python and R scripts, documentation, example inputs, and complete outputs, is archived in Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17752062) and is openly available on GitHub for versioned access and ongoing development (https://github.com/merfre/Adaptive_Sequencing_Analysis_Workflow). Only a high-level description is provided here to support understanding and reproducibility.

ASAW was designed to analyse adaptive sequencing experiments on human metagenomic microbiome samples, enabling consistent comparison between control runs and ReadFish-mediated adaptive sequencing runs. The workflow begins with Guppy v6.0.6 basecalled and demultiplexed data, together with read ID lists, sequence summaries, and sample metadata. It incorporates standard metagenomic preprocessing steps closely aligned with those in MMCAW, including read quality control with fastp, optional host filtering using Minimap2 and SAMtools, and optional contig assembly via Flye, with Seqtk used throughout to generate sequence statistics (Table 1.5).

ASAW includes integrated taxonomic profiling of retained and rejected reads using Kraken2 and its standard database and embeds modular R and Python scripts to calculate and visualise alpha and beta diversity measures, taxonomic abundances, and sequencing metrics across runs. These analyses support direct comparison of adaptive and control datasets, quantify host depletion efficiency, and characterise changes in microbial community structure. A dedicated module processes rejected reads, from ReadFish read-ID lists, allowing reconstruction of their taxonomic and sequencing characteristics after demultiplexing. This ensures that both enriched and depleted fractions are analysed consistently across all runs.

ASAW also provides automated summaries of Guppy sequencing statistics, barcode distributions, and rejected-versus-retained read counts, enabling systematic evaluation of adaptive sequencing performance. The workflow records execution logs and benchmarking information for each Snakemake rule, supporting reproducibility and transparent assessment of computational performance. All workflow components, parameters, and example outputs referenced in Chapters 3 and 4 are included in the accompanying Zenodo archive.